

SafeHabitus

Deliverable 4.1

Current and future drivers of agricultural change: Assessing the implications for working conditions and occupational stress amongst farmers and farmworkers

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Deliverable	Deliverable 4.1 Current and future drivers of agricultural change: Assessing the implications for working conditions and occupational stress amongst farmers and farm workers
Due Date	31/08/2024
Actual submission date	30/08/2024
Project start date	01/01/2023
Duration	48 months
Work Package concerned	WP4
Concerned work package leader	Černič Istenič Majda
Dissemination level	[x] PU : Public (must be available on the website)
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Revision history	13/08/2024 Draft version 18/08/2024 1 st review 27/08/2024 2 nd review 30/08/2024 Final version 27/01/2025 Revised version In the revised version of this deliverable, the objectives of this study were additionally emphasised, the methodology of the literature review was expanded, the starting points in the chapters were clarified and refined, and the results of the analysis were further synthesised and captured in the discussions and conclusions sections. The general conclusions were supplemented with suggestions and recommendations for policy decision-makers.
Statement of originality	This report presents the results of original research undertaken by the authors listed.

Summary

SafeHabitus implements a participative foresight process, informed by research that enhances the capacity of all stakeholders to collectively and collaboratively translate longer-term challenges reshaping occupational health and safety, into extant or new policy options. Success in this endeavour will mean early identification of challenges and opportunities leading to the development and implementation of appropriate policy options that support improvements in occupational health and safety and the attractiveness of farming. The foresight process is adapted from the participatory approach developed by the EU Joint Research Council and follows a systematic approach to identifying, assessing, analysing and synthesising the drivers and root causes of social and economic change that may impact occupational health and safety and the attractiveness of farming as a job in the period to 2060.

This report presents the detailed results of research undertaken to evaluate the extant body of literature concerned with working conditions in agriculture. The aim of the study was to identify and assess the sources of stress which farmers and farm workers are exposed to in their working environment, which affect their safety, health (both physical and mental) and well-being, and have an impact on long-term food security. As the environment in which farmers and farm workers work is changing, the study also sought to identify the causes - the drivers of change - that influence working conditions in agriculture and the occurrence of sources of stress. In doing so it contributes to one of SafeHabitus' code objectives, namely to enhance understanding of the social and behavioural drivers of change on farming in the period to 2060 and assess the impact of current and future working and labour conditions on perceived attractiveness of farming or working in farming as a job.

The analysis, based on a systematic literature review using the PRISMA approach, covers four main topics identified in a workshop.

Chapter 1 explores psychosocial challenges in farming, identifying seven categories of stressors: economic pressures, social and community issues, environmental stressors, occupational hazards, health and safety risks, regulatory changes, and market dynamics.

Chapter 2 analyses how farming culture influences safety, health, and well-being. It identifies four main cultural stressors: gender identities, structural vulnerability and discrimination, ruptures in the moral economy, and risk perceptions and safety beliefs.

Chapter 3 focuses on social protection for farmers and farm workers, examining formal and informal social protection, discrimination and structural issues, and cultural and language barriers.

Chapter 4 investigates the impact of modern agricultural technologies on farmers' well-being, particularly automatic milking systems. Stressors include information overload, techno-intrusion, equipment maintenance, increased workload, animal training, lack of technological expertise, and debt burden.

The literature review shows that there are different sources of stress, both those that farmers can control and those that they cannot, which need to be taken into account when designing appropriate policy measures.

The review identifies several drivers of change affecting working conditions in farming: neoliberalism, globalisation, technological advancement, adoption of agroecological principles, labour shortages, increased reliance on migrant workers, and climate change.

The most vulnerable groups include migrant and seasonal farm workers (especially women), women on family farms, children, and young farmers, particularly those who are educated and skilled.

The literature provides examples of good practices to address farmers' and farm workers' stress, such as improving education and healthcare, identifying environmental microaggressions, and empowering migrant workers through participatory education.

The report concludes by highlighting the need for further research, both in terms of content and methodology, to better understand and address the challenges faced by farmers and farm workers in an evolving agricultural landscape.

Table of contents

- INTRODUCTION: Change, Uncertainty and the Future of Farmers* 8
- CHAPTER 1: FARMING AND PSYCHOSOCIAL CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES*..... 14
 - STARTING POINTS 14
 - MAIN FINDINGS 17
 - DRIVERS OF CHANGE AND MEGA-TRENDS..... 20
 - CONCLUSIONS 21
 - REFERENCES 24
- CHAPTER 2: CULTURE OF FARMING, FARM SAFETY AND FARMER WELL-BEING* 26
 - STARTING POINTS 26
 - MAIN FINDINGS 27
 - DRIVERS OF CHANGE AND MEGA-TRENDS..... 46
 - CONCLUSIONS 48
 - REFERENCES 51
- CHAPTER 3: SOCIAL PROTECTION OF FARMERS AND FARMWORKERS* 54
 - STARTING POINTS 54
 - MAIN FINDINGS 56
 - DRIVERS OF CHANGE AND MEGA-TRENDS..... 64
 - CONCLUSIONS 64
 - REFERENCES 67
- CHAPTER 4: IMPACT OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN AGRICULTURE ON THE SAFETY, HEALTH AND WELL-BEING OF FARMERS AND FARMWORKERS* 69
 - STARTING POINTS 69
 - MAIN FINDINGS 75
 - DRIVERS OF CHANGE AND MEGA-TRENDS..... 76
 - CONCLUSIONS 77
 - REFERENCES 78
- GENERAL CONCLUSIONS* 82

APPENDIX 1: ANALYSED REFERENCES	89
APPENDIX 2: DETAILED ANALYSIS AND REVIEW OF STUDIES ON TOPIC 1 IN CHAPTER 1	118
APPENDIX 3: DETAILED ANALYSIS AND REVIEW OF STUDIES ON TOPIC 2 IN CHAPTER 2	127
APPENDIX 4: DETAILED ANALYSIS AND REVIEW OF STUDIES ON TOPIC 3 IN CHAPTER 3	135
APPENDIX 5: DETAILED ANALYSIS AND REVIEW OF STUDIES ON TOPIC 4 IN CHAPTER 4	141
APPENDIX 6: REPORT FROM THE WORKSHOP ON PSYCHOSOCIAL STRESSORS/RISKS IN FARMING	153

Tables

Table 1: Article no., authors, publication year, country of study, year of study conducted, study type and target group(s)	118
Table 2: Article no., author(s), publication year, country of study, year of study conducted, study type and target group(s)	127
Table 3: Article no., authors, publication year, country of study, year of study conducted, study type and target group(s)	135
Table 4: Article no., authors, publication year, country of study, year of study conducted, study type and target group(s)	141

Figures

Figure 1: Article selection and inclusion process using the PRISMA workflow approach	12
Figure 2: Psychosocial risks and workers' health, derived from Šprah (2016)	14
Figure 3: The relationship between well-being and health, derived from: WHO (2013) and Stoll et al., (2012)	16

Acronyms

AI: artificial intelligence

AMS: automatic milking system

CIWD: cognitive impairment with disability

CSA: community-supported agriculture

CMS: conventional milking system

COVID-19: coronavirus disease 2019

FEMS scale: Female Microaggressions Scale

EU: European Union

EU-OSHA: European Agency for Safety and Health at Work

FPSICO: psychosocial factors

EM: microaggression

GIS: Geographic Information Systems

GNSS: Global Navigation Satellite Systems

GPS: Global Positioning Systems

H2A visas: Temporary Agricultural Employment of Foreign Workers (USA Department of Labor)

HRI: human-robot interaction

ISO: International Organisation for Standardisation

IoT: the Internet of Things

LGBT+: lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender

LGBTQIA+: Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender, Queer, Intersex, Asexual, and more

ML: machine learning

NGO: Non-governmental organisation / Non-profit organisation

OHS: Occupational safety and health

PICO: Population, Issue, Comparators and Outcomes approach

PLF: Precision Livestock Farming

PRISMA: Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses

PTSD: post-traumatic stress disorder

R&I: research and innovation

SARS-CoV-2: Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2

SLR: Systematic Literature Review method

Teagasc: Irish pronunciation: [ˈtʲiagəsˠk], meaning "Instruction"), semi-state authority in Ireland responsible for research and development, training and advisory services in the agri-food sector

US: United States

USA: United States of America

VMU: Vytautas Magnus University, public university in Kaunas, Lithuania

WHO: World Health Organization

WSN: wireless sensor networks

ZRC SAZU: Scientific Research Centre of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts, public research institute

INTRODUCTION: Change, Uncertainty and the Future of Farmers

The global agricultural and food industry is facing a number of long-term challenges: The world's population is growing, natural resources are coming under increasing pressure, exacerbated by climate change, and the global agricultural market continues to expand, to name but a few. Against this backdrop, agriculture in the EU faces the challenge of securing its place as a resilient and environmentally sustainable industry while remaining competitive both locally and globally and responding to changing societal demands (Boix-Fayos and de Vente, 2023; Pe'er et al., 2020; Prandecki et al., 2021; Swinbank, 2021). There is an assumption that those working in farming, whether as experts, policy makers or farmers and farmworkers, will be able to respond to these challenges and successfully contribute to their resolution. However, recent farmer revolts in the EU show that the proposed solutions, such as the Green Deal, are not in line with some groups of farmers' views, needs and capacities (Bourget, 2024). Furthermore, the agri-food sector is not only facing the problems mentioned above, but also a critical and long-lasting labour and skills shortage and the unattractiveness of the farming profession, which could challenge the transition of the agri-food sector towards a more sustainable and resilient future.

Whilst agriculture is characterised by processes of constant change, recent decades have seen a number of forces combine and threaten the viability of some farms and the overall attractiveness of the sector (Crowley and Meredith, 2014). Conventional drivers of change, i.e. economic pressures and low incomes, and high barriers to entry, have underpinned long-term trends of an ageing workforce and farm consolidation, intensification and specialisation in agriculture (Giller et al., 2021). More recently, new drivers of change have come to the fore, intersecting with these conventional drivers and amplifying the pace of change, and with it, the level of uncertainty regarding the future of farming (Woods, 2019). Unlike conventional drivers of change, these new and emerging processes are fast-paced and largely beyond the control of individual farmers, e.g. 'weird weather', changing societal understanding of and perceptions of farming and farmers, and access to commodity and financial markets.

A significant body of future studies research has developed in the EU over the past decade that focuses on identifying and teasing out the implications of contemporary and emerging drivers of agricultural restructuring (Bock et al., 2020; Bock and Krzysztofowicz, 2021; Copus et al., 2011; European Commission, 2021). A review of these studies concluded that farming and rural areas are facing a wide array of locally and globally interconnected drivers of change associated with climate change (or policy responses to climate change), ecological collapse, food security, digital exclusion and structural limitations; these drivers threaten the capacity of communities to avail of opportunities presented by change such as access to capital (Brunori and Mazzocchi, 2020). While these studies primarily focus on understanding the potential implications of drivers for the future structure of agriculture and rural areas, they often overlook crucial aspects of farming. Specifically, there is limited consideration given to the implications for working conditions of farmers, farm workers, and farm families; the effects on farming practices and day-to-day operations; the quality of life for those involved in agriculture; and, the long-term attractiveness of farming as a profession. In essence, many of these studies do not consider the potential implications for farmers, farm workers and rural communities.

The research activities within the SafeHabitus programme attempt to fill this knowledge gap and create the basis for a SafeHabitus Foresight Study which is due to be completed in 2025. This study, led by ZRC SAZU research team with the support of Teagasc and VDU, aims to highlight the relevant literature, identify sources of stress in relation to the drivers of change therein, and describe the impact of these sources and drivers on working conditions in agriculture. This will allow for the future selection of drivers, informed by experts in agriculture and occupational health and safety. At that point, as we develop future scenarios, we will be able to apply the knowledge gained from this review to understand the implications of the drivers for working conditions and, ultimately, the attractiveness of farming.

The concept of 'working conditions' as applied to studies of farmers or farm workers is the main focus of this report encompasses a broad range of factors that affect the day-to-day experience of farming

work/labour (EU-OSHA Foresight Report 2020). Working conditions in agriculture refer to the physical, psychological, social, and economic circumstances under which farmers and farm workers undertake work. Working conditions include the physical environment (exposure to weather conditions), work organization (working hours), workload and intensity, economic aspects (income and financial security), social factors (relationships with family, employers/employees), health and well-being (physical and mental health risks), access to health or social services, and technological aspects (level of mechanisation and automation or digital literacy requirements).

This definition underpins and guides the extensive body of work presented in this report. This work is structured around four key topics that were identified through a preliminary scoping review and two workshops which took place in March and April 2023. The topics are:

Topic 1 Farming and psychosocial challenges and opportunities

Topic 2 Culture of farming, farm safety and farmers well-being

Topic 3 Social protection of farmers and farm workers

Topic 4 Technology – impact on the future health and safety of farmers/farmworkers

It is important to note that the topics do not map directly to individual conceptual elements of ‘working conditions’, rather they overlap. As a consequence, issues such as workload or working time can be seen as cross cutting themes that link different topics.

Overview of Methodology

We used the Systematic Literature Review (SLR) method to review the main findings of research on psychosocial risks and occupational safety and health in the group of farmers and farm workers. We chose this approach because the SRL method is a powerful tool for summarising findings and gaining a comprehensive understanding of a research topic. By following a structured approach, from defining the research question to summarising and reporting the results, this approach ensures transparency, rigour and repeatability.

We recognise that the SLR methodology is rigorous, but it is not without limitations. The most important deficits that we also identify in our SLR on psychosocial risks and occupational safety and health in the group of farmers and farm workers are as follows:

- Database dependency: The scope of the review depended on the selected databases and our search terms.
- Language bias: We limit the studies to the English language, which may lead to the exclusion of other relevant research.
- Publication bias: Studies with negative or invalid results may be published less frequently, which may lead to a bias in our results.
- Resource intensive: The implementation of an SLR required a considerable amount of time and effort, especially in the screening and synthesis phase, where an important part of the output could be overlooked

Recognising these limitations is critical to interpreting the results and understanding the scope of the presented review. Despite its limitations, this methodology remains a cornerstone of evidence-based research that informs policy decisions and provides directions for future studies, which was also one of the aims of the current study.

Identification of studies and search strategy

A 3-step search strategy included an initial search of Web of Science and Scopus, followed by an analysis of keywords contained in the titles and abstracts. Studies published in full-text, peer reviewed and in English language were retrieved. The time period of the hits in Web of Science covered the period from 1974 to 2023, while in Scopus there was no time limit and the results ranged from 1924 to 2023. The PRISMA workflow (Page et al., 2021) was used as a reference for the mapping/identification, screening and selection/inclusion of articles/studies (Figure 1).

The search of the Web of Science dataset was conducted on 15 November 2023 and retrieved 692 search results using the following search stream:

“farm” OR “agri*” (Title) and “envir*” OR “condi*” (Title) and “health*” OR “safe*” OR “well-be*” (Title) or “farm*” OR “agri*” (Author Keywords) and “envir*” OR “condi*” (Author Keywords) and “health*” OR “safe*” OR “well-be*” (Author Keywords) and English (Languages) and Review Article (Exclude – Document Types)*

The search with the Scopus dataset was performed on 17 November 2023 and returned 4277 results using the following search stream in the typical search form for this dataset:

(TITLE-ABS-KEY (farm OR agri*) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (work* AND envir* OR work* AND condi*) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (health* OR safe* OR well-be*)) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE, “English”)) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE, “ar”))*

A total of 4.936 search results were imported into the Endnote Reference Manager 21.2. and considered for inclusion in the review. Then, 4.329 records were removed in the next phase after checking for duplicates, reviews and non-matching search results (Figure 1).

Study selection and inclusion / exclusion criteria

In the first phase of the literature review we examine closely four key topics that were identified through a preliminary scoping review and two workshops which took place in March and April 2023. In developing the preliminary research questions for each topic, we followed the PICO (Population, Intervention, Comparison, and Outcome) principle, which originated in medical studies but, with some modifications, is increasingly being applied in other fields (Cooper et al., 2108; Eldawlatly et al., 2018; Mengista et al., 2020; Younker & Radunovic 2022). The research questions developed according to the PICO principle focus on 1. identifying the key group(s), 2. the problem relevant to the topic under investigation, 3. comparing the situation/problems of the group(s) under investigation with other groups, and 4. identifying lessons learnt, e.g. best practises, recommendations for policy makers, recommendations for further research, etc. Using this framework helps to define the exclusion/inclusion criteria for the selection of articles and therefore the scope of the study. The preliminary questions for the four themes were:

Topic 1: Farming and psychosocial challenges and opportunities (Main research question: *“What causes stress to farmers and farmworkers and how does it affect their mental health and well-being?”*)

Topic 2: Culture of farming, farm safety and farmers well-being (Main research question: *“How does farming culture shape the safety, health and wellbeing of farmers and farm workers? – focusing on farmers’ and farm workers’ understanding of risks, hazards and problematic relationships in their workplace and changes that affect the farming (safety) culture.”*)

Topic 3: Social protection of farmers and farm workers (Main research question: *“How does social protection or the lack thereof affect the health and safety at work and quality of life of farmers and farm workers?”*)

Topic 4: Technology – impact on the future health and safety of farmers/farmworkers (Main research question: “*What is the impact of the use of modern technologies in agriculture on the working environment, safety, health and well-being of farmers and farmworkers?*”)

603 studies that met the inclusion criteria were screened based on the title first for appropriateness, then the abstract of the studies was checked by three researchers.

122 studies (Topic 1), 94 studies (Topic 2), 165 studies (Topic 3) and 44 studies (Topic 4) for which PDFs were retrieved (see Appendix 1: ANALYSED REFERENCES) have been screened for eligibility before inclusion in the next phase. Studies where working conditions, safety, physical and mental health and well-being in farming were not in the focus of research were excluded. Finally, the full studies were screened using specific inclusion/exclusion criteria defined within certain four Topics before being included in the final review where data extraction was performed.

Data were extracted from the included studies and described by using Microsoft Excel 2016. Extracted data included:

- Study information: author(s), publication year, and journal;
- Study design: methodological approach, such as randomized controlled trials or qualitative studies;
- Sample characteristics: demographics, sample size, and setting;
- Interventions and outcomes: description of interventions, outcomes measured, and key findings.

Data extraction ensured that all necessary information is systematically collected and ready for synthesis. Due to the heterogeneity of included studies, we utilized a narrative synthesis to analyse findings. A detailed process for selecting studies for the final list of selected articles for each of the four Topics is presented separately later in this report, as they depended on specific research questions related to the four previously identified topics. A detailed analysis and overview of the studies for each topic can be found in Appendices 2, 3, 4 and 5.

Figure 1: Article selection and inclusion process using the PRISMA workflow approach.

In order to validate the ongoing work on the literature review with the experts in this field, an online workshop was held on 20 June 2024, the minutes of which are reproduced in Appendix 6.

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CHAPTER 1: FARMING AND PSYCHOSOCIAL CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

STARTING POINTS

The reviewed studies in TOPIC 1 focus on identifying significant stressors among farmers and farmworkers and their impact on mental health and well-being.

Psychosocial risks and farmer's health

The experience of being a farmer or a member of a farming family has changed profoundly in recent decades and is likely to continue to do so. These changes are related to, among other things, the loss of farm income, the position of farmers in society and societal expectations and demographic changes in their own communities. Many farmers feel that key stressors such as government policies are beyond their control, which adds to the stress. There is evidence that these changes have contributed to farmers and their families becoming more vulnerable to stress (Lobley et al., 2004). In addition to the social context, the psychosocial work environment and the nature of the work itself also have an important influence on the health and well-being of (farm) workers.

There is strong and growing evidence that the link between work-related health complaints and exposure to psychosocial risks, or an interaction between physical and psychosocial risks, leads to a variety of health consequences for the individual worker and the organisation. Exposure to psychosocial risks can affect the mental and physical health of workers, through a stress-mediated pathway. In addition, the health and resilience of an organisation (e.g. absenteeism, high turnover, lower productivity and organisational commitment) can also be affected (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Psychosocial risks and workers' health, derived from Šprah (2016)

Psychosocial risks are defined as the psychological and social aspects (hazards/pressures/actors) of the work, the workplace, the workers, the work organisation and the wider environment that cause feelings of stress and consequently increase the likelihood of health complications of workers. Psychosocial stress is associated with the so-called indirect risk of endangering the health of workers and the work organisation (Figure 2). Broader (social and organisational circumstances of work) and

narrower (characteristics of work and its management) factors of work and work organisation can be different sources of stress (hazards) and are understood as risks to workers' health and well-being (mental, physical and social). They also have an impact on the economic performance of companies (more sick leave and absenteeism, lower productivity at work - presentism, employee turnover, etc.), employee morale and loyalty to the company may decrease, hostility and other negative emotions may increase. On the other hand, various physical, biological and chemical hazards in the workplace can also represent a form of psychosocial stress, as they have psychological effects in addition to the immediate health risks (poisoning, injury, etc.). They can make individuals feel threatened, overwhelmed, insecure, anxious and uncomfortable, which in turn increases the level of stress experienced. It can therefore be said that physical, chemical and biological stresses pose direct risks to workers' health (impacts, falls, poisoning, injuries, with immediate health consequences), while psychosocial stresses mainly act as indirect risks by triggering stress and thus having an indirect impact on well-being and health. If employees and the work organisation do not know how to deal with stress properly (recognising sources of stress and limiting or eliminating them, knowing techniques and skills for emotional and physical relief, etc.), excessive stress arises, which severely affects the health of employees as well as the "health" of the work organisation (Šprah, 2016).

Psychosocial risk factors include aspects such as job control, work schedules, work overload, interpersonal relationships in the workplace and organisational culture. Dealing with psychosocial risks in the workplace requires appropriate risk assessment and the establishment of measures aimed at both the organisation and the individual.

Psychosocial risks in agriculture, may emerge from poor working conditions relative to work design, organisation, management and/or the workplace's social context. Psychosocial risks, stress and mental health issues are important challenges facing the sector, as up to half of farmers and farm workers exceed 48-hour weeks. Rates of stress, anxiety, burnout, suicide and depression are high. For example, one in four Irish farmers face burnout, and in France, one farmer suicide takes place every two days (EU-OSHA – European Agency for Safety and Health at Work, 2024).

Psychosocial risks in the agricultural sector may also include equipment breakdown, ergonomics, financial instability and insecurity, regulatory pressures, health concerns, and professional status. Risk differs according to farming typology (e.g. dairy farming versus crop production), as some farmers and farm workers are more impacted by chemical exposure and others are more impacted by risks associated with animal husbandry (EU-OSHA – European Agency for Safety and Health at Work, 2024).

As the focus of SafeHabitus is on well-being and consequently on understanding work-related stressors and how to change them and on developing practical interventions that meet the needs of farmers and farmworkers needs, we should first emphasise the relationship between well-being and mental health and exposure to work-related hazards, an interaction between physical and psychosocial hazards.

How to define mental health?

The terms mental health and wellbeing are often used interchangeably, but research suggests that while they are related, they are conceptually distinct. It may be useful to consider wellbeing as a broader concept that encompasses a range of factors experienced at individual, community and national levels. Mental health refers to a whole spectrum of experiences ranging from good mental health to mental ill health. Good mental health means more than the absence of illness. It is a dynamic state of inner balance in which a person regularly and consistently experiences positive feelings, thoughts and behaviours, can respond appropriately to normal negative emotions and situations, and is able to contribute positively to their community. A mental illness is a condition and the experience of thoughts, feelings, symptoms, and/or behaviours that cause distress and limit functioning, that negatively impact a person's daily life, and that may receive or be eligible for a clinical diagnosis. Mental health is defined or better understood as a continuum with two dimensions – mental disorder and mental well-being. Continuum means that mental health can constantly change from the positive to the negative pole or

vice versa. Since it consists of two interrelated but separate dimensions, mental well-being can exist despite an existing mental disorder and vice versa.

Mental well-being does not simply mean the presence or absence of a mental disorder. A mental disorder is therefore not inherently an obstacle to well-being.

- A person with a mental disorder can be satisfied with life, have fulfilling relationships, feel that life has meaning, adapt and contribute fruitfully to the community.
- Conversely, a person without a mental disorder may have low mental well-being, be dissatisfied with life, feel pressured and lack trusting relationships.

Being mentally healthy is not only to have no mental disorder, but is a more comprehensive state. Mental health manifests itself in our: emotional, psychological and social well-being, in our attitude to ourselves, to other people and to the world.

The relationship between well-being and mental health

The relationship between well-being and mental health is well illustrated in the picture from the WHO (2013) (Figure 3).

Figure 3: The relationship between well-being and health, derived from: WHO (2013) and Stoll et al., (2012)

Both physical and mental health can affect well-being. Recent acute health problems have the greatest impact on well-being, but longer-term chronic illnesses also have an effect on well-being. The relationship between health and wellbeing is not just one-way, there are a number of correlations between wellbeing and physical health outcomes such as:

- an improved immune system response,
- cardiovascular health,
- higher pain tolerance,
- longer life expectancy,
- slower progression of disease and reproductive health.

Farmers' mental health

The results of the study on Farmers' Psychosocial Work Environment and mental health (Lundqvist et al., 2022) show that the health and safety risks identified in the psychosocial work environment of farmers are as follows: Workload, finances, climate change and weather conditions, crime, globalisation, laws and regulations, masculine norms and gender differences, loneliness, isolation and lack of support. Other risk factors include exposure to pesticides, living near predators, modern technology and automation systems, and new risks such as the COVID-19 pandemic.

Problems related to poor mental health, including depression, anxiety, suicide attempts, etc., are generally more prevalent among farmers, especially older farmers, than in other occupational groups. Farmers have a higher incidence of depression and suicide attempts than other occupational groups, and mental illness among farmers has increased in recent years (Lundqvist et al., 2022).

Farmers' ability to cope and recover from stress

In terms of farmers' ability to cope with and recover from stress, it is important to examine how farmers themselves deal with the stress they face in their working lives. A literature study on farmers' mental health found that resilience is the most important health factor for farmers (Hagen et al., 2019).

Farmers reported that support from family and other social support, nature and animals, and the fact that work on the farm is perceived as meaningful helped to strengthen their resilience.

Planned work in TOPIC 1

The aim of the SafeHabitus project is therefore to address all these issues and to identify the current occupational stress factors to which different groups of farmers and farmworkers are exposed.

The question of what causes farmers and farmworkers stress and influence their mental health and well-being is dealt with in Topic 1.

We focused on identifying the most significant stressors among farmers and farmworkers and their impact on mental health and well-being. We also identified various concepts, terms, models and theories in the studies examined, which deal with the perceived health and safety risks of the working and living environment of the group under investigation. In addition, we reflected on drivers of change and mega-trends, the factors that may influence the future of farming in relation to mental health best deduced indirectly from discussions and conclusions of the literature.

Steps of systematic literature review for TOPIC 1

In the third step, three researchers reviewed 603 articles based on titles and abstracts using the initial TOPIC 1 questions. All articles were voted on by consensus – if two reviewers selected the same article for further review, that article was accepted. After the title and abstract screening, 122 articles were suitable for the next step. In the fourth step, the articles were screened using the exclusion criteria (no research was conducted; the research is neither quantitative nor qualitative; the country is not relevant for the study; there is no relevant core target group; not at least one of the initial questions raised in TOPIC 1 is addressed). Exclusion criteria for TOPIC 1 were as follows: Core target groups: All individuals who are not farmers/farm workers/farm owners were excluded. We excluded all studies whose geographical location was not Europe, North America, USA, Canada, Australia or New Zealand, we excluded all studies whose language was not English and all qualitative studies. Regarding the content of the review, we excluded all studies that dealt with physical diseases and disabilities. An article was excluded if it met one or more of the exclusion criteria. After the fourth step, 31 articles were selected for the fifth – final analysis and were reviewed in-full (see Figure 1). A detailed analysis and overview of the studies on this topic can be found in Appendix 2.

MAIN FINDINGS

The general aim of the studies examined in TOPIC 1 was to identify the important stressors affecting mental health and well-being of farmers and/or farm workers and, in particular, their impact on mental health. For TOPIC 1, the specific variables were divided into 3 interrelated thematic strands: sources of stress, well-being and mental health.

A. Sources of stress

The sources of stress identified can be grouped in different categories. For ease of reference, we have organised the variables in the same categories as we did for reporting the results.

Identified stressors:

1. **Economic pressures:** financial instability, family/personal finances, debt, poverty
2. **Social and community problems:** isolation and loneliness, family dynamics/conflict, adverse childhood experiences, daily life, marital status, education level, housing conditions

(number of people per bedroom, perceived safety of self and belongings, presence of a key to the front door, presence of storage space in the bedroom, privacy in the restroom, number of house rule violations), drug and alcohol use, concerns about documents, fear of deportation, social support, intentions to leave

3. **Environmental stressors:** unfavourable weather conditions due to climate change (floods, droughts, pesticide exposure)

4. **Occupational or work-related stressors:** workload, job tension, lack of autonomy, long working hours, pressure to perform, labour availability, worker interest, role definition, rigid job requirements, heavy physical work, job description, role definition, personal (employee) relationships at work, pace of work, time pressure, supervisory support, worries about the future

5. **Health and safety risks:** injuries, chronic illness, pesticide exposure, lack of access to (mental) health services, suicidal behaviour, dementia and cognitive impairment

6. **Regulatory and policy changes:** involvement of farmers in long-term evaluation programmes and changes in farming practise, e.g. through participation in agri-environmental programmes

7. **Market dynamics:** global competition, society/consumers' expectations conversion to another practice - organic farming.

Among the studies, we would like to draw particular attention to the study "Psychosocial stressors among Mexican migrant farmworkers" [383], which systematically lists 18 categories of specific stressors associated with being a migrant farmworker in the Midwestern United States. Some of these stressors are also found in other studies. Stressors listed: seclusion from family or friends, rigid job requirements, unpredictable work/lodging and uprooting, low family income/poverty/poor pay, poor housing, language barriers education of self or children, hard physical labour, lack of transportation/unreliable transportation (to and from work), exploitation by employer, lack of childcare, geographic isolation, limited access to health care, discrimination, undocumented status, adjustment to new environment, concerns about socialisation of children, paperwork for social services. Some studies focused explicitly on the stress levels of different groups in farming (Latino migrant farmworkers in Nebraska, [465], [466], older rural couples [469]).

B. Well-being

The following variables were placed in this category: well-being, life satisfaction, with one subcategory: satisfaction with work in farming [469] and the other: access to farm health services, which also contribute to life satisfaction in general. In the study "Conversion to organic farming" increases dairy farmers' satisfaction regardless of the strategies used [113], farmers' satisfaction was defined as a variable consisting of five independent variables: 1. economic aspects, 2. agronomic aspects, 3. animal-related aspects, 4. social aspects, 5. working conditions, which shows how the variables are interrelated and intertwined.

C. Mental health

An important category included mental health related variables such as mental health in general depression, anxiety, suicide mortality rates, alcohol (ab)use/ binge drinking, opioid use tobacco use, nervous; as a culturally-defined mental health condition that is shared across Latino subgroups with specific symptoms including, idea stuck in head, distraction, sadness, irritation, dementia and cognitive impairment. Another variable is farm exit intention, meaning intention to leave or abandon farming.

Recommendations, good practices and future research

Future directions arising from the studies discussed in TOPIC 1 relate to interventions and opportunities for coping with stress and/or reducing stressors in agriculture. For the sake of transparency, we have

grouped them into three categories: Recommendation/ directions, Proposed interventions, and Good practices.

a) Recommendations/future directions

Recommendations largely relate to the issue of injury prevention and stress reduction in farmers and ranchers [76]. Another study reported that experiencing an injury may have led to depression, but depression may also have led to injury. Longitudinal studies are needed to clarify the causal pathway [465]. Other findings suggest the need for greater attention to workplace stress and injury and their potential impact on family functioning, and point to the development of intervention measures aimed at reducing this stress, improving access to mental health services, and developing a strong safety culture, including a robust safety training program. Developing a safety culture that prioritizes worker well-being can be an important prevention strategy to reduce the risk of workplace accidents and stress. [134].

In addition, the studies also point to improved awareness and the need for future research ([81], [93], [306], [406], [462], [486], [528]). Improved awareness of stressors may help to reduce farmers' frustration with outsiders' lack of understanding of their way of life, normalize stressors and thus reduce stigma, and empower farmers to seek help. These findings could also help in the development of targeted initiatives to prevent and promote farmers' mental health in future droughts [215]. Future work should address stressors that were not considered in the current study(s), as well as additional strategies for coping with stress [93]. Rigorous research is needed to quantify the impact and demonstrate the protective effect of sustainable practices on the health of rural populations [81]. Findings suggest that people who do not live on a farm may be more susceptible to mental health impairment in rural Saskatchewan than their agricultural counterparts. Further research with a longitudinal design and improved measurements is needed to confirm or refute these findings [306]. There is a need to identify other housing factors that could influence the mental health of farmworkers (relationship with roommates) [406]. There is a need to conduct a larger study to better characterize the impact of the opioid crisis on farmworkers across age and gender [462]. Additional research should further investigate protective factors for mental illness and opportunities for intervention [486]. As the sedentary, non-migratory farming population did not report significant differences in occupational and psychosocial stress during periods of low and high work demands, there is a need to evaluate these measures in additional populations [528].

Some studies suggest designing and developing specific programs or/and tailored interventions for farmers and farmworkers. The results should be considered when designing assistance programs for farmers [442]. Tailored interventions for injury prevention and pain management would be particularly beneficial for the horticultural industry [462]. Continued advocacy for increasing mental health capacity in rural hospitals and clinics to meet the needs of farmers is needed. Emphasised community-based interventions to increase awareness of mental disorders [486] are needed too as well as to develop and implement culturally appropriate initiatives to prevent, recognize, and treat mental health problems among farmers [535].

Some other suggestions are related to farm suicides and mental health problems among Latino migrant workers: the results of the study may be useful for a better understanding of farm suicides from an epidemiologic perspective and for improving suicide prevention interventions in the agricultural population [107]. Mental health problems among Latino immigrant (migrant) farmworkers represent a potential public health crisis [423].

b) Proposed interventions

Some of the proposed concrete actions relate to specific climate situations: drought; health risks for farmers can be included in drought early warning plans and local strategies to mitigate the effects of drought and reduce the burden on the population [90] or a specific type of farmworker, namely feedlot workers. Employers in feedlots should focus on improving safety culture, including sound on-the-job

training [134]. Others call for interventions that reduce stress and financial threat in farming and increase social support for farmers [225], or suggest stricter regulations and enforcement of existing regulations [406]. The more regionally focused proposals to improve occupational health and safety information and training, integrate behavioural health services into primary care, and strengthen protections through the Migrant and seasonal agricultural worker protection act may improve conditions for migrant farmworkers in the rural Midwest [465].

c) Identified good practices

The study, which showed that farmers satisfaction increased greatly during the conversion to organic farming, is in stark contrast to previous studies that emphasised the multiple risks of converting to organic farming [113]. The results of the FPSICO method showed that the greenhouses in Almería provide an acceptable psychosocial environment; however, medium- to long-term measures are needed to improve and optimise these conditions [128]. A French study found that education levels and the management of vascular risk factors improved during the study period and that overall health and living conditions improved [445]. However, notwithstanding the results of the study [445], there is still scope to improve economic and living conditions and to address social and cultural needs by creating more welcoming host communities [466]. And stress management may also be particularly important in older farmer couples, as the perceived stress of one member of the dyad affects both [469]. Not to be neglected, modern statistical learning methods can help to make the most of exit studies. The results have implications for farmers, extension services and agricultural policy makers [262].

DRIVERS OF CHANGE AND MEGA-TRENDS

Based on the articles reviewed in TOPIC 1 and considering the PRISMA protocol, the factors that will influence the future of farming in relation to mental health **can only be deduced indirectly, not from the actual results of the studies**, but from their discussions and conclusions. We have grouped the key drivers of change that will impact on farmers' mental health into the following categories: climate change, demographic trends, economic growth, and globalisation and digitalization.

Climate change [81], [90], [215]

An increase in extreme weather events is expected in the future, especially frequent, severe droughts, which are among the largest and most consequential of all natural hazards. In the last 40 years, the percentage of the global area affected by drought has almost doubled and more people are affected than by any other natural disaster affecting rural areas and farming. The increase in extreme weather events, particularly severe droughts, is highly connected to mental health, through the impact on psychological stress and anxiety. The anticipation of more frequent and severe droughts can lead to chronic stress and anxiety, especially for those whose livelihoods depend on agriculture. Uncertainty about water availability and crop yields can lead to prolonged psychological stress among farmers. As droughts affect agricultural productivity, many farmers experience economic difficulties, leading to financial stress. This economic strain is closely linked to an increase in depression, anxiety and other mental health problems. Long-term psychological impairment from repeated droughts and other extreme weather events can have a cumulative traumatic effect and lead to conditions such as post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD). The impact of extreme weather events such as droughts on mental health can be passed down through generations as children grow up in an environment characterised by stress, fear and economic instability.

Labour shortages and Migration [128], [245], [383], [469]

Among demographic changes, migration and the exchange of labour between countries is the dominant issue. The study, which focused on agricultural workers in Almería-type greenhouses in south eastern Spain [128], reported that foreign seasonal workers make up about 40% of the workforce, including workers from Africa and Eastern Europe. For the USA, it has been estimated that agricultural producers employ between 3 and 5 million migrant workers annually and that 80% of migrant workers in this country have migrant status and over 90% of these individuals are of Mexican origin [383]. Latino migrant farmworkers face numerous challenges that threaten their mental health [245]. Another important

demographic issue is the aging of the agricultural population, which is usually associated with health factors that may increase the risk of depression [469].

Neoliberalism, Globalisation, and Agroecological principles [113], [442], [533], [535]

Conversion to organic farming requires a period of 18 or 24 months, depending on the dairy farmer's choice, and presents a significant challenge. During this transition, farmers must comply with organic farming regulations and implement a wide range of changes in farming practices, marketing strategies, knowledge-sharing networks, and social relations, even though they do not yet receive the price for their organic milk [113]. These challenges are further complicated by broader factors such as economic growth and globalisation, which can influence market dynamics and the availability of resources needed for the successful adoption of organic practices."

The agro-industries of many developed countries are going through a prolonged period of structural change. Farms are becoming larger and more efficient and the number of farmers is decreasing. As a result, many of today's farmers will no longer be farmers in the future. Some will retire, but others will leave while still of working age and switch to another profession. This can be a difficult process that has a negative impact on their well-being. As prices rise and fall and market conditions change, farmers adapt to the circumstances and for some, leaving the farm is the best option for their well-being [442].

The study, which examined working conditions in rural areas using psychosocial indices [533], emphasized that conditions for farmers have changed rapidly and the situation in recent years is characterized by instability and uncertainty about future conditions, which are the main causes of psychological stress.

Structural change in agriculture in recent decades may be another source of stress for farmers in industrialized countries [535]. The development in agriculture is characterized by the introduction of new technologies and consequently increased productivity requirements, decreased number of farmers and increased farm size [535].

Technological Advances [442]

In most industrialized countries, the number of people working as farmers is declining. There are a number of reasons for this, but among the most important are technological advances and productivity gains that allow fewer farmers to produce more, as well as economic policies that encourage greater competition between farmers [442]. These changes, while beneficial in some ways, they also introduce new pressures and challenges that can negatively impact farmers' mental health, leading to stress, anxiety, depression, and a heightened risk of mental health crises.

CONCLUSIONS

The studies analysed in TOPIC 1 focused on identifying key stressors in farmers/farmworkers and their impact on mental health and well-being. Studying the stressors faced by farmers and farmworkers provides a comprehensive understanding of the mental health challenges faced by this important workforce. This analysis identifies economic, environmental and social stressors, providing valuable insights into their interrelated effects on mental health and well-being. It emphasises the urgent need for targeted interventions and policy adjustments to effectively address these challenges.

Key stressors

Farmers and farmworkers are exposed to a unique mix of stressors that differentiate their mental health risks from those of other occupational groups. Financial stressors are consistently the most important predictors of poor mental health. High debt, unpredictable income and market volatility contribute to chronic financial stress. These problems are exacerbated by environmental factors such as prolonged droughts, heat waves and other climate change-related challenges that not only jeopardise crop yields and livestock health, but also increase financial instability. These conditions lead to an increased workload, which adds to the stress.

Health-related stressors such as limited access to health care, chronic diseases and occupational hazards such as exposure to pesticides also play an important role in affecting mental health. Injuries sustained during farm labour and the physically demanding nature of farm work contribute to the development of chronic illnesses which, if left untreated, further deteriorate mental wellbeing. In addition, the psychosocial environment in agriculture, which is characterised by isolation, lack of social support and harsh working conditions, is directly linked to an increased incidence of depression and anxiety among farmers and farmworkers. Traditional gender roles add another layer of stress, with women often bearing a disproportionate emotional and physical burden.

Social dynamics within farming communities add additional stressors. Family conflicts, particularly those arising from financial pressures or the intergenerational transfer of farms, have a significant impact on mental health. For adolescents in farming families, these conflicts combined with work-related injuries can lead to behavioural problems and long-term mental health effects. Migrant farm workers face even more serious problems, such as poor living conditions, social isolation, fear of deportation and high levels of substance abuse, such as alcohol and opioids. These factors contribute to the alarmingly high rates of depression and anxiety in this subgroup. The results of the studies analysed emphasise the importance of addressing these particular vulnerabilities in order to improve the overall mental health of farmworkers.

The findings are consistent with previous studies, underpinning the general understanding of mental health risks in farming (Braun, 2019, Hagen et al., 2019; Lundquist et al., 2022; EU-OSHA; 2024). Notably, these risks are not evenly distributed across all subgroups. Male farmers, for example, have a higher risk of suicide, while the prevalence of dementia among older farmers highlights the long-term cognitive effects of stress and isolation. These findings emphasise the need for a tailored approach to mental health interventions, taking into account the specific needs of different demographic groups within the farming workforce.

Megatrends

The analysis highlights several megatrends that are likely to shape farmers' mental health in the coming years. Climate change is a key driver, with the associated environmental pressures and economic impacts likely to intensify. Demographic changes, including labour shortages and migration trends, will also have an impact on farmers' mental health. While globalisation of food markets and digitalisation in agriculture offer opportunities for greater efficiency, they also bring new challenges such as technological adaptation and market competition. These trends, as well as the ongoing impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, require a proactive approach to mitigate their potential impact on mental health.

Stress reduction interventions

The analysis points to several promising interventions that should be explored further. Practises such as organic farming, which promote sustainable and environmentally friendly farming practises, have the potential to reduce stress associated with climate change and market volatility. Safety training programmes, particularly those tailored to the specific needs of different farming populations, can increase workplace safety and reduce injury-related stress. However, further research is needed to assess the long-term effectiveness and scalability of these interventions in different contexts.

Dealing with the identified stressors requires a multi-faceted approach to stress reduction. Financial stressors that are deeply embedded in broader economic and political systems require systemic solutions. Policy makers need to integrate mental health considerations into farming policies, such as the EU Common Agricultural Policy, to ensure a holistic response. Financial incentives, subsidies and risk mitigation programmes can alleviate some of the financial burdens that exacerbate mental health problems. For stressors related to health and occupational risks, improvements in workplace health and safety standards are essential. Access to affordable health care, regular health screenings and training on safe farming practises can significantly reduce the physical and mental stress of working in agriculture.

Interventions that address family and social dynamics can have a profound impact on stress reduction. Community-based mental health services, conflict resolution programmes and support networks for farm families can help mitigate the negative effects of family conflict and social isolation. Raising awareness to reduce the stigma of mental health and promoting culturally sensitive initiatives are also important steps to create a favourable environment for seeking help.

The challenges faced by migrant workers in agriculture highlight the urgent need for inclusive policies that address their particular vulnerabilities. Providing safe and affordable housing, ensuring access to healthcare and introducing legal protection against exploitation and discrimination are essential measures. In addition, outreach programmes that connect migrant workers with community resources can help reduce isolation and improve mental health.

Farmers and farm workers face a range of stressors that they have varying degrees of control over. Stressors related to family and social dynamics, such as family conflict, are generally the easiest to manage. In contrast, health and occupational risks are much more difficult for individuals to control, although there is potential for improvement through improved health and safety practices. Financial stressors, influenced by national monetary policy and political discourse, make matters even more complex. Stressors related to climate change are the most challenging as they are completely beyond the control of the individual. These issues raise the broader question of whether society can collectively reverse the effects of climate change. Stressors that are beyond the control of farm families, including those that affect resource management and family dynamics, are often categorized as exceptional stressors (Braun, 2019).

Limitations of the analysis

Despite its contributions, the analysis points to some gaps in existing research. Methodological limitations, such as dependence on databases and linguistic biases, emphasise the need for more comprehensive research approaches. Extending the studies to non-English language studies and using different data sources can contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the issues at stake.

Longitudinal studies are needed to clarify the causal relationships between stress, mental health problems and outcomes such as injuries and productivity loss. Future research should also examine underrepresented populations such as female farmers, younger generations and ethnic minorities to ensure comprehensive coverage of mental health problems in agriculture. In addition, new topics such as the impact of digitalisation, market volatility and the green transition on mental health are not yet sufficiently researched and require further investigation.

This analysis bridges the gap between research and policy by offering actionable findings and practical recommendations. Policy makers are encouraged to prioritise prevention, resilience and wellbeing in their strategies and ensure that the mental health of farmers and farmworkers is an integral part of sustainable farming practises. By addressing the identified research gaps and implementing evidence-based interventions, society can support the mental health of this important workforce and pave the way for a healthier and more productive farming future.

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CHAPTER 2: CULTURE OF FARMING, FARM SAFETY AND FARMER WELL-BEING

STARTING POINTS

Research problem

In this chapter, the authors discuss the sociocultural domain of agriculture to identify the cultural sources of health and safety risks. Consistent with the observation that agricultural health and safety research and interventions have been dominated by health professionals, educators and engineers (Thu, 1998) or psychological and psychiatric discourses when examining farming stress (Price and Evans, 2005), we concur, that, as a result, there has been a lack of critical attention to the underlying sociocultural (and economic) conditions of contemporary agriculture that may impact on the health and safety of people who farm and an incomplete understanding of the impact of these conditions on the alarming rates of illness, injury and death in this occupational group.

The still ongoing modernisation of agriculture, usually referred to as the introduction of innovations, economic transition or restructuring (Ramírez-Ferrero, 2005), has always been culturally mediated by different actors involved in its shaping, mostly through the valuation of the new or the devaluation of the old notions of agricultural development, progress and practises. The reaction of farmers and farm labourers to such changes in agriculture was also always embedded in their respective farming cultures. Rare social scientists who have explicitly addressed the question of why farmers and farm workers do not adopt interventions to prevent injury and disease have discussed cultural phenomena in terms of gendered technologies of care (Lovelock, 2012), normalisation and socialisation of danger (Shortall et al., 2018), ethnicity and gender in agricultural health and safety (Barnes & Bendixsen, 2017), health and safety within agrarian ethics (Bendixsen, 2017), emic (farmer) conceptualisations of risk (Sorensen et al., 2017), etc. Moreover, some anthropologists have questioned the usual focus of mainstream public health and social service practise on mainly individual risk behaviour in agriculture, underpinned by psychological discourses, which usually marginalised, for example, “the root cause of farmers’ stress ... [such as] the economic crisis in family farming and the changing nature of rural communities” (Ramírez-Ferrero, 2005, p. 3), discrimination as a lived experience (Snipes et al., 2017), or symbolic violence and social suffering (Holmes, 2013), in sum, structural phenomena that are all culturally mediated.

To identify the cultural roots of health and safety risks in agriculture, the authors of this chapter draw on Emery’s (2010) dynamic concept of culture as presented in his theoretical discussion of farming cultures and the idea of the “good farmer”. Emery’s work explicitly addresses the interplay between individual agency and structural influences. Guided largely by a rhetoric-culture approach, as developed in Carrithers’ works, he argues that culture is continuously created and reshaped by individuals who strategically engage with and negotiate cultural norms. This dynamic view of culture reflects a broader understanding of society as a network of individuals interacting through constant negotiation. Individuals are seen as capable of using cultural elements strategically and creatively to adapt to evolving circumstances or advance their interests, while remaining embedded in structural power relations. Emery highlights the dual role of individuals as both agents who influence their surroundings and patients who are influenced by external forces. In the context of the “good farmer” and evolving farming cultures, this perspective underscores that changes in values arise through ongoing (re)negotiations between farmers and others. Farmers strategically draw on and negotiate within a repertoire of values to shape their identity or personhood, all while recognizing that this repertoire is intertwined with existing structures of social power (Burton et al., 2021).

Therefore, the authors of the chapter argue that the cultural sources of health and safety risks in agriculture are related to farming culture through beliefs, practises and symbols learned and shared among farmers and farm workers that shape their worldview, identities and way of life (Braff & Nelson, 2020), including their agricultural ethics, different cultural identities, health beliefs and self-medication, perceptions of risk and danger, discriminatory beliefs and behaviours, etc., which are embedded in the interplay of agency and structure and are constantly renegotiated. Finally, based on the dynamic concept

of culture, the authors wanted to caution against the various “inadequate conceptions of culture” (Spencer-Oatey, 2012, p. 16), such as culture being homogeneous, static, evenly distributed, unique to individuals, exclusively visible customs, or a reified entity independent of human agency, which can form the underlying assumption for designing culturally appropriate interventions.

Research aims and expectations

Using a systematic literature review, this chapter aims to identify how the selected literature addresses the cultural sources of health and safety risks in agriculture in order to discuss interventions and research in this area. Employing a more dynamic concept of culture that emphasises the interplay between agency and structure, this review aims to contribute new insights, reflections and questions on both the impact of cultural stressors on the health, safety and well-being of farmers and farm workers and on culturally appropriate interventions.

Research question

Consistent with a dynamic concept of culture, the authors of this chapter reorganised the initial TOPIC 2 questions¹ for the systematic literature review into the general question – **How does farming culture shape the safety, health and wellbeing of farmers and farm workers?** – focusing on farmers’ and farm workers’ understanding of risks, hazards and problematic relationships in their workplace and changes that affect the farming (safety) culture.

Screening steps of systematic literature review for TOPIC 2

After completing the first two steps of a systematic literature review (see methodological overview in the introduction), three researchers reviewed 603 titles and abstracts in the third step using the initial TOPIC 2 questions. All reviewers uniformly selected only 25 identical articles for inclusion, while the remainder of the reviewed articles were voted on by consensus – If two reviewers selected the same article for further review, that article was accepted. Ultimately, 94 articles were deemed suitable for the next step.

In the fourth step, the articles were screened against the inclusion/exclusion criteria (no research was conducted; the research is neither quantitative nor qualitative; the country is not relevant for the study; there is no relevant core target group; not at least one of the initial questions raised in TOPIC 2 is addressed). An article was excluded if it met one or more of the exclusion criteria. After the fourth step, 45 articles were selected for the fifth – final analysis of the systematic literature review (see Table 2).

The PICO (Population, Issue, Comparators and Outcomes) approach is used to analyse the selected articles, which also forms the framework for the subsequent discussion and conclusion. A detailed analysis and overview of the studies on this topic can be found in Appendix 3.

MAIN FINDINGS

THE FIRST FINDING of the literature review analysis of cultural sources of health and safety risks in agriculture confirms the current and recent emphasis that agricultural studies **underrepresent some groups of people by gender, age, ethnicity, etc.**, or ignore them in favour of others (Nye et al., 2025; chapter 6 of Burton et al., 2021). Research participants are still predominantly male farmers and farm labourers. Few studies that have directly or indirectly examined the cultural roots of health and safety risks in agriculture focus on female farmers and (migrant) farm workers, and none on LGBTQIA+ farmers or labourers. The same is true for age groups – younger and older farmers and labourers are rarely the

¹ The initial TOPIC 2 questions were drafted during the workshops in March and April 2023, and the brainstorming exercise in October and November 2023 as follows:

How is farming culture (rules of the game, beliefs and values (the ‘good farmer’, hard work, struggle, self-sacrifice), male/female identity, etc.) related to the safety, health and wellbeing of farmers/farm workers?

How do farmers/farm workers experience/understand/socialise/perceive the risks and hazards on the farm?

What contributes to values, attitudes and behaviours related to farming (safety) culture?

What changes affect (directly or indirectly) the farming (safety) culture/(safety) practises (rules of the game, beliefs and values, etc.), and in which direction?

target groups of research, nor are children and youth, disabled and indigenous farmers and labourers, or other ethnic minorities. Greater consideration of underrepresented groups in the literature on the cultural roots of health and safety risks in agriculture would be valuable, as this has the potential to promote more diverse and inclusive health and safety interventions and support systems. The literature review for TOPIC 2 identified the following vulnerable groups:

Vulnerable groups identified in the four groups of cultural stressors explained below (see THIRD FINDING):

1. *Gender identities and relationships*: women due to the reproduction of patriarchal relationships in farming and new responsibilities and roles.
2. *Structural vulnerability and discrimination*: migrants from indigenous communities due to discrimination, poor working and living conditions; children and youth because they are invisible.
3. *Ruptures in the moral economy (ethics and emotions)*: young, highly skilled and educated farmers who have chosen to stay in agriculture but are faced with unpredictable ethical issues that affect their choices and well-being.
4. *Risk perception, safety and health beliefs in agriculture*: migrant workers and all children due to the social normalisation of hazardous work and agricultural exceptionalism regarding safety regulations in agriculture.

It is also observed that there is **a lack of comparisons** between farmers and other occupational groups or general population groups that would contribute to a better understanding of the socio-cultural characteristics of people in agriculture, as highlighted in an earlier literature review by Chiswell (2022), which explicitly compared the mental health of farmers and non-farmers. She investigated whether farmers are more prone to psychological morbidity than the wider, non-farming population and found little consensus on this issue in the studies reviewed. We can agree with her recommendation to explore, for example, the specific “pathway” of farmers to suicide and to emphasise the need for multidisciplinary research that would provide a more culturally appropriate and effective understanding of mental health in the farming population.

THE SECOND FINDING reports on the fact that studies on the cultural roots of health and safety risks in agriculture between the second half of the 1990s and the first and second decade of the 2000s were **mainly conducted in the USA, Canada, Australia and New Zealand**. Although 40% of the studies focused on farmers and their family members in Europe, only 12% of the studies investigated the cultural sources of health and safety risks among (migrant) agricultural workers or employees from Europe. Such **a geographical gap** or **limited** number of **studies** on mental well-being in farming communities **from Europe** (excluding the UK) was also found in other previous and current reviews (Hagen et al., 2019; Yazd et al., 2019; Nye et al., 2025).

THE THIRD FINDING is that most of the studies analysed have only **indirectly** addressed **the cultural sources of health and safety risks in agriculture**. Since cultural stressors as such were not explicitly mentioned in the study objectives, we first identified four groups of cultural sources of health and safety risks in agriculture. In doing so, we followed Emery’s dynamic concept of culture and the idea of the “good farmer” (2010), which states that culture is continuously created and reshaped by individuals who strategically engage with and negotiate cultural norms. The need for a dynamic concept of farming culture through the idea of a “good farmer” has been emphasised in previous studies since Burton’s famous 2004 article, but not directly in the context of farmers’ health, safety and wellbeing. Following Burton et al.’s suggestion that “conceptualisations of the good farmer should be selected on the basis of their utility for understanding the particular aspect of cultural object/behaviour under investigation” (2021: 13), and given that there is no consensus on the definition or understanding of farming culture, we recognised those among the numerous possible cultural sources of health and safety risks in

agriculture that have been discussed in relation to the mental health, safety and well-being of farmers and farm workers.

Identified cultural sources of health and safety risks in agriculture include:

1. Gender identities and relationships
2. Structural vulnerability and discrimination
3. Breaks in the moral economy (ethics and emotions)
4. Risk perception, safety and health beliefs in agriculture

Most of the studies in our review were concerned with perceived risk, danger and control over the agricultural working and living environment as cultural stressors, followed by the studies that consider phenomena of structural vulnerability, violence and discrimination as cultural stressors, the studies that consider gender as cultural stressors, and finally the studies that discuss ruptures in the moral economy (ethics and emotions) of farmers' specific agricultural systems as a cultural source of their discomfort or ill-being.

As the selection of articles was influenced by our understanding of farming culture, it is not surprising that **qualitative methods** predominated over quantitative ones (25 vs. 14), while six studies used mixed methods. **The concepts and theories** reflected the aims of the studies. Studies of farm workers' perceptions of risks, hazards and control in the agricultural environment used different health models — such as the health beliefs model, the health behaviour model and ecological models — while other studies examined farm workers' perceptions of child safety and disability-related barriers to return to work, often relying on interviews or questionnaires without a specific theoretical framework. Studies that addressed structural vulnerability, violence and discrimination as cultural stressors utilised different theoretical frameworks — such as farmworker-specific environmental microaggressions, structural violence and structural vulnerability — to examine the cultural, economic and political mechanisms that perpetuate social hierarchies, inequalities and systemic barriers to health and safety, particularly for migrant farmworkers, while also highlighting gaps in general health and safety research. Studies looking at gender as a cultural stressor have used gender role strain theory and concepts such as traditional machismo and rural masculinity to analyse their impact on men's mental health, particularly depression and anxiety. Finally, studies analysing breaks in the moral economy of farmers show how the discrepancy between their ideals of being a "good farmer" and the new agricultural realities contributes to emotional distress and ill-being.

In summary, the different methods, concepts and theories used in the selected TOPIC 2 articles reflect the different academic perspectives of researchers on how best to operationalise farming culture as a context for the health, safety and well-being of farmers and farm workers.

THE FOURTH MAIN FINDING confirms **the relationship between the above four groups of cultural stressors and safety, health and well-being in agriculture.**

The reviewed studies on gender as a cultural stressor in agriculture show that it has a significant impact on health, well-being and safety. They show that men's traditional masculinity exacerbates stress and health risks, while patriarchal dynamics increase women's financial, health and safety vulnerability due to their lack of education, economic independence and exposure to risk, with women often prioritising the needs of others over their own and facing greater mental health problems and safety risks. This finding replicates the observations of several previous studies; either the majority of studies highlighting the vulnerability of male farmers who experienced the devaluation of cultural ideas and practises that supported their subjectivity, such as the sense of pride (e.g. Ramírez-Ferrero, 2005; Roy et al., 2014; Garnham & Bryant, 2014; Bryant & Garnham, 2015), or to a much lesser extent those who problematise the invisibility of women in agriculture as part of a patriarchal way of life (e.g. Price & Evans, 2009; Burton et al., 2021, especially chapter 6). This finding, however, does not refer to the still rare studies that focus only on women who experience distress and who, like men, are also owners, managers or employees of productivist family farms (e.g. Bryant, 2022). The same is true for other almost invisible

agricultural gender identities (e.g. LGBTQ+ farmers) given the prevalence of agricultural heterosexism (Wypler & Hoffelmeyer, 2020).

Studies that have looked at structural vulnerability, violence and discrimination as cultural stressors refer not only to mechanisms of power, but also to reified cultural constructions of disadvantaged social groups (in our case migrants and seasonal or foreign farm workers) as “others” and “outsiders”. These studies have highlighted racialised hierarchies, ethnically segregated work, poor housing conditions, lack of community support, limited access to health care, language barriers, unsafe working conditions and systematic exclusion from health protection, all of which exacerbate stress and health risks, with myths, workplace discrimination and economic pressures compounding the challenges. This finding confirms the observations of previous studies, particularly from the US, which have documented the health suffering of vulnerable agricultural groups in relation to their socio-cultural context, history, poverty, gender and the confluence of many other life experiences (e.g. Arcury & Quandt, 2009; Holmes, 2013; Snipes et al., 2017; Barnes & Bendixsen, 2017).

Studies of ruptures in the moral economy of farmers show that unexpected challenges — such as the mismatch between ideals of good farming and new agricultural realities, socio-economic pressures, political contradictions and systemic injustices — contribute to farmers’ distress and ill-being, with factors such as unfulfilled ethical obligations, economic constraints and perceived injustices undermining their well-being and their trust in governmental and institutional support. This finding supports rare previous studies which emphasise the importance of understanding farmers’ (negative) moral emotions and judgements elicited by so-called moral events (e.g. proposed farm exit or agricultural transition) that potentially impair (or enhance) farmers’ well-being or enable their distress (e.g. Kuehne, 2013; Bryant & Garnham, 2018). As a recent study by Wheeler et al. (2023) shows, culturally construed feelings of loneliness can also arise from a sense that a cultural group with which the individual identifies (in our case, farmers) is poorly understood and to some extent marginalised by the wider rural community, the public or hegemonic society.

Finally, the perception of risk, danger and control in agriculture is established to be culturally constructed. Migrant farm workers often underestimate workplace hazards due to traditional health beliefs and systemic barriers, while farmers normalise risky behaviours, prioritise autonomy over safety, and downplay workers’ safety concerns, leading to inequalities that are reinforced by extension workers but recognised by health providers who observe poor working and living conditions on the ground. This finding supports the observations of even scarcer previous studies linking the high rates of injury and illness among farmers and agricultural workers to their cultural imageries of primarily male risk and hazard behaviour and their resistance to care techniques considered feminine (Lovelock, 2012; Shortal et al., 2018). On the other hand, the finding is consistent with previous observations that farmers and farm workers understand but ignore health and safety risks when confronted with threats to their families’ financial well-being or their misconceptions about health, e.g. harmless pesticides, heat, etc. (e.g. Hunt et al., 1999; Sorensen et al., 2008; Arcury, 2017).

THE FIFTH FINDING, which only **indirectly** refers to **megatrends** and **drivers of change** as a contextualisation of the study under review and not the subject of analysis, confirms the earlier observation that agriculture is facing profound changes due to neoliberal reforms, globalisation, climate change, etc. (Donham & Thelin, 2016), as well as studies documenting the health consequences of industrialised agriculture for farmers, farm workers and their families since the post-World War II period (e.g. Thu, 1998). Farmers, in turn, are increasingly under pressure to adapt to rising costs, reduced subsidies and demographic change, leading to reduced labour, off-farm employment and a decline in rural services. Labour shortages highlight the dependence on migrant workers, who often face discrimination, poor conditions and systematic exploitation, particularly affecting women and children. Climate change exacerbates the risks of extreme weather conditions and health hazards and increases the vulnerability of agricultural workers and farms. The transition to agroecological farming in Europe emphasises sustainability and social cohesion, but it is a challenge to reconcile traditional and new

demands. These interwoven trends emphasise the urgent need for systemic reforms to ensure the sustainability, equity and resilience of agriculture.

THE LAST FINDING offers **recommendations** (in the form of suggestions for **concrete actions and future research**) and identifies **good practises** to overcome cultural stressors to safety, health and well-being in agriculture.

In general, **effective interventions** require simultaneous and parallel actions of culturally sensitive measures and participatory approaches **at the local and community level** as well as systemic policy reforms **at the national level**, which are summarised and discussed below for each identified group of cultural stressors:

Gender and health risks: The studies reviewed have shown that gender inequalities require interventions such as the creation of safe spaces for dialogue in the context of observed male suffering, national support for exiting agriculture and measures to promote work-life balance. However, such interventions still remain trapped within the broader society of modern agriculture as a predominantly masculine world, reproduced and promoted through numerous cultural discourses or values of industrialised agriculture (Ramírez-Ferrero, 2005; Thu, 1998). It is no surprise that women farmers are more visible in alternative agricultural networks than in conventional ones, although, as some authors emphasise (Burton et al., 2021), such practices do not necessarily lead to gender parity. As the social and cultural conditions under which farmers may experience distress change, they may be a potential site for gender-specific interventions.

Structural vulnerabilities: The selected articles mostly focused on migrant and seasonal workers who face systemic discrimination and health risks, although farmers can also be considered structurally vulnerable in relation to agribusiness (Holmes, 2013; Bryant & Garnham, 2014), not to mention other structurally vulnerable groups based on gender, age or ethnicity in agriculture. Suggested interventions therefore include culturally sensitive health education, improved access to healthcare, empowerment of marginalised groups and integration of social medicine into community support despite the observed contradictory portrayals of farmers as ethical and hardworking and as discriminating against their employees. We can agree with Arcury (2017) who calls for independent (e.g., anthropological) field studies to address the larger context of agricultural health and safety policy, as such a study is not part of mainstream agriculture (e.g., large national and multinational agricultural corporations, commodity groups, agricultural colleges in land-grant universities, state departments of agriculture, etc.) that may resist efforts to document the hazards of agricultural work and develop strategies to improve occupational safety in agriculture. His suggestion of talking to farmers and farm workers, asking them about their experiences and trying to understand their perspective, and then documenting their actual circumstances may be a way to work with them and the larger community in developing and designing practises to improve their health and safety.

Moral economy and ethics: The reviewed studies that addressed ruptures in the moral economy of farmers, consumers or the state proposed not only context-sensitive approaches to the situation of farmers as a very heterogeneous occupational group, but also multidimensional frameworks for analysing their working conditions (control, income, job security) to help agricultural advisors and farmers effectively address health and safety challenges. In this context, a study by Meijboom and Stafleu (2016) is worth mentioning, which proposes an even more ambitious measure – the development of an ethical code in the form of professional moral autonomy for those farmers who recognise the moral dimension of agriculture and are still looking for legitimate moral responses to the public issues and debates related to agriculture. The professional ethical autonomy can contribute to the well-being of farmers as this ethical code provides a tool for clarifying the mutual expectations of farmers, the public and agricultural professionals and for managing their conflicting moral expectations in relation to agriculture.

Risk perception and safety beliefs: The proposed actions mainly concerned customised safety education addressing cultural barriers and educational deficits, stricter safety regulations, economic support and multi-stakeholder engagement to promote a safer agricultural environment. These measures implicitly acknowledge the fact that workers in agriculture are known for their relatively high risk tolerance (e.g. Kallioniemi et al., 2011), as well as those studies that recognise farmers' identity with the risk orientation within farming cultures or agrarian ethics that shape farmers' belief in their (economic) success despite the stressors they face on a daily basis (Sorensen et al., 2017; Bendixsen, 2017). Rather than encouraging the adoption of safety technologies, the latter studies suggested safer technologies that are both safer and increase the efficiency of production, thus leading to financial savings, or another option to focus on the cost of injuries over time and how this affects the financial viability of the farm, rather than emphasising safety statistics, or the option about changing the farming environment and farming work patterns so that they do not support a positive focus on risk behaviours. These studies not only challenge those who primarily insist on improved health and safety education, but rather favour interventions in the root causes of the so-called safety paradox (e.g. Murphy, 2003).²

Future research directions should focus more on gender-specific stressors and the role of women in mitigating men's mental health problems in agriculture, cultural barriers to care, socioeconomic inequalities, culturally sensitive health solutions according to age, gender and ethnicity, and interdisciplinary studies to improve interventions. In addition, historical and cross-cultural studies are considered essential for identifying trends and improving the well-being of farmers and workers in agriculture. This overall finding is also recognised in more recent studies (Rose et al., 2023; Nye et al., 2025), in particular the need to rethink current approaches and methods in the field of mental health and well-being in agriculture and to call for interdisciplinary and participatory approaches.

Good Practices to overcome structural vulnerabilities in the selected articles include: Identification and assessment of microaggressions in the environment, participatory education initiatives (such as, for example, the PACE project – Preventing Agricultural Chemical Exposure among North Carolina Farmworkers) and localised healthcare for migrants with translation services.

Good practices related to breaks in the moral economy include ethical and emotional analysis to address distress and suicide prevention, multidimensional analysis of working conditions (e.g. income, job security, health) and educational programmes such as Environmental Farm plans and peer discussions.

As a good practice related to risk perceptions and safety beliefs may be recognised legislation in California that reduces heat-related illness through mandated employer actions was identified as a good practise.

1. Recommendations, good practices and future research

The TOPIC 2 studies reviewed also discussed *recommendations for improving existing or introducing new policies or future research* in the form of concrete actions, further study directions, or both. Good practises are identified *a posteriori*.

1.1. Gender identities as a cultural source of health and safety risks in agriculture

Concrete actions proposed:

A comprehensive approach to addressing the challenges faced by gender-specific groups in rural and agricultural contexts in different regions involves multiple levels of intervention. At the local level, it is important to create supportive spaces and services where both men and women can speak openly about their hardships, fostering also a culturally sensitive environment that builds trust in health care and agricultural support systems. At a national level, targeted information and counselling is crucial to

² The safety-risk paradox in agriculture refers to the fact that farmers know that their work is dangerous, but are still willing to take risks and in some cases forego safety measures in agriculture.

provide dignified financial exit from agriculture, retraining opportunities and support for new business ventures, alongside campaigns to promote gender equality ([25]).

In addition, systemic changes are needed at the policy level, such as EU directives to eliminate outdated practises that marginalise women ([316]), and regulations in the US that support work-life balance for Latina immigrant women in agriculture through services such as childcare and food provision ([176]).

Future research proposed:

For a comprehensive understanding of the mental health and wellbeing of agricultural workers, it is necessary to examine gender-specific factors and experiences in different regions. Future research should explore the different beliefs and stressors associated with male and female gender roles ([6]).

The role of women in addressing male suicide rates and challenges to traditional masculinity in rural areas should be emphasised ([25]).

As the proportion of women in the agricultural labour force, such as in the United States, increases, it is critical to examine the unique experiences of Latina farm workers, as their experiences differ significantly from those of their male counterparts ([176]).

The gender-sensitive study approach is essential for the development of effective support systems and interventions ([435]).

Good practices identified: None.

1.2. Structural vulnerability and discrimination as a cultural stressor

Concrete actions proposed:

An inclusive approach to improving the structural conditions of agricultural workers, especially migrant workers, requires multi-faceted interventions at different levels. Key recommendations include:

1. Dialogue and education:

It is crucial to engage farm owners and managers in dialogues with (migrant) agricultural workers on good husbandry principles and to train future farm owners in leadership skills ([39]).

Collective advocacy should aim to change political-economic conditions and corporate power dynamics, thereby improving the economic security of both producers and (migrant) workers ([89]).

2. Health and safety:

To ensure the health and safety of migrant workers, their health must be prioritised at the national level, culturally sensitive training on occupational health hazards provided, and public health information on environmental impacts disseminated ([154]).

To meet these needs, also transnational governance mechanisms and innovations in health care are needed, including culturally safe approaches and specialised clinics ([163]).

3. Empowerment and advocacy:

Empowering indigenous and migrant workers as health promoters, facilitating their participation in the development of educational materials, and promoting a healthier work environment are essential steps ([213]).

Ensuring culturally sensitive application of health and safety policies and guidelines to combat the pandemic and promoting collective bargaining are also important ([218]).

4. *Policy and community support:*

Governments should make coordinated efforts to protect the health and safety of migrant workers, taking into account all stages of migration ([269]).

Clinicians should consider the social determinants of health and work toward integrating social medicine education into medical training ([283]).

Community responses should include creating welcoming environments, improving language skills, and networking social services to improve access ([466]).

5. *Public health and legal advocacy:*

Increasing funding for comprehensive health care, training culturally competent workers, and promoting law enforcement to ensure a safe environment for workers are critical. Community nurses can play an important role in training for self-advocacy and navigating the legal system ([443], [447]).

6. *Socioeconomic interventions:*

Incorporating knowledge of community conditions into interventions can consider the broader gender, economic and social environment of migrant farm workers ([250]). Extending minimum wage reforms to agricultural workers can help alleviate poverty and reduce stress-related health problems ([466]).

Overall, a coordinated effort that includes education, health and safety measures, empowerment, policy advocacy, and socioeconomic interventions is needed to improve the living, working, and social conditions of agricultural workers worldwide.

Future research proposed:

Tackling health inequalities in migrant farm workers requires a comprehensive research approach that focuses on the social determinants of health and the structural factors that contribute to inequalities. Key proposed research strategies include:

1. *Focusing on barriers and service delivery:*

Future research should examine barriers to care for emancipated immigrant youth, identify ideal methods of service delivery, and understand how migration patterns influence their health ([443]).

2. *Examine ethnic and civic inequalities:*

Researchers should consider the international context of migration to better understand ethnic and civic health disparities. Both qualitative and quantitative methods are needed to examine the impact of racism and anti-immigrant prejudice on health inequalities, with in-depth ethnographic methods being particularly effective in capturing the complexity of these issues ([283]).

3. *Use the concept of structural violence:*

The concept of structural violence is crucial in shifting the focus of anthropological and public health analysis from individual behaviours to social structures. This approach emphasises the broader social and systemic factors that contribute to risk, harm and suffering ([284]).

By integrating these research strategies, a more holistic understanding of health inequalities can be achieved, leading to more effective interventions and policies that address the root causes of inequalities in migrant populations.

Good practices identified:

The main contributions of three identified good practises are:

1. *Identification and assessment of environmental microaggressions (EMs):*

Through the application of critical race theory and interdisciplinary methods, researchers have identified how farm workers experience subtle forms of discrimination. This understanding is critical to addressing the health impacts of these microaggressions on marginalised groups ([51]).

2. *Empowerment through participatory education:*

Initiatives like the four-year PACE project (Preventing Agricultural Chemical Exposure among North Carolina Farmworkers) empower farm workers by directly engaging them in education and training about workplace hazards, particularly pesticide exposure. By working with community organisations and involving agricultural employers, these programmes improve the ability of farm workers to identify and address their own health and safety issues ([66]).

3. *Providing Specialized Local Health Care:*

Local clinics and support groups have made significant strides in providing specialised, accessible health care to migrant farm workers. These efforts include better access with open appointments, translation services and community support to meet the immediate health needs of farm workers and compensate for the lack of comprehensive national systems ([269]).

1.3. Ruptures in the moral economy (ethics and emotions) as a cultural source of health and safety risks in agriculture

Concrete actions proposed:

A context-sensitive approach to understanding the situation of farmers in the context of community-supported agriculture is essential for the development of effective health programmes and policy support ([97]).

A tested multidimensional framework for working conditions in line with agroecological principles of farming may not be able to quantify change or provide detailed insights into activities, but it provides valuable support in identifying solutions to improve working conditions. The ability of this framework to show relationships and linkages between different dimensions can assist in providing extension advice and help farmers to activate or develop effective levers for change and ultimately improve their working conditions ([206]).

Future research proposed:

For a comprehensive understanding of health and safety in agricultural systems (e. g. community-supported agricultural systems), it is necessary to incorporate qualitative health research from a first-person perspective into broader contextual debates and decision-making processes ([97]).

Furthermore, it is crucial to recognise the significant influence of economic pressures on risk-taking, as this underlines the active and creative ability of farmers to develop different solutions to similar economic challenges. This dual approach ensures that health and safety programmes and measures are both context-sensitive and adaptable to the different strategies that farmers use in response to economic pressures ([257]).

Good practices identified:

Three good practises in research and intervention are:

1. *Ethical, political and emotional analysis of farmers' distress:*

This approach challenges the traditional mental health framework and offers alternative social and political responses to alleviate farmers' distress and prevent suicide by focusing on the cultural, political and emotional dynamics that shape their experiences ([121]).

2. *Multidimensional framework to examine working conditions:*

A comprehensive theoretical framework examines multiple dimensions of working conditions, such as control, income, job security, health, and political experiences. This systemic analysis identifies specific trends, trade-offs and key issues in different farming systems (agroecological, organic and conventional) and provides insights to improve sustainability and working conditions in agriculture ([204]).

3. *Farmer responsibility and knowledge acquisition:*

Encouraging farmers to take responsibility for health, safety and the environment despite financial constraints promotes a culture of informed change. Programmes such as the Environmental Farm Plan and the Pesticide Safety Course, as well as personal research and peer discussions, help farmers to adapt their practises in a careful and informed way, contributing to an overall improvement in sustainability and safety in agriculture ([257]).

1.4. Risk perception, safety and health beliefs in agriculture as a cultural stress factor

Concrete actions proposed:

The overall conclusion from the concrete actions proposed is that improving the health, safety and working conditions of farm workers and farmers requires a multi-faceted and comprehensive approach. Key elements include:

1. *Culturally appropriate education and communication:*

Tailored health and safety information and education that addresses cultural differences (myths, stereotypes and conflicting health beliefs), literacy and language barriers. This includes explaining the reasons for safety behaviours (rather than just listing the right behaviours!) and involving farmers and (migrant) farm workers in community-based safety programmes ([47], [48], ([54], [117], [214], [557]).

2. *Regulatory and policy support:*

Enforce stricter regulations and best practises in occupational health and safety in agriculture, similar to other industries ([255]).

Encourage policy makers to consider farmers' wellbeing in their strategies and develop policies that support the economic viability of farms ([86]).

3. *Stakeholder engagement and training:*

Engage all stakeholders, including farm owners, workers, health professionals and regulators, in collaborative efforts to improve safety and health. Provide training that is appropriate to the context and addresses the specific needs and concerns of different farm groups ([262], ([263], [293], [329]).

4. *Economic and social support:*

Addressing general economic challenges and social structures that affect farm workers and farmers. Ensuring adequate rest and time off and supporting initiatives that improve economic stability and reduce risks ([319], [337]).

5. *Comprehensive health interventions:*

Conduct awareness campaigns, telemedicine consultations and support for farmers and farm families with disabilities. Ensure that health services are accessible, confidential and culturally appropriate ([223]).

By integrating the above practises, a more holistic and effective approach can be developed to support the diverse needs of the farming community, ultimately leading to a safer and healthier working environment.

Future research proposed:

1. *Interdisciplinary collaboration:*

Overcoming disciplinary silos to integrate insights from psychology, behavioural economics, risk science, sociology, anthropology and human geography. This collaboration will improve understanding of socioeconomic inequalities, the impact of policy and the mental processes that influence safety practises ([86]).

2. *Childcare and institutional support:*

Investigating the role of childcare facilities and institutional support in reducing injuries to children in agriculture. Considering the socio-economic realities and lived experiences of farmers can lead to better solutions for childcare during labour ([86]).

3. *Improved research tools and approaches:*

Develop and validate new research tools, such as adapted theoretical models, to better capture the health needs of farm workers. We should go beyond clinical samples to reduce selection bias and accurately estimate the prevalence of health problems ([117], [214], [223]).

4. *Community-based participatory research:*

Engaging researchers with diverse backgrounds and methodologies in community-based participatory research to address the concerns of farm workers and develop effective interventions. Organising emerging themes into models for further investigation and refinement ([329]).

5. *Changing safety attitudes and practises:*

Exploring ways how to influence the cost-benefit analysis of safety for older farmers and communicating solutions with them in an acceptable and understandable way ([394]).

6. *Historical and cross-cultural studies:*

Conducting comparative studies to determine the relative hazards and health risks of industrialised agriculture compared to other forms of food production. Historical and cross-cultural research will identify trends in farmer morbidity and mortality ([534]).

By integrating the above approaches, researchers and policy makers can develop more effective, contextualised strategies to improve the health, safety and overall well-being of farm workers and their families.

Good practices identified:

The finding that the employers surveyed have taken the necessary and mandated actions to reduce heat risks indicates that legislation to reduce heat-related illnesses has worked in California farms. In

addition, the campaigns to reduce heat-related illnesses and deaths in California appear to have been successful ([557]).

2. Cultural stressors in relation to safety, health and wellbeing in agriculture (OUTCOMES)

It is worth noting that the categorisation of cultural stressors in the form of fixed subtitles below is not a clear-cut and limited to only one dimension of the cultural source of health and safety risks in agriculture. On the contrary, they are interlinked in the studies examined, but usually focus on the one dimension that is emphasised in accordance with the above mentioned respective theoretical and methodological approach.

2.1. Gender identities as a cultural source of health and safety risks in agriculture

The reviewed studies that directly address gender as a cultural stressor ([6], [25], [176], [316], [435]) and those that indirectly address gender relations on the farm as a source of health and safety risks ([250], [257], [293], [263], [316], [470]) attempted to determine the relationship between gender and health, wellbeing and safety in agriculture. Despite different methodological approaches, the results of all studies confirmed this relationship. Latino migrant farm workers' "traditional machismo" was found to increase the impact of some stressors thought to be incongruent with their beliefs (e.g., fear of deportation and discrimination), while it did not alter the impact of congruent stressors (poverty and harsh working conditions) on depression outcomes [6]. Farmers who valued traditional and hegemonic notions of rural masculinity experienced the devastating consequences of extreme climate variability and national and global rural and agricultural restructuring as a personal failure or loss of a secure future based on old certainties, leading to a deterioration in their health (increasing levels of stress, depression and social isolation, sense of entrapment and suicidal ideation). Despite the observation that rural men are more able to talk about their health, especially with their immediate family, they continue to propagate the idea that they are strong and tough and therefore successful in farming, keep health problems to themselves, distrust support services and are more likely to turn to alcohol to "self-medicate" ([6], [293], [435]).

Women, on the other hand, foster the view of traditional masculinity by supporting their husbands and monitoring their health while ignoring their own health needs ([25], [435]). Their role as "helpers" on the farm stems from patriarchal relations, which may be directly linked to safety risk, as they do not undergo mandatory training on farm safety risk management (e.g., a course on pesticide safety), as they neither own and manage the farm, nor have health and disability insurance, which is at the discretion of the male operators of the farm. As they are exposed to greater financial and health risks due to their economic and occupational independence from their male partners, despite their hard work and multiple commitments, this may be related to their lower wellbeing in terms of mental health and their desire to leave the industry ([257], [263], [435], [470]).

Gendered responsibilities as a result of social hierarchies have been shown to affect the wellbeing (health) and safety of women farmers ([263], [316], [435], [470]) and farm workers ([176], [250]). Women face the challenges of balancing the demands of farm work (long working hours) with their domestic and caring responsibilities. Some farm women in the study [470] stated that it is difficult and stressful to manage multiple roles and tasks and that they are therefore not always able to fulfil their caring responsibilities effectively. Overall, women work more than men and start the working day with insufficient rest, but see their housework as a duty imposed on them by social norms, which they do not question ([250]). In addition to the challenges of balancing the demands of farm work (long hours) with their domestic responsibilities and access to health care, or working where they were told to work without being informed about pesticide use, the Latina women farm workers in the study [176] expressed concern about food security and supply as their primary responsibility, experienced social isolation, and their health (neurological disorders) was at risk from constant exposure to pesticides, as evidenced by biological monitoring.

2.2. Structural vulnerability and discrimination as a cultural stressor

The interrelated concepts of *structural vulnerability, structural violence and discrimination were identified as cultural stressors in numerous of the reviewed studies* ([39], [51], [66], [89], [154], [163], [176], [203], [213], [218], [250], [269], [283], [284], [443], [447], [466]) as they not only refer to *mechanisms of power* but also to *reified cultural constructions of deprived social groups* – in our case migrant and seasonal or foreign farm workers. Thus, the social production of the “face” of Latino American migrant farm workers was explained in the study ([89]) as *an act of cultural separation and demarcation* through which migrant farm workers are viewed and treated as “others” and “outsiders”. Their faces were given cultural meaning in the practises of daily life, had a figurative quality, were perceived in terms of a stereotype, and their labour camps were also facialised. Face has been explained as *a mode of perception* that determines ordinary interactions in empirical life and is crucial for the maintenance of structural violence, as it *can help legitimise patterns of racialised workplace hierarchy and spatial segregation* by farmers who have translated structural problems of increased quality demands and international competition into cultural problems related to Mexican backwardness. *Perceived bodily differences along ethnic lines*, e.g., Triqui from Mexico are too small for the better paid job of apple picking than berry picking, a task that presumably fits their body size, serve to naturalise and justify inequalities on farms ([283]).

The farm workers in the study ([89]) experienced sleeplessness not only as a negation of the natural phenomenon of sleep, but mostly as an inability to go home and leave work behind because they had to endure no privacy and constant lighting and heat in the overcrowded labour camps, i.e., poor wellbeing. Farmers *naturalised the nastiness* of the camps as a stereotypical *ethnic pathology*, obscuring the role of government and agribusiness neglect in creating these conditions. Farmers were in constant interaction with farm workers, despite language barriers, but visits to the camps and meetings with workers in face time were also about the management of property, which was assumed to be constantly available for the farmer to monitor and manage, even when the working day was over. Finally, a migrant public health worker who provided free medical care in the camps saw the crew leaders (who recruit, transport, pay and supervise the farm workers) as the most dangerous part of the labour because they could make it difficult for farm workers to access health services or clinics ([89]).

The structural vulnerability of migrant farm workers is embedded in *the understanding of race and ethnicity* that both workers and farmers see as *naturalising principles for the organisation of labour*. As the studies ([203], [283], [284]) show, work activities are structured by an ethnically reified division of labour determined by historical patterns of migration, English language proficiency, racialised and nationalised notions of what constitutes a “good worker”, and the pecking order of perceived indigeneity, as each ethnic group is expected to deserve its relative social status. At the bottom of the hierarchy are the “purest indigenous”, the “undercivilised” “savages” and “simpletons” with the worst work, wage and housing opportunities on the farms. Their *structural vulnerability* is *underlined* not only by *official and unofficial farm policies*, but also by *the global hierarchy of citizenship and agribusiness*, which is reinforced by policies and practises that make each group of farm workers structurally vulnerable in their own way. Everyone on the farm worries about factors over which they have little or no control. The farm executives are vulnerable to macro-social structures, while vulnerability increases down the labour hierarchy, *particularly on the basis of ethnicity and citizenship* ([283], [284]).

Moreover, *governmentality* affects workers’ health and wellbeing by *fuelling ethnic competition and reducing* the likelihood that workers will advocate for *better working conditions and solidarity* among them. As a result, farm workers suffer in silence from heat exhaustion and dehydration while working under tarps, from green tobacco disease, from neurological stress damage due to the pace and repetition required in manual harvesting, from working in the fields shortly after spraying without protective equipment, or even from hunger and loneliness as they leave their families and communities behind to earn a living. *The ethnically segregated accommodation* was particularly poor: the barracks were hot, overcrowded and offered little privacy, there were vermin, pesticide residues and a lack of (functional) hygiene, washing and cooking facilities, which posed potential health hazard for the migrant farm workers and their families ([203], [250], [283], [284], [447]). The labour camps were so *isolated*

from the local centres that workers often complained of boredom ([203]); the small or few camps also lacked opportunities to build a migrant community for social support and to better cope with work-related stress ([466]).

The disproportionately high rate at which disadvantaged groups (by ethnicity, gender, socioeconomic background, etc.) are exposed to pollutants or denied access to sources with environmental or health benefits is the focus of several studies that took a critical race or structural vulnerability perspective. Latino workers who reported more frequent experiences of so-called *farm worker-specific environmental microaggressions* (related to everyday discrimination in working conditions, housing/neighbourhood, language, and coworker evaluation – FEMS scale), also reported more symptoms of depression and anxiety compared to their reports of general *environmental microaggressions* (centred on the Racial Ethnic Microaggression Scale), suggesting that the FEMS measure better captures farm worker-specific concerns and experiences that are relevant to this population ([51]). In the study [283], too, depression in the form of somatisation and substance abuse are the problems most frequently mentioned by physicians and nurses among migrant farm workers. Substance abuse is mainly attributed to men and the younger generation, which often worsens family relationships and tends to lead to domestic violence ([443], [447]). Interviews with migrant farm workers indicate that the main proximal determinants of this suffering are lack of opportunities for social advancement and job choice, social isolation, disrespect and discrimination by supervisors, locals, medical providers and sending-country government agents who even deny them the medical services ([269], [283], [443], [447]). *Environmental discrimination* was a focus of the study, which revealed that farm workers and their families are exposed not only to the hazardous working conditions in the field, but also to the wider region in which they live (e.g., the nearby, drying Salton Sea), which they believe, causes their and their families constant health sufferings (respiratory illnesses, poor eye health, itchy skin, nosebleeds, sinusitis, colds, allergies, etc.) ([154]).

Inappropriate working conditions in agriculture also have a negative impact on the physical health of migrant farm workers. This ranges from diabetes, premature births, headaches and hearing damage from noisy machinery to bladder and kidney problems, especially in women, due to reduced water intake and urine retention due to the remoteness of toilets, to musculoskeletal conditions, vision problems, and stomach problems from drinking controversial water, food spoiled by heat and lack of drinks and food, as well as lung and skin diseases due to exposure to dust, pesticides and chemicals in the workplace ([154], [250], [269], [283], [284], [443], [447]). Although they also experienced stress and trauma related to their working conditions, they again feared the consequences of *structural vulnerability* in seeking medical help, either because they were immigrants, were seen as a danger to themselves or others, or because they were afraid of losing their working hours and income or their job ([154], [250], [269], [443], [447]). Therefore, *self-medication* through traditional healers, herbs, alcohol, illegal drugs, drinking caffeinated beverages or mixing painkillers with energy drinks and sharing medication was commonplace ([154], [447]). Nevertheless, the study participants wanted health information, including about mental health, although it is not common in immigrant communities to seek psychological help, especially not among men ([154]).

The observation that migrant farm workers are good workers but bad patients is also believed by most rural health care providers in a study that examined how the structures of international labour migration programmes and health services affect the care of rural workers. Among the various challenges they face in providing care to migrant agricultural workers (e.g., one physician commented that they wouldn't see a doctor unless they're very sick, healthcare facilities are often long distances from farm residences and workers lack independent transportation, workers involvement in medical consultations raised concerns about privacy and confidentiality, including the use of medical information by consular officials, the lack of translation services) were *migrant workers' concerns about jeopardising their current or future employment* in the receiving country and fears that their employer or consular officials might find out about their health problems, which would ultimately leading to deportation if they are unable to work. Cultural issues were also identified due to *different interpretations of illness* between migrant farm workers and healthcare providers in the host country, which often reflected the usual practises in their countries of origin and leaving many of the most immediate factors of suffering unrecognised and

untreated ([163], ([269], [283], [284], [447])). Australian farmers report similar problems with health care as migrant farm workers. They complain about the long distances and limited working hours of health facilities and the rotation of doctors, as well as their lack of understanding of the farmers' way of life, which leads them to distrust local health services and favour help from family and friends ([293]).

Language discrimination against farm workers, whether it is not being able to speak the language of the employer or being discriminated against in the workplace because they speak their native language, or not receiving safety training in one of the indigenous languages, frustrates many farm workers as it proves to be a barrier to education and training in safety practises and the communication of warnings ([213], [283]). The study [284] has also shown the importance of the ability to learn English in order to be promoted and helps to illuminate the contours of the structures that lead to vulnerability. As migrant farm workers face many uncertainties due to their liminal status – they may not be part of the formal educational, employment and health systems of the host and home countries – they remain excluded from the loop of comprehensive health protection, limiting their access to health services and increasing the potential for health problems ([269]).

In addition, farm workers feel that employers are under time pressure, which they translate into the perceived *threat of firing them* if they do not work accurately or quickly enough, and that farmers do not care about the health of their employees because safety training is not considered cost-effective. Therefore, they submit to unsafe working conditions and continue to work even though they have acute symptoms of pesticide exposure and little or no control over this dangerous workplace ([66], [213], [283], [284], [443]).

Despite differences in focus, the study ([39]) showed that some local and foreign farm workers agreed that in addition to poor management and too little time for animal welfare training, *myths about the culture of foreign workers, language problems, working without feeling valued or rewarded for the extra work, and feeling part of a problem* reflected problematic working conditions on the farm, which were a source of pressure and stress for them.

The only study which considers the seemingly *positive discrimination* caused by the *policy of agricultural exceptionalism* introduced during the COVID-19 pandemic ([218]) classified migrant agricultural workers as good workers if they crossed the border easily, bypassed mandatory quarantine or bought fake negative tests at the border, thus put their health at risk which was also reinforced by the fact that none of the farms observed developed recommended solutions to prevent the spread of the SARS-CoV-2 virus. In addition, farm workers did not have to pay for accommodation and usually lived within a few metres of the employer's home, which made workers vulnerable to raising concerns about the work, the quality of accommodation, the wages offered or other forms of abuse of their rights. Some employers have made systematic efforts to improve the quality of accommodation offered in order to be competitive in recruiting foreign labour. However, the accommodation observed was often below the minimum standards for accommodation – it did not meet the standards for mandatory quarantine, workers could not count on a separate sleeping area or access to a separate kitchen or bathroom, and despite restrictions on movement and access to shops, employers did not offer prepared food to seasonal workers during the pandemic.

2.3. Ruptures in the moral economy (ethics and emotions) as a cultural source of health and safety risks in agriculture

Studies that focus their analysis on ruptures in the moral economy of farmers that lead them to experience unexpected difficulties in their work environment that are beyond their control and power, or that make them unable to reconcile their own ideas of being a good farmer with the new agricultural realities, which constrain their choices, their values and also their safety behaviour, suggest that the moral and emotional dimensions of the political economy of farming also have an impact on their well-being, including their health, through their *negative emotions of disappointment or distrust* because of *experienced ethical injustice and lack of support from the government* ([97], [121], [204], [206], [257]).

For example, alternative food networks were believed to surpass many of the operational difficulties of agriculture as an unpredictable occupation shaped by various risk factors. However, the study conducted in Hungary ([97]) shows that farmers in community-supported agriculture (CSA) face both engagement-related work difficulties and their subjective discomfort due to *the experienced ruptures of the moral economy in their new forms of consumer-producer connection on the one hand and their work-life balance on the other*. *Conflicting autonomy* (maintaining the obligations of local sustainable agriculture and everyday obligations to themselves), the pressure of boxes and social overload are examples of the sources of stress experienced by CSA farmers. They arise from the mismatch between their moral obligation to good farm management and high standards in producing healthy and sustainable food for the CSA community and the hard-to-achieve results, leading to anxiety, dissatisfaction and emotions with negative consequences (e.g., sadness, anger and embarrassment), in short, ill-being.

The observation that *the conversion to agroecological farming can bring new hardships for working conditions and wellbeing* was discussed in the three studies ([204], [206], [257]).

The first study was conducted among conventional, organic and agroecological vegetable producers in Belgium gardening on small, medium and large plots or with field crops, and the second among French cattle farmers adopting agroecological practises. Despite the strong interest and positive intrinsic benefits of their work in market gardening, especially the beneficial contribution to society, all producer groups *felt constrained by the socio-economic and political context*. However, agroecological producers, especially those with limited land, were the most constrained as they were affected by factors such as unaffordable land prices, low food price policies, subsidy policies, increasing competition in the supply of vegetable boxes and consumers who did not want to commit to them in the long term, which affected their wellbeing and compounded their *frustration by their inability to fully realise their vision of farming in practise* ([204]).

Similarly, some livestock farmers *felt constrained piloting the new system*, as adopting agroecological practises requires long-term thinking, setting new goals and considering multiple parameters and analysing each situation rather than always applying the same solution. This was perceived as a source of stress by those who *felt that they could not master certain elements of their new farming system or reconcile them with their personal values* in terms of economic benefits in terms of being more autonomous in the decision-making, protecting the environment, producing safe food, preserving human and animal health, providing a positive image of their profession, etc. ([206]).

The study [257] on Canadian farmers with conventional, no-till, organic and mixed grain and livestock production shows that they are all *confronted with an ambivalent discourse on the part of the agricultural industry, government agencies and farmers organisations*. *On the one hand, the demands of environmental groups and labour unions* regarding health, safety and environmental protection are presented as a threat to the survival and independence of agriculture, while on the other hand, farmers are encouraged to change their practises to become safer and more environmentally sustainable. These discourses focus primarily on profitability and farmer responsibility, which is reflected in the fact that the farms with the most extensive safety changes in the study were the most conventional, managerialist and neoliberal farms. In this case, the exacerbation of risks associated with farmers' focus on growth, flexibility and lean production is ignored. Moreover, all less affluent farmers, including *organic farmers who have tried to move away from the productivist imperative in favour of safety and environmental goals, may face the problem of profitability and survival*, meaning that economics is still a reason to take safety risks rather than control them. To summarise, the organic movement can hardly be seen as an answer to the safety problem until it truly takes an alternative direction for food production and begins to promote farm safety as being as important as environmental issues [257].

In the study, which was initiated by the Australian Grape Growers Association to explore their perceptions of the economic, social and health impacts of the drought, farmers experienced that deflating land prices and a lack of potential buyers combined with crushing financial debt severely limited the industry's options and contributed to them feeling trapped and hopeless ([121]). However, they did

not blame themselves for their own financial problems and the general economic crisis in the industry, but rather *saw themselves as victims of ethical breaches within the economic arrangements, carrying a disproportionate amount of risk in the supply chain*. The majority of farmers saw the grape glut of the time as a result of government interference in the wine industry, supporting corporate investment and unethical behaviour in relation to contract farming, where most wineries made an offer to farmers that they could either accept or refuse, including the suspension of contracts and late or non-payment for their produce. The loyalty of the winegrowers was not appreciated by the wineries. *The winegrowers perceived this as an ethical injustice and lack of support from the government*, which affected their wellbeing as they felt hurt, angry and cheated, which threatened their self-esteem and was detrimental to their wellbeing.

Disappointment and distrust of government structures that directly impact safety culture can also be observed among resource-poor African American farmers from the United States in the study [329] presented in the next section, which focuses primarily on their safety and health concerns and perceptions of risk. They believe that the institutions whose ostensible mission is to help farmers and which organise agricultural extension programmes have too few resources of their own and therefore try to appease their funders and constituents, resulting in impractical training tailored to the needs of large-scale farmers.

2.4. Risk perception, safety and health beliefs in agriculture as a cultural stress factor

Perceived risk, danger and control over the working and living environment in agriculture are neither general nor universal, but culturally constructed, as most TOPIC 2 studies show ([47], [48], [54], [86], [117], [214], [223], [255], [256], [262], [263], [293], [319], [329], [337], [394], [470], [534], [557]), but also partly the studies with other research foci ([257], [316], [435]). As some studies show ([47], [48], [54], [86], [117], [214], [223], [557]), these different perceptions of risk, danger and control over the working and living environment reflect rather cultural (and structural) differences between migrant farm workers, farmers or supervisors, extension workers, health care providers or outreach, or between farmers with different agricultural backgrounds, between women, men and children, etc. In turn:

Most MIGRANT FARM WORKERS – especially those on H2A visas – reported that despite some recent improvements in the provision of basic safety and sanitation facilities, they still lacked a safe workplace and adequate accommodation ([47], [48]). On the other hand, about a third of them stated that pesticides were not a problem for their health, the health of other farm workers or their children, that they harmed unborn children or affected their ability to have children. Studies have also shown that migrant farm workers are at risk of ingesting pesticides or contaminating others they come into contact with due to their belief in humoral medicine (e.g., cooling down before showering). In addition, more of them reported having no control over reducing their pesticide exposure at work, especially those who migrated for work or lived in housing on the farm. On the other hand, the minority of those who felt they could largely avoid the harmful effects of pesticides at work and at home were those who had a labour contract and lived in farm housing. In addition, the results show that *better access to information for farm workers (e.g., signs about pesticide application) increases their perceived control but decreases their perceived risk of pesticide exposure* ([48]).

THE CHILDREN OF MIGRANT AND SEASONAL WORKERS also reported negative aspects of working in agriculture related to heat-related illnesses (dizziness, headaches, fainting, sudden muscle cramps, dry skin, vomiting, etc.), citing the work in the heat, the lack of water supply or water that was not always clean, the intense pace of work and the close supervision; some believed that the children, unaccustomed to the heat, were at greater risk, wrongly downplaying their own risk ([54]).

Workers on Canadian farms are also less inclined to normalise the risks they face than their employers. However, they *accept dangerous working conditions and the legal status quo due to lack of employment opportunities*, high cost of living and a desire to retain the same autonomy if they could one day become farmers themselves ([470]).

Health beliefs were at the centre of the studies ([117], [214], [223]) aimed at improving preventive (health) care in agriculture. The studies, which used different self-reported health models ([117], [214]), showed that (Latino American) agricultural workers believe that their pain is caused by hot-cold imbalance (rather than a consequence of labour tasks in difficult working conditions), and that this belief may also influence their willingness to try Western medical treatment strategies for symptoms. Instead, they favoured self-medication and alternative traditional healing methods over seeking Western medical care, albeit also in response to the barriers to such care and to convey their critical need to work through the pain or illness ([117]). The use of various self-treatments was also common for skin conditions, but the use of prescription medication by a healthcare provider was rare, partly because many skin conditions did not interfere with the work lives of farm labourers to the extent that they would need to take time out to use the healthcare system. More often, however, cultural beliefs in this population, such as the hot-cold (humoral) theory of health, folk illnesses and traditional herbal remedies, cause medical care to be delayed or medical treatments to be ignored ([214]).

In contrast to farm workers, FARMERS believe that workers are rarely exposed to anything dangerous, that as employers they provide adequate safety precautions in the field and proper housing, and they complain about the laziness of workers and their lack of interest in hygiene and property. *Farmers as employers and their supervisors often believe that the workers themselves should take care of the safety risk. However, farmers never or only occasionally prioritise the safety of themselves, their family members or their employers. They are also unwilling or able to prioritise safe working practises, allegedly due to economic fears and time and work pressures. Farmers value hard work, the unregulated nature of agricultural labour and believe in their autonomy.* They often point to farming ethics, including fatalism, as the reason for their risky behaviour and they often normalise pain and illness. Ignoring health issues is also valued in the farming community, and they often consider farming to be safe or as safe as other occupations. As for the safety of their children, studies show that they want to use an invisible play area, while they rarely have a limited and safe physical play area. Some normalise the risks and describe playing in grain silos as a child as something common and unproblematic in their socialisation on the farm. Finally, reference to the culture of privacy, the independence of farmers and the lack of understanding by health and social service providers of the demands of farming is recognised as a barrier to farmers who try return to work after injury or with a disability.

In turn, the study ([47]) provides an example in which farmers who employ migrant labourers report that workers are rarely exposed to anything hazardous, that as employers they provide washing facilities in the field and adequate shelter, and complain about workers' laziness and lack of interest in hygiene and property.

Furthermore, EMPLOYERS AND SUPERVISORS often believe that workers should take care of the safety risk themselves ([284], [337], [557]). For example, the study [557] on US agricultural employers, points to the contradictory beliefs of respondents who are convinced that they actively care for the crew and cater to their needs and that workers need to look after themselves, which is particularly problematic in areas where legislation is not specifically designed to protect workers (e.g., managing workers in rain, fires, poor air quality as opposed to working in the heat).

Several studies ([255], [256], [257], [262], [263], [284], [293], [319], [329], [337], [394], [435], [534]) show that FARM OPERATORS never or only occasionally prioritise the safety of themselves, their family members or their employees or that farmers are unwilling or unable to prioritise safe working practises. The most commonly cited reasons for this are high levels of economic anxiety, time and work pressure, as farmers feel they have no choice but to work in order to earn a living and mitigate the negative effects of weather and other uncertainties. Economic and labour stress is attributed to both small farmers with limited resources because they are less likely to invest in new, safer equipment, and larger farms because they are more concerned about financial returns. However, studies show that all farmers, whether small or large, conventional or organic, value hard work. They work long hours, are tired and eat irregularly while working ([257], [329], [534]). The uncertainty associated with life on the farm can

lead not only to stress but also to mental health problems, illnesses and accidents due to distractions, although some farmers believe that stress can be good because “it gets you going” ([262], [263], [534]).

There were also other examples of blatant contradictions between knowledge and practise that have little to do with economic considerations, as some farmers point to agrarian ethics, including fatalism and habit, as the reason for their risky behaviour ([257]). The experience and presence of pain and illness (back pain, ankle and knee swelling, high blood pressure, diabetes, arthritis, etc.) was normalised, as were beliefs and expectations about daily health fluctuations and managing reasonable risk of injury ([293], [316], [329], [337], [394]).

The strategy of ignoring health problems is highly valued in the farming community until the health problem worsens, limits the ability to do daily farm work, or is noticed by someone else, especially female farmers and other family members ([293], [316], [329]). Limited resource African-American male farmers also believe that their years of experience and the good fortune of having had no significant accidents are the reasons they maintain their relatively unsafe customary farming practises ([329]), Canadian farm operators express the rationale that there is intrinsic safety within families ([470]), while experienced male farmers in the US believe that they are more capable and less at risk than others ([394]). They also describe playing in grain containers as children at risk of suffocation as something normal, which points to the problem of normalising risks through the socialisation of children on the farm.

Some farmers *minimize the dangers of farming for their health* because they nowadays know how to handle chemicals that are relatively harmless compared to the past. This self-construction of farmers' knowledge, responsibility and control is in line with the safety discourses of governments, corporate and farm organisations, which insist that farmers have the necessary means and motivation to avoid farming accidents and exposure to harmful pesticides ([257]).

Furthermore, farmers of all generations *value the unregulated nature of agricultural labour*, as they believe that they are relatively autonomous. A generational shift has been noted among THE YOUNGER GENERATION OF FARMERS working alongside their fathers, as they see the need for a fairer and more secure workplace ([470]).

The differences in safety beliefs regarding THE RISK EXPOSURE OF THEIR CHILDREN were also analysed between parents with different agricultural backgrounds in so-called first-generation and multigenerational families with different parenting styles ([86]). The results show that the majority of parents in both types of farming families shared the view that farming is safer or as safe as other occupations, that they reported high levels of confidence in their ability to supervise farm work and in their knowledge of safety, that almost all planned to use an invisible play area, while the use of a physical play area was significantly lower, and that almost two-thirds of them reported that at least one child (more boys than girls) had suffered an injury directly related to farming at some point in their lives. The main differences between first and multigenerational respondents were related to demographic characteristics and parenting styles. Multigenerational respondents may have more resources because they have a higher level of education and have fewer and older children. In terms of parenting style, multigenerational respondents were more likely to have a strong involvement parenting style (authoritarian and permissive), which was previously associated with a lower risk of injury.

Finally, one of the findings of the study examining barriers (and facilitators) to farmers' return to work after injury or acquired disability was that at the micro level, a “*culture of privacy*” and “*independence*” persisted as barriers to return to farming, while at the mesosystem level, one of the barriers expressed by farmers related to the fact that health and social service providers did not always encourage them to continue working or return to farming, presumably because, as non-farmers, they did not understand the demands of farming or the adjustments that could be made ([223]).

Lastly, the studies also show that THE EXTENSION WORKERS who are in contact with farmers share their views on migrant or seasonal workers, while HEALTH CARE PROVIDERS OR OUTREACH

WORKERS who meet farm workers in clinics or visit them regularly at work and at home more often confirm their inadequate working and living conditions ([47]).

DRIVERS OF CHANGE AND MEGA-TRENDS

The drivers of change and mega-trends described below were not the focus of the analysis in the selected articles of TOPIC 2, but were mentioned in the sections (mostly in the introductions) describing the rationale and broader context of the research.

Neoliberalism and Globalisation

Several studies ([121], [257], [394], [534]) have highlighted in particular the impact of neoliberal political economic reforms and the globalisation of agricultural trade on the ongoing restructuring of agriculture. Farmers are under great pressure to restructure their farms in direct response to increasing global competition for the distribution of food resources, rising input and land costs, low farm-gate prices for food and declining government subsidies. The tight economic situation with insufficient cash flow and high indebtedness, criticism from society, difficulties in maintaining traditional values and lifestyles and reconciling work and family life are factors that are known to have a negative impact on farmers' health and safety ([6], [206], [213], [255], [256], [262], [293], [316], [319], [534]).

Technological advancement and demographic development on farms

The restructuring of agriculture affects the demographics of farming communities and the social roles between generations and genders on farms. Due to technological advances, the latter require fewer employers or are economically forced to bring labour needs into the family, whose members take on more and changing tasks and roles ([25], [233], [316], [337], [394]). Many farming families rely on off-farm work to maintain the financial viability of an expanding farm, which is mostly done by women ([25], [534]). Despite technological advances, working conditions in agriculture remain difficult and are associated with an increased workload, including in administration. In addition, small rural communities are experiencing a decline in services ([25]). As a result, agriculture is losing people's interest in becoming farmers; the renewal of generations of farmers is at stake as young people migrate from rural areas and seek career opportunities outside agriculture ([25], [39], [204], [262]). Therefore, the closure of many family farms is common due to technological advances, the consolidation of land into larger farms and the retirement of older farmers without successors ([25], [262], [263], [316]).

For the remaining family farms, a further global shift towards a stronger market orientation is predicted in order to continue replacing human labour with capital-intensive, heavily fossil fuel-dependent equipment and inputs, to increase their acreage and livestock numbers and to try to become more efficient ([316], [319], [394], [534]). This means, among other things, longer working hours with more intensive and prolonged contact with heavy machinery under isolated working conditions ([534]).

Agroecological transition in European agriculture

In Europe, the young people who stay in farming are often qualified and well educated, not only in agriculture but also in management and business. In the last 15 years, however, the trend has been for skilled and well-educated young and new farmers to create alternatives to the modern multinational food system and to practise their food-related principles, for example community-supported agriculture initiatives ([97]). A clear shift in values towards agricultural diversification can be observed in European society, as young farmers not only favour a high income, but also value leisure and other work-related ventures that are in line with agroecological principles, social cohesion and consumer confidence, the importance of sustainability and ethical aspects such as animal welfare ([39]). This is in line with claims by scientists and associations that agroecological farming, which is also subsidised by some governments, can provide better working conditions and is less harmful to the environment than conventional farming ([204], [206]). However, young and other farmers are confronted with a new consumer environment, take on new, time-consuming work responsibilities, struggle to balance family

and farm work, and face further tensions in their farming lifestyles that can indirectly affect their health and safety ([97], [206]).

Labour Shortages, Migration, and Neoliberalism

Virtually all studies have dealt with the ongoing global changes in the structures of working life in relation to the labour market. They have emphasised the growing need for migrant and seasonal farm workers, but employers, health care providers, government officials and policy makers do not take into account the discriminatory practises and power relations that worsen the health and safety of migrant workers in agriculture.

Greater need for and the issue of availability of workforce in agriculture

Labour shortages are a growing problem, and migrant and seasonal workers of different nationalities are becoming increasingly important in agriculture. This also applies to Europe, where many agricultural workers come from Eastern Europe ([39], [218]). Some agricultural employers fear losing experienced labour and not attracting new workers, even if older farmers are unable to work fast and long hours. These fears have existed in the US for 50 years and have not yet been realised, as new labour is always available ([557]). Some countries, including Canada and Poland, have enacted laws to facilitate the entry and employment of migrant farm workers ([163], [218], [269]).

Worldwide, the number of seasonal and migrant workers in agriculture has increased dramatically as family labour is replaced by hired labour ([48], [154], [269]). In the USA, where studies on migrant workers in agriculture predominate, some trends can be identified as to which groups of migrant workers in agriculture are increasing in numbers. The majority of migrant farm workers are Latinx as opposed to African Americans, who dominated in the 1980s ([48], [89], [154]). Increasing numbers of migrant farm workers are from indigenous communities such as Mexico and Guatemala, making communication and acculturation difficult ([213], [466]). The proportion of women in the agricultural labour force in the USA has increased significantly. They are more economically and socially vulnerable than men, which affects their well-being and health ([176]). Children, not only from farm families but also from migrant families, continue to be an important labour force whose work is unregulated and therefore extremely vulnerable to heat-related illnesses, occupational accidents and deaths ([54], [86], [443]).

Persistent structural violence against migrant and seasonal farm workers

The studies listed below, particularly from the US and Canada, show the persistent exploitative and unethical attitude of employers, healthcare providers, government officials and wider society towards migrant farm workers. Migrant and seasonal agricultural workers have little ability to control their working conditions ([48], [54], [117], [250], [269], [466]). They are exposed to injuries and diseases from handling machinery, pesticides and weather exposure ([47], [54], [66], [117], [154], [214], [466]). In addition, many of them are severely affected by poverty, prejudice, hostility and discrimination in the communities where they work and live, and suffer from stress-related disorders such as anxiety and depression; they also have poor access to health care ([6], [51], [89], [117], [154], [176], [203], [213], [214], [269], [283], [447], [466]).

Climate Change

Another set of studies mentioned below deals with climate change and its impact on policy measures to reduce the negative economic impact of extreme weather events on the economic situation of farms or on labour management due to the impact of extreme weather conditions on the health and safety of farm workers. In both areas, measures to support farmers are inadequate. This promotes unequal power relations between industrial and family farming and unethical practises by farmers towards their employees, leading to mental and other health problems for all involved.

Climate change in interaction with neoliberal agriculture

Climate change could seriously worsen the safety and health of agricultural workers over the next 50 years and increase their structural vulnerability, as rising temperatures could increase workers' exposure to chemicals in the fields and lead to new pathogens, diseases and wildfires that affect air quality ([557]). Global climate change is already leading to an increase in the frequency and intensity of extreme heat events and increasing the risk of heat-related illnesses, putting farm workers, especially migrant workers, at particular risk of injury and illness ([54], [154]). In addition, agricultural employers in the US complain about the heat and its contribution to crop losses and thus loss of labour, as workers migrate to where there is work for them ([557]).

Two studies from Australia ([25], [121]) show the effects of climate change on family farms. Frequent extreme weather events such as long periods of drought jeopardise their livelihoods, as it is very difficult to produce crops in the face of dwindling water supplies. Some farmers have been forced to sell their natural resources, which are often controlled by the state and multinational companies. This situation has led to health problems being downplayed because they limit farmers' valued autonomy, cause them distress and have other social consequences that are also linked to farmers' increasing indebtedness and poverty, which ultimately jeopardise their notions of being a good farmer.

(Future) stronger regulation of labour management in extreme weather conditions

In view of climate change, we can expect more regulations for the management of agricultural workers ([557]). Safety issues in agriculture have become increasingly important over the last 30 years, but continue to be excluded from regulations ([257]). This exclusion and the narratives underpinning specific agricultural safety regulations are linked to the extreme forms of precarity and exploitation within the food system ([89], [470]). In the absence of safety regulations and approaches to community involvement in the agricultural working and living environment of farm workers, the voluntariness of safety standards and educational approaches has been questioned in terms of their effectiveness in the agricultural context, although they remain an important component of safety and health in agricultural work ([48], [97], [154], [255], [447]).

CONCLUSIONS

This chapter highlights the cultural foundations of agricultural health and safety risks, identifies gaps in current research and offers new perspectives based on the dynamic concept of farming culture. Research on health and safety in agriculture has historically focused on technical, health, psychological and psychiatric frameworks, often neglecting the socio-cultural and structural factors that affect the health and well-being of farmers and farm workers. However, the ongoing modernisation of agriculture reflects cultural negotiations between different and multiple stakeholders and actors in agriculture. Farmers' and farm workers' responses to innovation and economic change are deeply embedded in their cultural norms, identities and practices.

Therefore, we conducted a literature review to answer the general question of TOPIC 2:

How does farming culture shape the safety, health and well-being of farmers and farm workers, focusing on farmers' and workers' understanding of risks, hazards and problematic relationships in their workplace as well as changes that (directly or indirectly) affect the farming (safety) culture.

Following the dynamic concept of culture, we identified four groups of cultural sources of health and safety risks in agriculture from the 45 articles reviewed. The first group of articles refers to gender identities and relationships as cultural sources of health and safety risks in agriculture, the second group considers structural vulnerability and discrimination as a cultural stressor, the third group discusses ruptures in the moral economy (ethics and emotions) and the fourth, risk perceptions, safety and health beliefs in agriculture. The above findings on the individual cultural stressors identified confirm that **farming culture strongly influences the safety, health and well-being of farmers and farm workers** in all aspects investigated.

Cultural sources and their impact on health, safety and well-being in agriculture

- *Gender identities* and their dynamics: Traditional gender roles exacerbate health risks, with men experiencing stress related to their masculinity and women facing increased vulnerability due to patriarchal structures.
- *Structural vulnerabilities*: Migrant and seasonal workers face systemic discrimination, unsafe conditions and limited access to healthcare, which increases their health and safety risks.
- *Moral economy*: Ethical conflicts, socio-economic pressures and systemic injustices contribute to farmers' emotional distress and undermine their trust in institutional support.
- *Risk perception and health beliefs*: Farmers and workers often normalise risky behaviours and prioritise financial stability over safety, which reinforces hazardous conditions. In addition, their culturally different health beliefs lead them to mistrust and avoid, ignore or delay available medical treatments or safety precautions as inadequate (if they are available at all).

In addition, the systematic literature review identifies critical gaps and opportunities in understanding the cultural sources of health and safety risks in agriculture. Key insights include:

Underrepresentation of vulnerable groups: Research focuses predominantly on male farmers and neglects women, LGBTQIA+ individuals, youth, the elderly, the disabled, indigenous and ethnic minorities. Greater inclusion in studies is essential for effective and equitable health and safety interventions.

Geographic gaps: Most studies are from the US, Canada, Australia and New Zealand, while European contexts, particularly migrant workers, are underrepresented. This emphasises the need for broader geographical coverage.

Systemic challenges: Neoliberal reforms, globalisation and climate change are putting additional pressure on agriculture, exacerbating labour shortages, economic vulnerability and health risks. These changes require systemic reforms to ensure resilience, equity and sustainability.

Effective interventions:

- *Culturally sensitive approaches*: Interventions must address gender-, age- and ethnicity-specific stressors, empower marginalised groups and incorporate community-based participatory methods.
- *Policy and educational reforms*: Stricter regulations, targeted safety education and customised technical solutions can mitigate risks.
- *Ethical frameworks*: developing ethical codes and addressing moral and emotional challenges are critical to farmer well-being.

Research directions: Future studies should focus on gender-, age- and ethnicity-specific issues, interdisciplinary approaches, and historical and cross-cultural analyses to better understand and address health and safety challenges in agriculture.

Identified good practises:

- Dealing with microaggressions and improving health care on the ground.
- Development of ethical codes and promotion of a safer working environment.
- Legislation requiring employers to take action (e.g. prevention of heat-related illnesses in California).

General conclusion:

The chapter emphasises that health and safety risks in agriculture are deeply rooted in socio-cultural dynamics shaped by structural inequalities, cultural norms and evolving economic pressures. Addressing these risks requires a shift away from traditional frameworks of health and safety in agriculture towards culturally sensitive, participatory and interdisciplinary approaches. Interventions must prioritise the inclusion of underrepresented groups, focus on systemic reforms and recognise the dynamic interplay between individual agency and structural constraints. Such efforts are critical to promoting equitable, sustainable and resilient agricultural systems.

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CHAPTER 3: SOCIAL PROTECTION OF FARMERS AND FARMWORKERS

STARTING POINTS

The interest of governments and international organisations in providing social protection to vulnerable members of society is growing in developed as well as in developing countries (Mumtaz, 2023). In agriculture, this could be also due the fact that social protection and agricultural policies overlap. Social protection policies could help people improve their livelihoods by expanding their assets, using them more efficiently and in turn contribute to agricultural development (Sabates-Wheeler et al., 2009). Namely, sustainable rural development requires tackling vulnerability as well as decreasing poverty (Devereaux, 2001). Thus, in the long term, social protection can help smooth consumption, improve and build human capital and enable investments that could improve people's resilience to future crises (United Nations, 2021). According to the United Nations (2021), poverty reduction has not always led to decreased rural inequalities and to a lessening of the urban-rural divide, as disparities in access to basic services continue to exist globally within rural areas as well between rural and urban areas and are particularly evident for some population groups. Additionally, the impact of economic restructuring and structural adjustment policies further reduces the role of national governments in providing safety nets for their populations, which experience the effect of these policies in different ways. Social and cultural capital are inevitably stratified and there exist radical differences in access to essential goods, services and information in both national and international contexts (Okongwu and Mencher, 2000). There has been only one comprehensive review on the interaction of social protection and agriculture (Tirivayi et al., 2016) using empirical evidence on how social protection impacts agricultural production and how agricultural interventions reduce risk and vulnerability at the household and local economy levels in Africa, Asia, Latin America and the Caribbean. Most studies under this review demonstrate that social protection can increase agricultural production while agricultural interventions can lower vulnerability, but with differences across particular cases. Gizaw et al. (2022) conducted a more specific systematic review to identify key approaches from international experiences to enhance access to primary health care services in rural communities, but not focussing exclusively on farming communities. This systematic literature review found that community health programs or community-directed healthcare interventions, school-based healthcare services, student-led healthcare services, outreach services or mobile clinics, family health programme, empanelment, community health funding schemes, telehealth, integrative medicine, and working with non-profit private sectors and NGOs are key strategies to improve access to primary health services in rural communities.

Studies have discovered risk and vulnerability as key features of rural livelihoods and people at risk try to manage uncertainty both through informal community support systems/safety nets (e.g. support from the extended family, friends, neighbours) as well as through state interventions (Devereux, 2001). Meeting social needs through social policy programmes could therefore be important for shaping the farm business across life course variations, as for example health care needs and health care use patterns may exhibit important demographic differentiations across the life course (Becot and Inwood, 2022). These demographic determinants could be age, gender, education, socio-economic and legal status, etc. However, according to Shortland and authors (2022), there is a dearth of studies on the organisations and individuals that support farmers through difficult times. Social protection has been initially defined as 'public interventions to assist individuals, households and communities better manage risk and provide support to the critically poor' (Holzmann and Jorgenson, 2000: 3). While earlier conceptualisations of social protection focussed on providing the most vulnerable members of the society with safety nets, the current literature points to the fact that social protection policies and interventions include much more than solely welfare support (Dorward et al., 2006).

In this perspective, the mix and interaction of informal and formal protection mechanisms is important, as studies conducted particularly in the Global South, have addressed the inadequacies of formal social protection programmes due to limited financial resources and weak organisational and technical capabilities in these countries. Thus, studies have focussed on the increasing role of informal networks, such as the extended family and kinship or non-kin networks and other organisations (in Mumtaz, 2023), and are increasingly recognising the diversity of welfare providers. In addition to the state, market and

family, Wood and Gough (2004) have broadened the concept of the welfare mix in developing and less developed countries to include other actors within the community (e.g. non-governmental and religious organisations, kinship and non-kinship relations, landowners, etc.) as providers of informal benefits. According to Langer and Højlund (2011), we can also apply such a concept of social protection to more 'traditional' welfare states (e.g. countries of the Western/Southern Europe, USA, Canada and Australia) and to former socialist countries.

Various social safety net programmes have therefore sought to meet the basic needs of farmers and farm households. They can be provided by actors in the public, private and non-profit sectors to support individuals and households during planned and unplanned life course events such as childbirth, maternity, retirement, unemployment, poverty, retirement, unemployment, illness, accidents and deaths through the provision of cash and/or in-kind benefits (e.g. goods and services) (Becot and Inwood, 2020). Comprehensive social protection systems include social assistance and social insurance programmes. The former are primarily tax-based and refer to establishing basic guarantees for all people, such as a basic level of income security (for example, social pensions and child benefits) and access to essential health care. The latter provide basic protection to individuals in the case of income loss and contributions from workers and/or employers finance them. They can also contribute to a decent work agenda by encouraging formalization of employment, which is particularly important for rural areas that generally have high levels of informality and informal work (United Nations, 2021). While scholars have examined supports for social safety net programmes for farm households, such as those in the area of health insurance, household income support and retirement, they less often considered the question how social policies may also intersect with farm households (Becot and Inwood, 2022). Understanding barriers to accessing social protection, even when programmes and schemes are available, is thus crucial to achieve increased social protection coverage in rural environments (United Nations, 2021).

Based on the above observations, the author of the chapter argues that for farmers and farmworkers alike, the sources of health and safety risks in agriculture can be tied to the use of formal and informal social protection mechanisms. We can observe these through analysing different levels of access to such services (for instance, geographical/spatial, legal, structural, cultural, etc.). On this basis, the author identifies structural issues and discrimination as well as cultural and language issues as the main obstacles in accessing formal and informal social protection for farmers and farmworkers. Additionally, the aim of the review is to identify particularly vulnerable groups in farming in terms of access to social protection mechanisms and to compare the levels of social protection of farmers and farmworkers to other occupational groups. Therefore, the main questions for the literature review have been organised into three general questions using the PICO approach:

1. What is the level of social protection among farmers and farmworkers compared to other occupational groups and which groups are particularly vulnerable in agriculture in terms of access to social protection measures?
2. What are the main barriers to accessing social protection for farmers and farmworkers?
3. How does social protection or the lack thereof affect the health and safety at work and quality of life of farmers and farmworkers?

The first and second research questions are topic specific and have been organised into four main sub-topics:

- Formal social protection and access to formal social protection;
- Informal social protection;
- Discrimination and structural issues;
- Cultural and language issues.

The third research question relates to the crosscutting issue of health and safety at work that we focussed on in all four analysed thematic areas in this report. We conducted thematic analyses to discuss the main issues identified through the screening steps.

After completing the first two steps of a systematic literature review (see methodological overview in the introduction), three researchers reviewed 603 titles and abstracts in the third step using the initial Topic 3 questions. If two reviewers selected the same article for review, it was accepted for further review. This review resulted in 165 articles, which were included in the next analysis step. In the fourth step, the articles were screened using additional inclusion and exclusion criteria. That could mean that no empirical research was conducted or the country where the research was conducted is not relevant to the study - countries in Europe, USA, Canada and Australia were included. It could also be that there is no relevant target group - farmers, farmworkers and/or professionals/ and stakeholders who work or are in contact with them - and/or none of the research questions were addressed. If an article met one of the exclusion criteria, we did not select it for review. After this step, 31 articles were selected for the fifth, final literature review (see Figure 1). A list of selected articles can be found in Table 3 in Appendix 4, which also contains a detailed analysis and overview of the studies on this topic.

MAIN FINDINGS

1. Results of the analyses – Social protection of farmers and farmworkers 1.1. Formal social protection and access to formal social protection

In the analysed articles, the use of health care services was among the most frequently described measures of formal social protection. Gaps and barriers in the delivery of health care and social services (e.g. cost, time, communication issues, lack of transport, existence of and coverage by insurance schemes, employer practices, occupational and safety hazards), are usually addressed in qualitative studies, and health services uptake rates are frequently used in more quantitatively based studies as a quantitative measure of formal social protection. In this respect, studies focus on either local or migrant workers, and only a few studies compare social protection between migrant and non-migrant workers or between different occupational groups (e.g. workers in agriculture versus workers in other sectors).

The use of health care services is sometimes described in quantitative terms as health services uptake rates and/or the non-existence of health and social insurance and subsequently compared by different socio-economic and demographic variables. When the studies use qualitative methods, they usually discuss barriers and gaps in the delivery of social and health services. Some studies compare the health services uptake between workers in agriculture and workers in other sectors. For example, a study of essential infrastructure workers in 31 US states showed that workers in farming, fishing and forestry had the highest prevalence of not having health insurance. They also had significantly higher prevalence of positive answers on two other items: 'does not have a personal health care provider' and 'does not visit a doctor in past year for routine check-up' [100]. Similarly, a study in Sweden [479] found that workers in agriculture, forestry and fishing were two to three times more likely to receive a disability pension than those in the administration and management sector.

Other studies examined health care utilisation only in agriculture. For instance, a study on healthcare use among farmworkers in California ([278]) found that nearly half of farmworkers sought healthcare during the previous two years. Those that did so more often were significantly older, female, married, non-Hispanic and US born. Among migrant workers, those that had been in the USA for more than two years were more likely to use healthcare. The study also found other predictors of increased healthcare use: those that had more than six years of education, spoke and read English somewhat well, earned 15.000 USD, were insured, authorised, non-migrant and used the car for work transportation, were more likely to use health care services. Coverage type in this study was not significantly associated with health care use. Among the barriers, respondents cited cost (90.6%), and significantly smaller percentages cited language (8.5%), providers not understanding their problems (5.2%), feeling unwelcome by the providers (4%) and not knowing where to go for healthcare (2.5%). Cost was also mentioned in another study of Mexican American farmworkers ([293]), as well as inappropriate working hours of services, as workers are unable to take time off work. Results of a study comparing resident and migrant farmworkers in Turkey are also illustrative ([426]). Of the resident farmworkers, 20.5% were not covered by any social security scheme while this percentage was 35.1% in migrant seasonal farmworkers. Another study in

Turkey ([432]) only analysed migrant farmworkers and found that one fourth of participants had no security coverage. Among the reported reasons lack of money, too much workload, remoteness, spontaneous healing and the lack of formal protection, especially for injuries at work, were cited. Studies have also found that employers often, especially in the case of migrant workers, prevent workers from the use of some formal protection measures, for instance, paid sick leave, and cases of presenteeism – workers being present at their workplaces despite illnesses and injuries – often occur ([11]). Rarer were studies that examined 'alternative' forms of social protection, such as for example, being treated by complimentary health care providers. A study among Mexican farmworkers in North Carolina found that 63% were treated by a conventional provider (physician, physician assistant, nurse practitioner), and one-in five were treated by a traditional healer ([45]).

Studies also found problematic practices of employers in terms of accessing formal protection measures. A study of migrant farmworkers in Canada reported the reluctance of some employers to report workplace injuries to the workers' compensation agency. The study discovered that health professionals were also doing this - workers sometimes had to pay out of their pockets and then apply for reimbursement ([140]). Similar practices were observed in another Canadian study on migrant farmworkers ([164]). Only three injuries out of 28 reported were reported to the WorkSafeBC (the British Columbia Workers' Compensation Board), 26 to supervisors, 16 went to hospital, and 6 informed consular officers. 32.4% disagreed or strongly disagreed there were enough supports available to them to assert their rights, 15% reported receiving services from a support group, and only 4% agreed or strongly agreed they would be able to get the help they needed if serious problems arose. The study also reported a lack of transportation and instances of employers (bosses, supervisors) translating for workers in medical environments, which can also influence access for migrant farmworkers. A similar study in Turkey among female farmworkers found that employers often evade regulations about safety and health. A study on Mexican-born farmworkers in the USA discovered that workers often did not seek any professional help from health workers or go to a hospital, unless it was very serious. The reason for this is they are not paid if they are not working and in turn, they reported a low uptake of health care services utilization ([258]). This study also found that unauthorised farmworkers are less likely to have health insurance coverage than their authorised counterparts are. In a study of migrant farmworkers in Canada ([269]) less than third made visits to the health provider while in Canada, the majority attributed their problems to work, 93% claimed they did not know how to access workplace safety insurance and only 22% received information on use of the Ontario health care and insurance. Employers were also mediating access to the insurance card for workers.

Material constraints, lack of federal funding and focus of policies and services on the permanent residents are also present ([140]). Migrant farmworkers are a hard to reach population; they are often isolated and have limited access to transportation. There often exists inaction by service providers and other actors, which can cause that migrant farmworkers internalize and normalize barriers to access ([140]). A study of migrant farmworkers in Idaho reported a lack of basic sanitary protection as an emerging issue, which heightened pesticide exposure, workers were sometimes not given notification when pesticide was sprayed and pesticide-handling training sometimes not received ([176]).

Access was not only an obstacle for migrant farmworkers. A study on social supports for farmers that lived with disability in Canada ([223]) proved that limited community or home care services in the rural area exist, but specialist health and therapy services were available in larger cities and there were hidden costs associated with going to these areas. A study of farmworkers in the USA ([279]), reported that 55.8% endorsed no barriers to care, 81.8% got no health care outside US and just over half had used health care in the past 2 years in the US. Women used more health care than men did, unauthorised migrants used less services than other groups of migrants and people with higher English proficiency, used services more often. Conversely, migrants and those that did not own a vehicle, used services to a lesser extent. An ethnographically based study on the social context of migrant health in the USA reported difficult access to services, sometimes without the translator, a lack of funding and poor conditions in migrant clinics without access to state of the art medicines and instruments, frustrated clinicians in the system and virtually non-existent insurance coverage for migrant farmworkers ([283]).

During the COVID-19 pandemics, farmworkers, particularly unauthorised ones ([482]) faced even greater vulnerabilities, as access to social and health services was further restricted ([11], [482]).

In a study in Australia [293], for non-migrant farmers, availability of choice and access, professionals' lack of understanding of farm life, distrust in professionals, the rotation of doctors throughout various regional services, prior experience of themselves or family members, time and money constraints and difficulties in communication were the key barriers to access services.

1.2. Informal social protection

Less articles under review focussed on informal social protection mechanisms. Family members were a group most frequently providing social protection and were seen as crucial in providing such care. Informal social protection was gendered, such as, for example, the distribution of household labour and reconciliation of family and work obligations. Farming culture, such as the value of independence, privacy and self-help was acknowledged as a barrier to help seeking in instances of distress. However, the local community and the local service providers were also perceived as important in providing such support. Most frequently mentioned source of informal social protection were family members ([176], [223], [225], [267], [297], [320]). However, also employers were sometimes those providing social protection. For instance, a study of migrant farmworkers in Canada ([140]) reported that business owners were sometimes assisting workers in translation, accompaniment to a hospital/clinic, in navigating services, mediation conflicts, organizing recreational events and stressed the importance of volunteer contributions.

When discussing informal social protection, some articles acknowledged that it was highly gendered. A study of migrant farmworkers in USA noted gender inequality in the distribution of household labour and the challenges of working in agriculture while raising children and providing childcare. Long working hours in agriculture were a strain especially for single mothers, and with a lack of social networks and limited opportunities for community connections in the somewhat isolated region of Idaho were contributing to decreased social security ([176]). A study of Mexican American farmworkers in USA also emphasised the centrality of family in care, the importance of positive family relationships and reliance on faith in providing emotional support/interpersonal care ([297]).

Also among 'local' farmers, the importance of hands-on support from spouses, children and other family members was emphasised. The study of community support systems for workers that live with disability in Canada ([223]) reported heavy reliance on their spouses for management tasks and caring for the injured farmers. After injury, family roles shifted and this often enabled farmers to continue farming. Obtaining hired help was also important although it was difficult to find skilled help. The study also mentioned the importance of the farming culture in providing informal social protection. The culture of privacy and independence might result in a hesitancy and reluctance to ask for assistance or to admit farmers needed help. Family members were limited in the amount of help they could provide, especially if not living on the farm. The importance of the church, farmwomen, community leaders, and help from local farmers and neighbours as part of the natural exchange in the farm community was also stressed in the study. Similarly, in an Australian study on farmers' perceptions of help-seeking ([293]), the importance of informal help and advice, including facilitating access to professional support, preference for lay support rather than seeking formal/professional support, particularly for mental health services was noted. Again, this was related to values of independence, privacy and self-help. Debriefing with friends was valuable, when they felt unable or willing to talk to their partners and the ability of female partners to provide support in breaking down some of the barriers to seeking help was also noted. Women were key drivers in help seeking, either formally or informally. A study among Norwegian farmwomen reported they were generally not satisfied with the gender division of domestic work, which was true especially for housewives and those working mainly on-farm ([267]). A study in Finland ([320]) also noted the gendered division of labour – women were clearly responsible for domestic work and caretaking work, males either assisted or did not participate at all in this line of work.

In an Irish study that included active farming men, they generally scored high in social support provided by family, friends and significant others grouped together to provide a generic measure of social support ([225]). Effects of social support on mental distress and potential effects of social supports in reducing financial stress were noted.

1.3. Discrimination and structural barriers

This item was particularly pronounced in the studies of migrant farmworkers. Discrimination and structural barriers refer to racism, xenophobia and vulnerability due to migrant/non-citizenship status. The differential treatment of employers based on discriminatory attitudes is often naturalised and normalised.

Findings concern discrimination in working environment and everyday spaces, racism, xenophobia, workers feeling vulnerable with no rights and powerless to resolve their situation, experiences of distrust of professional performance due to migrant/ethnic belonging ([11], [164], [269], [283], [447]). A study among migrant farmworkers in the US ([283]) reported more degrading treatment by supervisors, more physically demanding work and the lower position of migrant workers in work hierarchies. These differences could be influenced by health disparities shaped by racism, naturalization and internalisation of distress. Work and other inequalities have become seen as so normal that they are rarely questioned or challenged, as there are supposedly natural differences among bodies of different ethnicities, in which also farmworkers sometimes take pride.

The studies also exposed fear of conflict within the community ([11], [140]) and also with employers, since workers' problems are often not attributed to employer misconduct or inadequate regulations that are actually not addressing the issues faced by workers ([140], [164]). There is also distrust in authorities, which can conflict with the intention to report violations. To illustrate, in a study of migrant farmworkers in Canada, 69.8% said they would report assault or mistreatment to authorities ([164]).

Insecure legal status was among the important obstacles in accessing different services ([258], [269], [555]) with unauthorised farmworkers less likely to have health insurance coverage than their authorized counter parts.

1.4. Cultural and language barriers

Cultural and language barriers refer to communication, language and translation issues, to the role of stigma and to the importance of culturally appropriate care. This refers not only to migrants that experience various language issues, but also to the non-migrant population. It is related to the culture of privacy and independence that may impede farmers to seek support when in distress.

Most studies that addressed cultural and language barriers focussed on migrant workers ([11], [269], [278], [279], [297]) and reported on their problems with communication and translation issues ([269]), on language as a barrier to the use of health services ([278]), on the higher use of health care when having higher English proficiency ([279]), and on the importance of having to provider look at them when speaking. In this respect, they emphasized the value of culturally appropriate care, the role of stigma in recognising mental health issues and the occurrence of physical complaints as manifestations of mental health issues ([297]). In a Spanish study [11], these barriers were related to difficulties in obtaining a job, barriers between employers and employees, unfair working conditions and differences in employment contracts. In a study on migrant farmworkers in Canada, many times non-verbal communication and rudimentary Spanish was used in communication, language translators were often not considered, even when employers had specific protocols to enable such services. Additionally, professionals sometimes shared info with translators, who were sometimes bosses and supervisors and communication issues were often attributed to cultural differences ([140]). Another related study in Canada [164] reported that 50.3% of workers did not know whom to contact to get help with translation and that employers were translating for them in medical environments.

In a Canadian study of 'local' farmers ([223]), it was noted that the culture of privacy and independence among farmers might result in a hesitancy and reluctance to ask for assistance or to admit they needed help and act as a barrier to returning to farming. An Irish study on dairy farmers found that there existed a macho perception that symptoms constitute evidence of weakness ([225]). A study of barriers to help seeking among farmers in Australia further illuminated the characteristics of the farming culture. There was an emphasis on valuing independence and strength and there existed a perception that farm comes first and farm work is never done. Farmers also generally value privacy and keep problems to themselves (or within their immediate family), especially in relation to those who have experienced mental health difficulties. To illustrate, there exists an internal need to hide emotions and feelings from close family, one needs to be strong, not touch, to maintain a face like a man, possess the ability to take risk. Female partners in the study spoke of male partners as reluctant to seek help, to show weakness and hurt and as normalising pain illness, ignoring health problems and not wishing to complain about health issues.

1.5. Health and safety at work as a crosscutting issue

Health and safety concerns, particularly for migrant farmworkers, occur due to discrimination, precarious and hard working conditions, the lack of enforcement of occupational and safety measures and the lack of legal protections.

Studies have shown that the health problems of migrant workers in agriculture are mainly due to discrimination and racist attitudes, which are the main cause of precarious working conditions, as they have little influence on their working conditions. In this context, variables such as immigration status, economic need to work, gender and ethnicity/nationality play a role ([11], [164], [283]). For example, a study of the situation of migrant farmworkers in Canada ([161]) found that many of them believe that their living and working conditions jeopardise their health. 81.6% received workplace safety training, but 44.7% were unaware of their rights in Canada, and 44.7% disagreed or strongly disagreed that health care providers knew that their health problems could affect their employment. A study of Latino farmworkers in Idaho found that migrant farmworkers often work long hours and express concern about exposure to pesticides and the lack of enforcement of legal protections that are sometimes not afforded to them. For example, 21% were not given water to wash their hands regularly, which increased their exposure to pesticides. In a similar study in the US ([283]), working in extreme weather conditions and exposure to pesticides was also found among migrant workers. A study of migrant workers in Canada ([269]) also found that about half of the workers lacked protective equipment, worked long hours, were exposed to pesticides, and had limited access to clean water. The study also found that workers did not want to take advantage of their paid hours, as there were cases where they were fired or sent back to their countries of origin when they sought treatment. In another study on Mexican workers in the USA ([293]), it was also pointed out that they were unable to take time off work. A similar fact was highlighted in the study on female seasonal farmworkers in Turkey ([250]), who did not seek professional help from medical staff or visit a hospital unless it was a very serious case, as they are not paid during the time they are not working, indicating their lack of social security.

A study of farmers in Australia found that the ability to continue working on the farm despite health problems is most valued and that there is a perception among farmers that work on the farm comes first and is never given up. In this context, studies refer to the development of chronic health conditions because of enduring farm work and the somatization of distress ([283], [373]). As a study on seasonal migrant workers in Turkey has shown ([432]), inadequate working conditions, wages, housing, facilities, nutritional opportunities, health conditions and occupational safety and health conditions have a negative impact on workers' quality of life, their use of health services and their health and safety at work

In the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, a study on migrant farmworkers in Spain reported unfavourable working conditions, manipulation of pay, dismissal due to COVID-19 or care of children with COVID-19 ([482]). At the labour level, the study found a lack of compliance with the collective

agreement in the agricultural sector and the safety measures adopted by the government against COVID-19, which was particularly pronounced among undocumented migrants.

2. Recommendations, good practices and future research

Studies recognise the right to good health, regardless of migration status and stress the importance of comprehensive and sustained efforts in this area. They acknowledge the existence and use of different forms of knowledge about health. They highlight the role of different social support organisations and the need for collaboration between them in providing culturally appropriate services. Mobile clinics to reach farmers and farmworkers on site could be established and the importance of peer-support among farmers and farmworkers is recognised. Transnational cooperation between the countries of origin and host countries in providing health and other forms of social security is also important. Interventions in this area should target micro-, meso- and macro levels.

The authors of the studies generally present the measures and recommendations in the Discussion/Conclusion sections rather than including them in the Results section. It is generally mentioned that the right to good health is recognised regardless of the legal (migration) status of farmworkers ([11]). Some proposals address the issue of access to social/health protection, such as the need to have a National Health Service health card. [11]. Some articles also highlight the role of social support organisations, NGOs and migrant organisations in ensuring access and providing information on rights, legal assistance, training and available services ([11], [176], [278]).

With regard to migrant workers, studies have also pointed out that the use of social and health services in the countries of origin and host countries (e.g. between the USA and Mexico) is not comparable. They emphasised the importance of health sovereignty – the existence and use of different forms of knowledge about health – and the need to consider medical pluralism in the use of different services related to health and well-being ([45]). Understanding medical pluralism is a prerequisite for supporting autonomy in immigrants' health care practises. This in turn could lead to better education and knowledge about different aspects of health ([45]).

Studies have also emphasised the need for more comprehensive and sustained efforts to ensure the health of farmers and farmworkers ([100], [140], [223]). One of the ideas proposed in this context was university-community partnerships in which one organisation takes the lead in establishing sustainability, and research emphasised the need to improve knowledge about such partnerships ([140], [176]). In addition, there is a need for greater transparency of such programmes, which can also determine service delivery, as there is always a tension between protection and performance in such programmes. There is a need to identify those organisations that are more sensitive to issues faced by migrant farmworkers, for example, and collaboration with service providers is paramount ([140]). One of the key findings of the study on the utilisation of disability benefits among farmers is that health and service providers, the church, and financial institutions all expressed an interest in increasing their knowledge of available support services ([223]). To close the gaps in communication between the different actors, better coordination of treatment, especially between health care providers, is important ([223]). Information services should be non-stigmatising and confidential, and the need for a culturally appropriate approach is emphasised with regard to non-migrant farmworkers [223]. Support should be multi-level and multi-sectoral, address communication gaps and gaps between health and other services and focus on the immediate needs of farmers, their families and/or farmworkers, and policy and community developments should also be targeted in this area ([223], [278]).

One of the examples of good practise is a resource kit for farmers living with a disability in the Manitoba region of Canada, which also needs to be adapted to specific regional characteristics ([223]). For example, a study of migrant and seasonal farmworkers in North Carolina found that librarians could serve as key partners with public health professionals or medical practitioners in providing more training to community health workers and can review the information and turn the content into resources that are comprehensive and accessible to farmworkers.

The importance of peer support – e.g. farmers talking to and helping farmers – is also emphasised in some research ([223], [225]). In addition, the involvement of farmers and farmworkers in the design of various workforce and community development programmes seems important to ensure that strategies are evidence-based ([293], [432]). One of the suggestions in this regard relates to the establishment of a nationwide database to register migrant workers and their families. Information on injury and illness rates could also be helpful in the design of interventions ([320]).

One of the studies looking at the situation of migrant workers in Canadian agriculture has highlighted the fact that governments have been slow to respond to the increasing number of migrant workers in agriculture and have focused their efforts primarily at the local level. An example of this is the establishment of migrant clinics where services are provided at times convenient to migrants, such as the establishment of weekend clinics, in some cases including translation services ([269]), the establishment of mobile clinics, and improved transportation ([279], [432]). Nevertheless, the need for a more comprehensive approach and systems of care has been pointed out, in particular the need to consider the situation and use of health services in the countries of origin. One of the solutions proposed in this context could be the establishment of a transnational task force that could address the importance and characteristics of the different stages of the migration process ([269]). Limited language-tailored services in rural areas may have less impact on access to care than on its quality [279]. The need to target different migrant groups, e.g. those of lower socioeconomic status, undocumented migrants, those living in underserved areas and new arrivals, has also been highlighted ([278]). In terms of services provided, it is also important to convey compassion and sensitivity to farmworkers ([278]). Professionals who understand the needs of farm labour practises and routines are also valued and can facilitate access to health and social services for farmworkers [293].

Some suggestions specifically addressed the area of mental health ([297]). For example, patients should be informed about mental health resources, informational talks should be offered in the community to combat stigma, and support groups and other group activities should be given. One suggestion also related to asking patients/service users what is happening in their families and expanding health promotion efforts to include mental health issues and outreach and health promotion activities ([297]).

With regard to the recruitment of rural workers, a study in Turkey ([250]) called for the establishment of labour offices to better match labour demand and supply, which would also meet national and ILO (International Labour Organisation) requirements. One of the proposals is the establishment of a wage compensation commission, where it would be beneficial for employers if employees were compensated for additional hours worked. A study on migrant health in the US ([283]) called for more equitable employment services – e.g. not linking permission to reside in the US to an employment contract - and another for a restructuring of the immigration system that accepts applications for permanent residence and provides migrants with unattached, sectoral work authorization to enable their mobility ([457]). Policies are needed that improve the employment conditions of migrant farmworkers and their housing conditions, including their right to health, and comply with labour and safety standards ([482]).

Some research has also looked at the impact of COVID-19 on the health of (especially migrant) farmworkers ([100]). In some cases, there was no paid sick leave, in others workers had access to temporary sick leave and free testing, but in general, as also highlighted in studies not related to COVID-19, there was a lack of a comprehensive health care approach to the care and treatment of COVID-19 and other new or pre-existing health conditions. As a result, health and other vulnerabilities were elevated, and it seems critical to address these barriers to health insurance coverage ([100]). Furthermore, relying solely on employers to provide adequate occupational health and safety standards does not appear to be the best practice and active oversight and monitoring of health and safety standards in agriculture may be needed ([164]), as there are still problematic issues in auditing these practises ([426]). Workers providing the services need to be trained in environmental health and safety at work ([432]).

In terms of recommendations on the gendered dynamics of agricultural work and family life, research has emphasised the need to provide gender-specific services ([176], [223]) and to consider the dynamics of work and family, childcare responsibilities, and other gendered aspects of agricultural life. This includes, for example, food provision, one of the aspects that differs significantly from other tasks traditionally attributed to the farming population ([176]). However, the study on health care utilisation by migrant farmworkers in California also pointed to the need for programmes targeting men in particular to increase the use of health services ([278]), and health-promoting interventions could target occupations that use health services more frequently and are associated with high occupational risks ([474]).

Some articles also called for meso- and macro-level interventions ([223]), strategic planning and targeting ([444]), especially with regard to the expansion of public health care ([278], [447]) and reorganisation of primary health care services based on the needs of the population. In this context, a comprehensive study on migrant health in the USA ([283]) called for the training of health care providers to consider the role of economic, political and global structures that influence people's health, rather than using a decontextualized approach to health. The social determinants of health approach were proposed instead of the prevailing behavioural model of health. In turn, medical education could better address these multifaceted aspects of disease.

Future research directions

When analysing migrant farmworkers, different intersectional factors (e.g. legal status, nationality) should be addressed in research endeavours and an integrated and global perspective of migration should be considered. Up-to-date and valid measures of health outcomes, illness rates and other areas of social protection should be developed and studies should be conducted with a collaboration of farmers, farmworkers and other stakeholders with researchers in multi-level partnerships.

In relation to research on migrant farmworkers, particular attention should be paid to exploring vulnerabilities related to legal status and nationality (which implicitly requires intersectionality) in order to examine different risk perceptions and experiences in relation to health and to take an integrated and global perspective of immigration, not only in the receiving country but in all countries and institutions concerned ([11]). Research on the social determinants of health and their contextualization must consider the international context of migration and not only local and national dimensions, as well as the impact of racism and anti-immigrant prejudice on the development and maintenance of health disparities ([283]). From a public policy perspective, addressing the risks posed by the current pandemic and future threats to the health security of migrant farmworkers requires that studies address the structural conditions that deprive them of full protection [555].

Questions about medical pluralism and autonomy in health care need to be included in research and noted in patients' medical records, and health care providers need to be familiar with these practices so that they can also give advice and better integrate their knowledge ([45]). The need for partnerships between academic communities with one organization taking the lead to achieve sustainability has been emphasized ([140]). More up-to-date and valid measures of health that are used consistently over time are needed, as well as multilevel analyses that link policies and the experiences of migrant farmworkers to their health outcomes ([164]). More information on injury and illness rates needs to be provided and individual differences in insurance behaviour addressed ([320]). In this context, studies using qualitative data to develop a validated survey that can quantitatively measure and monitor social and community support for farmers could also be useful ([223]), and one study concluded that more representative samples should be used ([280]). As it is not always possible to identify a single risk factor for health problems ([264]), research into the work-relatedness of injuries is important. One study also suggested using focus groups as a tool to invite migrant farmworkers to collaborate with community health providers to identify their needs and possible concrete solutions for their community ([447]).

Further studies addressing the deficiencies in monitoring and testing should be conducted in collaboration with all stakeholders such as farmworkers, occupational health and safety professionals,

local authorities and the government ([426]). In addition, the need for further studies on working hours and exposure in different tasks, as well as injuries and illnesses in the same work tasks, was pointed out ([320]). Regarding the gender dimension, gender differences, particularly the social division of labour between the sexes, need further investigation ([11]), and one article addresses the challenges of involving young men in research ([293]).

DRIVERS OF CHANGE AND MEGA-TRENDS

Neoliberalism, Globalisation, Labour Shortages, and Migration

Among the most frequently mentioned changes in contemporary agriculture is the increase of the need for farmworkers, particularly migrants, which causes a growth in immigration in different countries. With regard to COVID-19, there is some mention of increased vulnerabilities of farmworkers as essential workers during the pandemic. An increased number of women in agriculture is mentioned and the ageing of the population as a general demographic trend is discussed. Another group of articles mention structural changes, such as the changes in health care provision in welfare states, effect of the abolition of quotas, the impact of mechanization, corporatization of agriculture and the deregulation of international free markets on farmers and farmworkers.

Less than half of the articles analysed deal with the social changes affecting contemporary agriculture, most of them in the introductory and/or concluding sections. Some articles mention the accelerated growth of immigration ([11]) and the resulting increase in the number of migrant workers in agriculture ([164], [269], [457]), especially in the context of COVID-19, which puts more focus on the vulnerability of workers [164]. Some articles mention the increase in the number of women in agriculture ([176]) and their increasing participation in non-farm activities ([267]). One article mentions changes in health care systems: shortened hospital stays for acute illnesses and injuries under the U.S. health care system place a greater burden on caregivers and farmworker families. Hidden costs occur when resources are limited and access is difficult or unattainable; these are perceived barriers to continued farming ([223]).

A few articles address structural change in contemporary agriculture. One discusses the impact of the abolition of the milk quota system in 2015 on the financial stability of farmers. It describes the trend towards mechanisation and more investment in infrastructure, which means that farmers spend more time on individual work, which can increase stress and reduce social support. In addition, farmers have to make significant financial investments to run their farms and such negative spirals can lead to farmers losing their farms and livelihoods [225]. Two articles mention the increasing tendency to downsize and split farms ([250], [320]). An article on the health of migrant farmworkers ([283]) discusses the effects of the corporatization of US agriculture and the deregulation of international free markets, perceived as structural violence exerted by the rule of the market and then channelled through international and national racism, classism, sexism, and anti-illegal immigrant sentiments. In this sense, increasingly exploitative economic relations are the main cause of poor health, and future deregulation of international and national trade can be expected in agriculture.

One article ([264]) also mentions the fact that work for self-employed farmers is changing from physically demanding to mentally demanding, with implications for the ageing population of self-employed farmers whose children are less willing to take over the farm. However, it is also acknowledged that the continuing burden of work-related disease also affects the general population, not just migrant workers [279].

CONCLUSIONS

This chapter highlights the importance of social protection for farmers and farmworkers. While social protection in agriculture has often been examined as a factor of agricultural development, particularly in less developed and developing countries or has been examined from the narrow perspective of social insurance for farmers, we have chosen to include in our review a wider conceptualisation of social protection encompassing both formal and informal social protection providers. Research in safety and

health in agriculture has often neglected the wider socio-political, socio-cultural and structural issues that could affect the social security of farmers and farmworkers. With the proposed research questions and the topics under scrutiny, we have managed to obtain a broader overview of health and safety risks of farmers and farmworkers that could impede access to social protection. Structural obstacles, discrimination and cultural and language issues have been identified as crucial obstacles in accessing social protection for farmers and farmworkers. Based on the findings, we have paid special attention to the expected futures of farming and farm work and their interaction with the issues of health and safety of work.

The review has confirmed that a further increase in immigration and the associated increase in the number of migrant workers in agriculture as one of the essential economic sectors can be expected. In this regard, the COVID-19 pandemic has led to a reassessment about whose work is perceived as essential, and governments and the public have recognised the importance of maintaining reliable food supplies during global health crises (Neef, 2020; Shortland et al., 2022). However, our review is in line with other research that has shown the specific vulnerabilities of workers in the agriculture sector (Neef, 2020; Becot et al., 2020). As Neef (2020) argues, the flexibility of governments to enable temporary migrants their essential work during the pandemic, did not result in improved recognition of their human rights to social protection, decent wages and safe working conditions. Also for farmers, stress, anxiety and suicidal ideation because of loss of social contact were exacerbated during the COVID-19 pandemic (Shortland et al., 2022).

With the expected further disintegration of public health care systems and welfare states at national levels that we noted in the review, the burden on caregivers in farming families will most likely increase further pointing to the increasing importance of informal social protection mechanisms. We can also argue that the traditional dichotomies - state vs. market, public vs. private transfers – cannot capture the diversity and complexity of relationships between formal and informal social protection actors (Devereux, 2001). In this respect, the review showed that the issue of access to social and health services is particularly acute. In this manner, incorporating the role of the historical and contemporary discriminatory practices affecting access to various programmes is essential to better understand farm and household trajectories (Becot and Inwood, 2022). Access concerns not only the spatial availability of certain services (e.g. the absence or lack of such services in rural, especially remote areas, the lack of adequate transportation), but also the legal and administrative provisions that condition access to services. These could refer to a lack or presence of health insurance coverage for farmers and farmworkers, to the dependence of insurance on nationality and legal status, as well as to cultural and linguistic barriers to accessing services. The latter refers not only to migrant workers, for whom culturally mismatched services are among the most important reasons for not accessing health and social services. It is also applicable to 'local' farmers, for whom cultural views on farming, such as the culture of independence and strength, placing farm work above all else and stating that farm work is never done, can hinder timely access to health and social services. Increasing digitalization and mechanization in agriculture can also mean that there is less informal social support and protection, which in turn increases stress among farmers and farmworkers. When referring to insurance use and insurance status for particular groups of individuals, the review has confirmed that the source of health insurance and type of coverage shape individual's access to health care (see also Becot and Inwood, 2022). However, we seem to be lacking a more nuanced understanding of the variations in farm households' health insurance arrangements and the lived experiences of farmers across the life course and how household level challenges related to health and health expenses interact with farm development and transition trajectories across the life course (Becot and Inwood, 2022). A question not addressed in our review is the increased reliance on digital services in improving the social protection services. There is still a digital divide and poor rural Internet connectivity in some areas that means these services are not available to all (United Nations, 2021, Shortland et al., 2022). Additionally, in our review, there is less focus on topics such as social insurance systems for farmers and farmworkers and on specific topics such as childcare, social insurance for farmers, reconciliation of work and family and other social benefits for farmers and farmworkers. This could be the consequence of the initial choice of search

words and search strings that was unified for all four analysed topics in this report, and has yielded a specific set of results on the topic of social protection.

The corporatization of agriculture, the future deregulation of markets and the decline in the number of small farms may also have a negative impact on the social security of farmers and farmworkers. Additional stressors for migrant workers include their often-uncertain legal status, citizenship and ethnic discrimination, with undocumented migrant workers at even greater risk. In this regard, existing social protection frameworks could also be expanded to reach groups that are currently excluded from social protection, such as informal workers (United Nations, 2021). Furthermore, extending these frameworks could also make it easier for people in rural areas to switch between agriculture and other sectors of the economy without losing access to benefits (United Nations, 2021). In addition, research in our review has generally not examined the provision of social security across countries, particularly in the countries of origin of farmworkers. Farmers with disabilities are also among the more vulnerable groups in agriculture. For women, the gender-specific double burden of farm work and family responsibilities can be a particular stress factor. However, some studies in this review have also found that men make little use of social and health services and that it is difficult to include them in various programmes for farmers and/or farmworkers.

In view of multi-layered vulnerabilities of farmers and farmworkers, multidisciplinary and integrated efforts to improve health and social welfare were emphasized in the reviewed research. As Langer and Højlund (2011) argue, welfare is indeed a set of shifting and diverse practices at individual, community and organisational level, which can also become the embodiment of particular forms of ethical orientations and normative expectations. Suggestions for policy and research could include working with community health services and other service providers to identify the needs of farmers and farmworkers and possible concrete solutions for their communities. Different forms of knowledge about health and social services should also be considered as a prerequisite for supporting autonomy in different health and social service practices. Peer support – farmers supporting farmers and/or farmworkers supporting farmworkers – could also help to improve the informal and formal social protection of farmers and farmworkers.

The social vulnerability of farmers and farmworkers is therefore complex and depends on a variety of factors that intersect. Local, national and global contexts and changes of contemporary agriculture that contribute to inequalities in health and social security should be addressed. Consequently, not only legitimate government bodies shape social policy at the local, national and international levels, but also the role of agencies such as the World Bank, regional banks, the International Monetary Fund, the European Union and large multinational corporations is becoming increasingly important (Okongwu and Mencher, 2000). This is in line with the increased corporatisation of agriculture emphasised also in the literature review and could be expected as a future trend. As stated in one of the articles in the literature review, analysing the role of economic, political and global structures that influence people's health, rather than using a decontextualized approach to health, is crucial. There exists, as Rodrik (in Okongwu and Mencher, 2000: 112) has stated 'a linkage between globalisation, international trade, social insurance, national safety nets, and changing patterns of labour force incorporation.' In view of the future trends in farming, Becot and Inwood (2022) argue that due to the neoliberal policies reflecting welfare state retrenchment and austerity measures that create new policy environments within which welfare states operate in, it is especially important to research the links between formal social safety nets and farm persistence. Therefore, we could propose a wider social determinants of health approach instead of the prevailing simplistic behavioural model of health. A wider contextual model has been less often applied in health and safety at work research, but could yield valuable and complex insights into the development, use and mutual interaction between formal and informal social protection mechanisms.

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CHAPTER 4: IMPACT OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN AGRICULTURE ON THE SAFETY, HEALTH AND WELL-BEING OF FARMERS AND FARMWORKERS

STARTING POINTS

As emphasised in various policy and expert documents (e.g. Bock et al., 2020; European Commission, 2022; European Environment Agency 2019; European Union, 2020a, 2020b), agriculture in Europe is facing a number of changes and challenges. The climate in particular is changing due to environmental pollution and greenhouse gas emissions. The increasing frequency and intensity of extreme weather events is affecting agricultural production, crop yields, livestock health and infrastructure, leading to increased economic losses. At the same time, intensive farming practises, monocultures, excessive use of chemicals and land use change have led to a loss of biodiversity, soil degradation and reduced water quality and availability. Agricultural markets in Europe are increasingly volatile due to factors such as disruptions in global supply chains, commodity price volatility, trade disputes and geopolitical tensions. In addition, the agricultural population in Europe is ageing, while the participation of young people is decreasing, which has an impact on the labour force. Furthermore, consumer demand for sufficient quantities of healthy and high-quality food is increasing. In the face of all these challenges, to name but a few, the technological change in agriculture that has taken place worldwide over the last fifteen years is expected to contribute to a sustainable food supply for the growing demand of the population, while ensuring the protection of the environment, responsible use of natural resources and more productive and economical production (De Clercq et al.; 2018, European Union, 2017, 2022a, 2022b; Lieve 2016). At the same time, experts, policy makers and some groups of farmers expect that the introduction of new technologies in agriculture will provide a solution to the current acute labour shortage in agriculture and improve the safety, health and well-being of farmers and farmworkers, which in turn will contribute to the attractiveness of the farming profession (EU-OSHA, 2021, 2022).

Against this background, efforts to promote the development of new/modern technologies, which denote several emerging concepts to express different forms of digitalisation in agriculture, such as digital farming, smart farming, advanced farming, Agriculture 4.0, precision farming and their introduction into agricultural practise, seem necessary and justified. In this context, technology researchers and experts, manufacturers and commercial companies are making great efforts to develop and introduce the new products/devices/solutions as quickly as possible and to equip farmers with them (e.g. StartUs, 2024; Zion Market Research, 2024; Global Market Insights, 2024). Public support in this area is considerable. For example, the European Commission has allocated more than 200 million euros for research and innovation (R&I) for the use of digital technologies in the agricultural sector as part of the Horizon 2020 programme (European Commission, 2023). In parallel with this momentum, research and scientific knowledge about the developments and challenges in the application of these new technologies are increasing. The main focus is on identifying and recognising the latest technological trends in the development of specific new tools and devices and testing their functionality and potential applications. Recently, however, the incentives and barriers to the adoption and utilisation of these new technologies by farmers and farmworkers have also come under the spotlight. In this context, the advantages and disadvantages of using new technologies are analysed, e.g. their impact on the work and life of farmers and farm workers, on their productivity and income, their working conditions and well-being. Some recent studies are critical of the impact of the introduction of modern technologies in agriculture so far and are cautious about the enthusiasm for the rapid and smooth introduction of new technological solutions/equipment/tools and their ability to solve the pressing problems of today's agriculture. In this context, we are particularly interested in the impact of this modern technology on the safety, health and well-being of farmers and farmworkers and what evidence already exists in the scientific literature on this topic. This is the content of section 2, which is an analysis of our literature review. Here, however, we begin with a description of the state of the art in modern technology in agriculture and a brief overview of the existing literature on the social aspects of this technology.

A brief overview of the literature on the technical aspects of the development of digital farming

As the recent literature reviews (Cisternas et al., 2020; Khan et al., 2021; Koutsos & Menexes 2017; Mizik 2023; Monteiro et al., 2021) on digital farming show, the ongoing technological developments, the emerging functional problems in the operation and safety of the devices, the search for solutions and their wide application are at the centre of interest of research activities in this field. The development of new technologies in agriculture includes the construction of equipment and tools for both cropping and livestock farming. The literature review by Khan et al. (2021) provides a listing and description of an already wide range of 'modern' machines, tools and equipment that are available, but an even more extensive list of those that have the potential to be used for the production of a variety of crops, vegetables and fruit. The list includes devices such as agricultural machinery and equipment supported by GIS (Geographic Information Systems) and GPS (Global Positioning Systems) / GNSS (Global Navigation Satellite Systems); ground-based and remote sensing applications with multi-purpose devices such as drones, aeroplanes and satellites; the Internet of Things (IoT) and smartphone sensors, image sensors, wireless sensors and accelerometers; tractors with automatic, self-propelled drive and others. They all rely on the latest scientific developments and technical solutions in the field of various information and communication technologies. The latest scientific advances and technical principles, e.g. the application of various mathematical and computational algorithms integrated into e.g. wireless sensor networks (WSN), GPS and the Internet of Things (IoT), cloud computing, artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML), are also used to a greater or lesser extent in the development and design of modern animal production technologies (Khan et al., 2021; Monteiro et al., 2021). Many of the tools and devices listed relate to machines, equipment and tools that enable the monitoring of animal behaviour/movement and condition (e.g. health and welfare), live weight monitoring and measurement, feed dosing and the performance of automatic milking.

At the same time, some of the above mentioned authors (Khan et al., 2021) acknowledge that most farmers cannot afford the extensive list of products that this advanced technology offers, while most service providers and manufacturers are operating well below their means and promotional efforts. It is assumed that the use of modern technology in farming is hindered by several reasons. First and foremost is the technical incompleteness of the devices in terms of their functionality and application security, as well as the incompatibility between different devices due to inconsistent digital standards, all of which require further technical refinement, consideration and testing. In addition, there is the cost of hardware, weather variability, the integrity and security of data management, the literacy rates, i.e. education and skills of users, the unavailability of infrastructure such as internet access, mobile networks, including Wi-Fi and base stations (Monteiro et al., 2021; Shafi et al., 2019; Knierim et al., 2022). Overcoming the imbalance between supply and demand and the increased use of modern farming equipment, such as tractors with automatic drivers, requires, for example, the development of cost-effective monitoring equipment and the introduction and amendment of international ISO standards, which is not yet the case.

An exception to this generally relatively low use of modern technology in agricultural practise which certainly varies geographically (McGrath et al., 2023) is the automatic milking system (AMS). This robot, or more specifically a robotic arm, takes over all milk production tasks so that milking can be scheduled on a 24-hour basis and the animals themselves decide when they want to be milked. In fact, this robotic device is already considered a classic application of modern agricultural technology. Since the late 1990s, this system has been used mainly in Western and Northern Europe to reduce the amount of labour on dairy farms, increase production per cow and improve the lifestyle of dairy farming families. In recent years, agricultural robotics has experienced unprecedented development. Many AMS models are now technically ready for use and available on the market (Martin et al., 2022).

Efforts have also been made to make robotic solutions an integral part of "advanced" plant and fruit production, particularly to facilitate labour-intensive operations and avoid exposure to many work-related hazards, such as a variety of chemicals. However, a look at the literature on agricultural robots in cropping systems (Bagagiolo et al., 2022; Vasconez et al., 2019) shows that there are several limitations

that hinder the spread of robotics in this sector, unlike in the case of AMS. The problems or limitations lie in the complexity and diversity of working environments. Indeed, the working mechanisms and conditions can be very different even within the same species and cultivar, so that each plant species requires specific gears. In addition, due to seasonality, they can only be used a few times a year, which contributes to their high cost and limited economic viability. Another disadvantage is their low labour efficiency. This applies in particular to harvesting robots, as recognising, gripping and collecting the fruit requires long processing and handling times. In addition, there are applications in small and medium-sized agricultural fields that are too difficult to be fully automated. The vast majority of robots in crop production are therefore still under development, require further sensors and algorithmic improvements and only exist as prototypes.

To overcome the above problems and promote robotic solutions in this field, a combination of human workers and robots, i.e. 'co-robots', has been suggested (Vasconez et al., 2019). This is indeed an emerging field of research focussing on the study of physical, cognitive and social interaction between humans and robots. However, to date, the development of strategies for human-robot interaction (HRI) has been a challenging problem, mainly due to the complexity of humans (dealing with cognitive factors, perceptions and psychophysical characteristics of operators) and the large number of different interactions that these specific operations represent (Vasconez et al., 2019). Another subtle factor to consider in this strategy is the safety of the HRI (Aby & Issa, 2023). Working in an agricultural environment already carries a significant risk of accidents. The impact of HRI strategies could make an important contribution to improving security. There is an ambition that the robot should be able to supplement or even replace human labour in risky or complex tasks when the operator is unable to perform them correctly. But the impact of robots on accidents is still an issue, as they can perform a range of movements that can be dangerous for humans in the vicinity. So there are dangerous situations where people could be injured when interacting with robots. Safety management standards such as those of the International Organisation for Standardisation (ISO), to which the European regulations refer, could be used in part for this purpose, but there are not yet any standards that focus on resilient automation environments. The path to developing robotics for an efficient and fully autonomous and safe agricultural process is therefore still long, mainly because it is a complex area that requires considerable investment in technical improvements and the upgrading of safety standards (Aby & Issa, 2023; Vasconez et al., 2019; Hayden et al., 2022).

An overview of the existent literature on the social aspects of digital farming

From a technical point of view, the above-mentioned difficulties in developing, testing and implementing the latest technological developments and solutions in the field of agricultural technology seem to be the most important and urgent ones to overcome in the future. However, in order to fully realise the potential of this new technology in practise, a number of obstacles that are not purely technical in nature must also be considered and overcome. In other words, technology is not context-neutral, and this also applies to new technologies in agriculture (Klerkx and Rose, 2020; Rotz et al., 2019). On the one hand, this means that new technologies are driven and are steered by certain interests and directed by the power of particular social actors. On the other hand, they have an impact on the lives and fates of the people who use them or are excluded from their use. It is therefore legitimate and necessary to analyse these new technologies in agriculture not only from a purely technical point of view, but also to understand their potentials and shortcomings from a social perspective. As Carolan (2024) argues, this need is evidenced and confirmed by the growing body of systematic literature reviews on new technologies in agriculture that focus exclusively on the social dimension of these platforms and practises. The key findings and messages of these summaries are outlined below.

From the growing but scattered social science literature on digitalisation in agriculture that has recently emerged, Klerkx et al. (2019) identified five thematic clusters: 1) Adoption, use and adaptation of digital technologies on farm; 2) Impacts of digitalisation on farmers' identity, skills and work; 3) Power, ownership, privacy and ethics in the digitalisation of agricultural production systems and value chains; 4) Digitalisation and agricultural knowledge and innovation systems (AKIS); and 5) Economics and

management of digitalised agricultural production systems and value chains. The last two clusters are still at an early stage, as there is still little empirical research. The first three, which are particularly relevant for the purpose of our study, are briefly summarised below.

Regarding the adoption and use of digital technologies, the existent literature shows that in spite of considerable enthusiasm for digital agriculture there are still many uncertainties about their actual use by farmers. Although some studies show that farmers, especially in dairy and arable farming, are interested and motivated to adopt these technologies, e.g. to reduce workload, to better balance work and private life and, last but not least, to make their farm more profitable and successful, the research (Barnes et al., 2019; Hansen, 2015; Kernecker et al., 2019; cited in Klerkx et al., 2019) shows that the decision to adopt the new technologies is hindered by several reasons. These include the high cost of the initial investment and doubts about its added value and whether it will pay off in the foreseeable future, the inaccessibility of technical support or training and the lack of accessibility of broadband connections and support services for data analysis. The studies also show that the number of users increased with the size of the farm, the high level of human and social capital in the farming community and a well-developed agricultural knowledge system in the region. Socio-cultural norms and a long tradition of close co-operation with the agricultural machinery industry also play a role.

The results of the studies related to farmers' identity, farmers' skills and farm work show that digital technology can have a major impact on the cultural fabric of rural areas by disrupting previous sentiments and institutions of knowledge sharing with kin and the neighbourhood (Janc et al. 2019; cited in Klerkx et al. 2019) and undermining farmer identity by impacting what it means to be a "good" farmer (Burton et al., 2012; Carolan, 2017b; cited in Klerkx et al., 2019). Research has also looked at the impact of digitalisation on the autonomy of farmers. This includes the fear that farmers will become 'data workers', but also that they will be marginalised or discriminated against if they do not have digital skills, which relates in particular to migrant farmworkers (Rotz et al., 2019b; cited in Klerkx et al., 2019). Studies on farm work have focused on the farmer-animal relationship in robotic milking, which raises some ethical concerns and issues (Bear and Holloway, 2019; Driessen and Heutinck, 2015; Bos and Munnichs, 2016; cited in Klerkx et al., 2019).

The core topics of the thematic cluster on power, data ownership, privacy and ethics deal with the questions of how digitalisation changes or reproduces the rules, institutions and power relations that determine these systems, how this affects the various actors and what reactions or resistance arise, and how ethical issues such as privacy, data ownership and data protection, e.g. against cyber-attacks, can be addressed and how to deal with them (Sykuta, 2016; Bronson, 2018; Carbonell, 2016; Carolan, 2017a, 2018a,b,c, 2019; Eastwood et al., 2017a; Fleming et al., 2018; Fraser, 2019a, b; Freidberg, 2019; Rose and Chilvers, 2018; Rotz et al., 2019a; Schuster, 2017; Miles, 2019; Rotz et al., 2019b; cited in Klerkx et al., 2019). In this respect, recent evidence, and in particular historical experience with the introduction of new technologies in agriculture, suggests that digital agricultural technologies will primarily benefit digital companies/corporations rather than farmers, especially smaller and less capital-intensive ones. It is also assumed that digital farming will lead to a bifurcated labour market with high/low skill requirements, where the needs of weaker groups, e.g. migrant farmworkers, will not be taken into account. Last but not least, the articles in this cluster also point to farmers' doubts as to whether the wealth of data and technology being deployed on the farm from the top down is as important and effective as their own knowledge.

The findings of the literature review presented above show that social science research on digital farming can contribute to a comprehensive insight into its current and future impact on farming, farmers and farmworkers. Similarly, the findings of the literature reviews presented below complement the above findings and add some additional insights.

The literature review by McGrath et al. (2023) adds three more clusters to those already identified: 1) work-life balance on the farm; 2) isolation and inclusion; and 3) the public perceptions of digital farming. For the purposes of our study, it is worth emphasising the first two in particular.

Studies on the first cluster suggest that automatic systems can help to reduce the time spent on routine farming tasks and free up more time for other tasks such as housework and other activities, leaving more time for children and family and more leisure time (Butler in Holloway, 2016; Driessen in Heutinck, 2015; Edwards et al., 2015; cited in McGrath et al., 2023). Digital tools can also take over labour-intensive tasks and help to destigmatise farming as “hard work” and make this occupation more attractive to different groups such as women, young people and highly skilled people and enable older and disabled people to continue farming (Barrett in Rose, 2020; Carolan, 2020b; Regan, 2019; Rotz et al., 2019b; Schewe in Stuart, 2015; cited in McGrath et al., 2023). The articles mentioned in this section also discuss how digital technologies in agriculture make it possible to combat labour shortages by shifting the labour pool towards migrant and/or highly skilled workers (Butler in Holloway, 2016; Rotz et al., 2019b; cited in McGrath et al., 2023). It is also hypothesised that technologies can lead to less stressful work, better working conditions and higher job satisfaction, all of which could have a positive impact on well-being (Tse et al., 2018; cited in McGrath et al., 2023). However, other articles in this cluster warn that the introduction of new technologies can have a negative impact in this respect. Farmers are afraid of such technologies due to their lack of knowledge, which leads to technology anxiety (Barrett in Rose, 2020; Pillai in Sivathanu, 2020; cited in McGrath et al., 2023). Higher levels of stress may result from farmers being forced to increase their production to compensate for the high costs and potential debt of acquiring these technologies, and from having to reorganise and adapt their farms to the new systems (Butler in Holloway, 2016; Driessen in Heutinck, 2015; Schewe in Stuart, 2015; cited in McGrath et al., 2023).

As highlighted in the articles in the second cluster, digitalisation can both connect and disconnect farmers. Digital platforms such as social media can provide an inclusive environment, help farmers to expand and develop their social networks, facilitate the exchange of knowledge and information between farmers, and reduce the distance between farmers and policy makers (Bojovic et al., 2015; Funk Kopecky, 2016; Lundström and Lindblom, 2018; cited in McGrath et al., 2023). However, digital tools can have an alienating effect on users, leading to feelings of loneliness (as farming can be seen as a lonely occupation and technology can exacerbate this) and marginalisation among farmers, leading to a potential social divide in communities between the ‘have’ and the ‘have-nots’ (Carolan, 2020d; Carolan 2017b; cited in McGrath et al., 2023).

From a social science and humanities perspective, then, there are several topics related to modern technologies in agriculture, and their number is growing. In particular, the impact of modern technologies on the health and safety of farmers have also been analysed in the literature in recent years. However, the authors of these reviews, which focus on animal husbandry (Hayden et al., 2022; Martin et al., 2022), emphasise that there is still a significant research gap on this topic. As Hayden et al. (2022) note, the articles describing new technologies such as sensors, computer vision, AMS and AI tend to focus on animal welfare as a justification for the introduction of these devices rather than the impact of these devices on the health and safety of farmers and/or farmworkers. Of the 80 articles analysed, only two (Basinas et al., 2017; Böhlandt et al., 2016; cited in Hayden et al., 2022) explicitly addressed the health and safety of farmers using modern technologies. These two studies have shown that the use of modern technologies in livestock farming has a positive impact on workers’ health compared to not using these technologies, e.g. through reduced exposure to dust, endotoxins and cow hair allergens. The remaining 19% of the 80 studies analysed looked at topics such as labour saving and mental load, which can affect farm productivity and also affect workers’ health and well-being. Traditional occupational health and safety stresses or events such as ergonomic effects on musculoskeletal disorders or vibration, noise, heat and cold stress, slips, trips or falls, and cuts or wounds to the farmer and/or farm workers associated with these new technologies were not addressed. Whilst the articles examined the positive and negative impacts of the introduction of new technologies, none of the articles directly assessed the impact on workers well-being, such as fatigue, distress or workers’ mental health associated with the new technologies.

However, in a systematic review by Martin et al. (2022) based on 90 articles dealing with robots and the change in work on dairy farms, several articles (Meskens et al., 2001; Hansen, 2015; Karttunen et al.,

2016; Hostiou et al., 2017b, a; Lunner-Kolstrup et al., 2018; Lundström and Lindblom, 2021; cited in Martin et al., 2022) have been identified that address the topic of mental health, i.e. the mental workload and technostress caused by the use of AMS. Their analysis shows that AMS reduces stress by removing the repetitive task of milking and reducing physical workload, which has a positive impact on lifestyle and time with family, and is expected to reduce mental workload by anticipating events such as insemination or mastitis. However, most of the studies in their pool report an increase in mental workload and stress. Four reasons were given for this: 1) the complexity of managing an AMS and the complexity or information overload; 2) the lack of sufficient knowledge on the part of farmers or hired workers and their dependence on AMS maintenance suppliers; 3) the fact that they are on call 24/7 and have to deal with night alarms; and 4) the debt burden that increases with the investment in the system. The issue of autonomy in its various aspects is therefore crucial for the future of working with AMS. However, as Martin et al. (2022) note, working with AMS is still very under-researched, it is not yet an area of study.

To summarise, most of the existing literature on new, modern technologies in agriculture, i.e. digital agriculture or Agriculture 4.0, primarily emphasises its technical aspects, problems and solutions. At the same time, however, there is a growing body of literature, especially in recent years, that focuses on the social aspects of these technologies, the social drivers for the development and adoption of these technologies and their impact on the lives and fortunes of those who adopt/use or do not adopt/use/have access to them. The topics of the social science literature are diverse, but are mainly concerned with the determinants of adoption/acceptance of modern agricultural technologies, particularly the question of their economic viability and effectiveness. Less attention has been paid to the impact of these technologies on the working conditions, safety, health and well-being of farmers and farmworkers. The latter, and the fact that the uptake of modern agricultural technologies among farmers is still relatively low, at least as far as Europe is concerned, is also reflected in the range and number of articles we have included in our literature review.

Research question

The first step in this review was to define the research question(s). In line with the aim to assess the impact of new, modern technologies in agriculture on the working environment of farmers and farmworkers based on the literature review, the original questions for TOPIC 43, formulated during the workshops in March and April 2023 and at the WP4 brainstorming in October 2023, were restructured during the screening process to this general question:

What is the impact of the use of modern technologies in agriculture on the working environment, safety, health and well-being of farmers and farmworkers?

The PICO (Population, Issue, Comparators and Outcomes) approach is reflected in the research question above, which is used to analyse the selected articles. Accordingly, the variables created to

³ The initial TOPIC 4 research questions were:

- How does technological development in agriculture affect the safety, health, and quality of life of farmers and farm workers, and what impact can be expected in the future?
- Are the new technologies effective and do they reduce the risks in farming and the number of fatalities among farmers?
- How do modern technologies affect/ change the working conditions of farmers/farm workers and make their work easier or more demanding/difficult and consequently affect the (physical and mental) health of farmers/farm workers and the likelihood of occupational accidents?
- Modern technologies can reduce the workload, but on the other hand, they can also change the autonomy, control of work and increase the financial burden (cause financial stress). They can also increase loneliness among farmers. So what are the financial risks and identity issues to farmers in this area?
- How will the new technologies (the existence of new technologies) affect different groups of farmers, e.g. in terms of their financial capabilities/constraints? Who will be left behind, e.g. will small farms be laid off/abandoned?
- Who can farmers rely on, e.g. do farm advisors/other professionals have the necessary knowledge and skills to help farmers adopt new technologies and practices to improve their health and safety?

analyse the selected articles follow a similar presentation structure as in the other three sections of this report.

Screening steps of systematic literature review for TOPIC 4

In the third phase of the search screening, 603 titles and abstracts were reviewed by three researchers using the initial TOPIC 4 questions. All reviewers unanimously selected only 19 identical articles for inclusion. The remaining articles were voted for exception if two reviewers selected the same article for further screening. In the end, 44 articles were deemed suitable for the next step. In a fourth step, the articles were screened against the inclusion/exclusion criteria (no research was conducted; the research is neither quantitative nor qualitative; the country is not relevant to the study; there is no relevant primary target group; none of the initial questions posed in TOPIC 4 are addressed). An article was excluded if it met one or more of the exclusion criteria. Studies that did not directly address the impact of new technologies in agriculture on the (mental) health, safety and quality of life of farmers, as well as studies that did not fulfil the inclusion criteria, were excluded from the full-text review. After the fourth step, only 5 articles were selected for the fifth step - the final analysis of the systematic literature review. After reviewing their reference lists, 6 additional articles were added. These articles are labelled with the base number of the article and the symbol '_' as well as the sub-number of the article (see Appendix 1). A total of 11 articles were selected for the fifth phase, i.e. the final analysis. A list of selected articles can be found in Table 4 in Appendix 5, which also contains a detailed analysis and overview of the studies on this topic (see Figure 1).

MAIN FINDINGS

This part of the literature review looked at the benefits and challenges of new technologies in agriculture in terms of safety, health and well-being from the perspective/experience of their users, i.e. farmers and farmworkers.

The most important finding related to our research question is that the vast majority of farmers ([236_4], [321], [334], [334_1], [321_1], [263], [236_2], [236_1]) stated that **the use of new technology had improved working conditions, job satisfaction, work-related physical and mental health, quality of life and well-being**. Improved animal health was also reported in some studies ([334], [334_1]).

The next important finding related to our research question is that **the automatic milking system (AMS) is by far the most widely represented and discussed technology** in the literature. Although the results of studies on the impact of drones and precision livestock management (PLM) on the working environment, health, safety and quality of life of farmers are promising, we could only find one study each on the impact of this type of specific technology. This suggests that the socio-psychological effects of new technologies on health, quality of life and safety have not yet been sufficiently researched. More than half of the analysed studies ([236_1], [265], [334], [236_2], [236_3], [321_1]) suggest further research in this area.

Another finding worth highlighting is that the majority of farmers ([265], [334], [236_1], [321_1], [236_4], [321], [236_2]) decided to purchase and adopt the new technology mainly for reasons of increasing the economic efficiency of their farms, i.e. to increase productivity, reduce operating costs and reduce labour costs. So this was one of the major **drivers of change**. Future detailed cost-benefit analyses would help to weigh up the short-term costs against the long-term benefits.

Another **driver of change** is the desire to improve working conditions on a farm. Farmers also hoped that new technologies would reduce the repetitive, routine tasks involved in farming and allow them to work more flexibly and have more free time. This was also the case, but it should be noted that some farmers ([321_1], [236_2], [236_1]) had to work just as much as before the introduction of the new technology due to the increased production volume.

However, the results also show a **certain paradox**: the greater flexibility of work went hand in hand with the fact that the work never really ended. Thus, the farmers ([263], [321], [236_2]) were on call around the clock to manage the technology, e.g. by setting the alarm clock at night, etc. However, some of them have adapted to the new technologies, e.g. night alarms, and have made certain adjustments to reduce the frequency of night alarms, e.g. by switching off all alarms that are not emergencies. Some **farmers also reported the stress** associated with maintaining the technology and repairing broken parts ([265], [236_3]), as well as the lack of sufficient knowledge and technical competence ([236_3], [334_1], [321], [265], [263]) on the part of farmers or hired labour and their dependence on maintenance companies.

The studies analysed also showed that new technology provides farmers with information about their animals, which can be positive if farmers are able to handle this data and use it wisely for management purposes. However, some farmers reported **technostress** because they were overwhelmed with information and data related to the new technology ([263], [334_1], [236_2], [321_1]). The stressors most frequently mentioned in the studies were the psychological and cognitive burden of technical overload and thus the technostress caused by the introduction of new technologies, as well as the inability to deal optimally and effectively with the new technologies.

In terms of **best practise and recommendations**, the finding is that **effective training and support** are crucial for a smooth transition to new technologies. The researchers ([334_1], [263], [236_2], [321]) therefore suggest that every farmer working with the new technology should also be offered a course and some form of training to ensure optimal and efficient use and to facilitate the transition. Farmers and farmworkers need to know how to operate machinery and other technologies and how to work with the software and data. One research group ([263]) pointed out that **adequate AMS training and the availability of counselling services are associated with higher well-being in terms of mental health**. In the qualitative study [236_2], some farmers emphasised **the importance of the social network** for the decision to invest in AMS and for their daily work. Strong networks and advisory services reduce individual stress and improve technology management. In this way, they can share their experiences with other farmers and ask if something is not working. Also, in another study [236_1], where it was found that CMS farmers differ from AMS farmers in two variables – feelings of loneliness and health concerns that reduce job satisfaction – the data can be interpreted as follows: AMS farmers are more likely to be in contact with advisors and other farmers, while CMS farmers can manage their dairy farm alone to some extent. They add that farmers who use AMS receive more attention from society: AMS farmers are offered various off-farm activities by both robot suppliers and extension services; in addition, milking robots still have a high profile in the media, local press and television.

Some researchers ([334_1], [265], [334], [321]) emphasise that it is also important **that new technologies are well tested and safe** and that their effectiveness is proven. In this way, the technological modernisation of farms can have an impact on the attractiveness of dairy farming for younger generations.

DRIVERS OF CHANGE AND MEGA-TRENDS

While other chapters identify technological advancement as a large-scale driver of change, this chapter examines what drives this process of technological advancement itself. Therefore, while this list of drivers of change shows that the increasing digitalisation of farming is driven by many factors and demands, many drivers of change mentioned across other chapters are not mentioned in these selected articles. Above all, farmers, the users of modern technology in agriculture, wanted to be innovative in order to further develop their business (also in comparison to others), to improve working conditions and thus their lives outside of work. The main reasons were, unsurprisingly, to increase productivity, address labor shortages and improve the profitability of their farms and products. In particular, the goal of making the working environment in farming safer and less hazardous to health was not recognised as a motivation/driver for adapting new technologies, although the results of the studies examined showed that the introduction of new technologies can improve the safety of farmers and farm workers. The

drivers of change identified by the researchers based on all the data collected can be categorized as follows:

1) *flexible working and more free time* ([236_2], [265], [236_4], [321]).

Farmers sought to achieve a better work-life balance by using technology to reduce the time spent on labor-intensive tasks. This gave them more time for family, leisure activities and socializing, which improved their overall quality of life.

2) *Higher productivity* or other financial reasons ([265], [334], [236_1], [321_1], [236_4], [321], [236_2]).

Farmers tried to achieve a better work-life balance by using technology to reduce the time spent on labor-intensive tasks. This left them more time for family, leisure activities and social contact, which improved their overall quality of life.

3) *Human and social capital/social network* ([236_1]).

The importance of skills, knowledge sharing and community support played an important role in technology adoption. Farmers benefited from strong social networks and collective expertise within their communities, which facilitated the adoption of new technologies.

4) *Labor shortage and lack of skilled labor* ([236_1], [321]).

With less and less (skilled) labor available, farmers turned to technology to maintain their productivity. Automated systems and other innovations helped to overcome the challenges of labor shortages and lack of skilled labor.

5) *Continuous monitoring and stress management* ([263], [321], [236_2], [265], [236_3], [334_1]):

While the new technologies allowed for greater flexibility, they also led to the paradox that the work never seemed to end, as farmers had to be on call 24/7 to manage and monitor these systems. Some farmers adapted by making adjustments, such as disabling unimportant alarms during the night, but the constant need for monitoring still caused stress.

CONCLUSIONS

As our overview of previous literature reviews and our analysis of selected articles shows, **digitalisation in agriculture is not progressing as fast**, at least not as fast as some believe (e.g. due to media and corporate advertising), that its implementation is well advanced and that farmers are already using new technological solutions to a significant extent.

There are several reasons why this process has not yet progressed so far. The first is certainly that there are still no mature and safe solutions available that are suitable for and used in farming. The exceptions are AMS, drones and other technologies that are mainly used in livestock farming. As the literature review in the introduction to topic 4 has shown, **development is not yet complete**, particularly in the areas of arable farming/crop cultivation and fruit growing. Many **technical hurdles still need to be overcome**, in particular the synchronisation and coordination of the behaviour of robots and humans, and suitable **safety standards need to be developed** and implemented to make this technology usable and safe for farming. How quickly these solutions will emerge is uncertain, because they require a holistic approach, the collaboration of interdisciplinary teams, experts from different fields, e.g. agriculture, mechanical engineering, electronics, cognitive science, psychology, sociology, etc., which is not yet common (Baptista 2012; Burch et al 2023; Klerkx and Rose 2020).

There are also reasons that lie on the side of the farm population. As the statistics on the labour force in Europe show, in addition to the decline and shortage of labour, the **age structure of the farming population** is also unfavourable, as the majority (57.6%) of the main actors, i.e. the farm managers (both sexes combined), are at least 55 years old, while only 11.9% of the farm managers (both sexes combined) are young farmers aged up to 40 years (EUROSTAT 2024). Added to this is the problem of their unfavourable **educational structure**. Most farm managers in the EU only have practical experience; in 2020, this was the case for seven in ten (72.3%). Only one in ten (10.2%) farm managers had full agricultural training and the rest (17.5%) had basic agricultural training (EUROSTAT 2024), which is not in line with expectations for the technological development of the sector. On this basis, it is somewhat unrealistic to expect that older and less educated farmers will opt for the latest developments in agricultural technology. Their strategy will probably be to maintain their current way of working and amortise the technology they have already invested in. This seems understandable, as the introduction of new technology requires **significant new financial investment** and a major **reorganisation of farms**, which older farmers are generally neither willing nor able to do. The introduction of new technology therefore requires a generational change and renewal, which of course takes time.

At the same time, it is important to consider and ensure **the expertise and skills** of those on whom farmers usually rely most when introducing innovations into their farming practises. This includes various actors such as “traditional” agricultural advisors, but also peer networks, online business information, farming social media, digital influencers in agriculture, etc. (Rust et al. 2022; Kvam et al. 2022; Madureira et al. 2022). It is therefore important that not only farmers but also other actors in their environment are trained. However, as the results of our selected articles show, such training is not yet generally available, neither specifically for farmers nor for advisors or students at agricultural colleges and universities. Such programmes (e.g. online) are in preparation and are being tested (e.g. the Erasmus+ BOOST project (2024)). So this will be left to individual initiative for a while yet. However, in addition to technical solutions and a lack of expertise, there are probably other obstacles that need to be recognised and addressed before modern technologies can be successfully introduced and used. Further research in this area is therefore required.

Furthermore, there is no clear and unambiguous answer yet to the question of how this technology will impact the future of farming, the nature of work and the safety and health of working conditions in farming, as the evidence, especially empirical evidence on the experiences of farmers and also other relevant actors, is not abundant, although some predictions and concerns, including criticisms, e.g. regarding unequal distribution/access to new technologies, i.e., Agriculture 4.0 platforms, have already been voiced (Barrett and Rose 2022; Carolan 2024, 2023, 2022; Rose and Bhattacharya 2023; Rose and Chilvers 2018). Based on the results of our analysis, we hypothesise that **the impact of modern technologies** on farmers and farmworkers can be **both positive and negative**, bringing either prosperity or distress to farmers and farmworkers. However, what will prevail depends on **complementary elements at different levels**, as technology is not context-neutral (Klerkx and Rose 2020; Rotz et al. 2019), but depends on interacting elements at different levels: e.g. informal and formal networks in farming communities, secured succession, knowledgeable farmers and farm workers as well as trained advisors, etc. as well as on structural positions in the agri-food hierarchy (farmers' power position) that may or may not allow fair payment for farm produce and consequently fair access to new, modern equipment, available affordable credit, adequate access and comprehensive big data protection laws, etc.

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GENERAL CONCLUSIONS

In this final section, the main findings of the literature review are summarised and highlighted, taking into account all four topics.

Drivers of change

This literature review has identified several drivers of change that are impacting and are likely to continue to impact agriculture as a sector, as well as the working conditions, quality of life, safety and health of farmers and farmworkers around the world, including in Europe in the following decades. It should be noted that these drivers of change were not at the centre of the analysis in the selected articles, but were mentioned and discussed in the introductory and concluding paragraphs. As for the key words and topics we considered and discussed, this list is most likely not exhaustive either. The further identification of drivers of change will be taken up and explored in more depth in a SafeHabitus Foresight Study to be finalised in 2025. However, on the basis of our study, it can be stated that in many cases the drivers of change identified here perpetuate and exacerbate the recognised stressors and are likely to fuel the emergence of new stressors:

- Neoliberalism and globalisation in agriculture have put farmers under intense pressure to restructure their farms in the face of increased global competition, rising costs, low prices and declining subsidies. Added to this economic stress with negative consequences for farmers' health and safety are social criticism from the public and consumers (e.g. environmental cost of farming, animal welfare, etc.), debt caused by the demand for constant investment in inputs, the challenges of maintaining traditional lifestyles and balancing work and family life. While we separated these processes as a discreet driver of change, they are also embedded in most others below.
- Technological advances in agriculture is tied to a declining number of people working as farmers in most industrialised countries, and the hope of maintaining food security through higher productivity lies in technological advances such as the digitalisation of agriculture, which is currently still largely in the prototype phase. It is assumed that farmers will be motivated to use this technology not only because of the higher productivity, but also to make their work easier and more flexible, i.e. to have more free time and move closer to the lifestyle of other occupational groups. At the same time, there is a trend towards larger, more market-orientated farms that increasingly using capital-intensive machinery. However, under the current political framework and the conditions of the global food market, which favour fierce competition, only a small number of farmers will benefit from this technology.
- Together, neoliberalism and globalisation along with technological development have contributed to changes in the demographics and social roles within farming communities in most industrialised countries, causing a profound labour shortage and an increased reliance on migration. The number of hired farmworkers has decreased and reliance on family labour, especially women, (who often working off-farm), has increased to maintain financial viability. Despite technological advances, farming conditions remain difficult and farming communities face shrinking social support networks and a decline in services. In addition, the farming population, like other sectors of society, is confronted with the ageing process, which exacerbates the problems mentioned above. These problems discourage the new generations from pursuing a career in farming, which has led to the closure of many family farms. At the same time, larger farms increasingly rely on cheaper migrant labour, and migrant workers face exploitation, discrimination, and harsh working conditions worldwide.
- In Europe, a clear shift towards agricultural diversification and agroecological principles can be observed among young, well-educated farmers who are committed to sustainable and ethical farming methods. However, they face the challenges of a new consumer environment, unfair payment for their e.g. organic produce, complicated regulations and confrontation with the traditional problems of farming life. This can be a difficult process that has a negative impact on their well-being.
- Climate change exacerbates all of these problems by increasing exposure to extreme weather conditions (particular severe droughts), chemicals and new pathogens, posing additional risks to the health and safety of farmworkers and amplifying already challenging working conditions.

Stressors

When analysing the selected articles on Topic 1 “Psychosocial challenges and opportunities in agriculture”, the following stressors/risks were identified that can affect the mental health of farmers and farmworkers:

1. **Economic pressures:** financial instability, family/personal finances, debt, poverty;
2. **Social and community problems:** isolation and loneliness, family dynamics/conflict, adverse childhood experiences, daily life, marital status, education level, housing conditions (number of people per bedroom, perceived safety of self and belongings, presence of a key to front door, presence of storage space in bedroom, privacy in toilet, number of house rule violations), drug and alcohol use, worry about documents, fear of deportation, lack of social support, intentions to leave farming;
3. **Environmental stressors:** unfavourable weather conditions due to climate change (floods, droughts), pesticide exposure;
4. **Occupational or work-related stressors:** workload, job tension, lack of autonomy, long working hours, pressure to perform, lack of labour availability, worker interest, role definition, rigid job requirements, heavy physical work, job description, role definition, personal (worker) relationships at work, pace of work, time pressure, supervisor support, worries about the future;
5. **Health and safety risks:** injuries, chronic illness, pesticide exposure, lack of access to (mental) health services, suicidal behaviour, dementia and cognitive impairment;
6. **Regulatory and policy changes;** involvement of farmers in long-term evaluation programmes and changes in farming practise, e.g. through participation in agri-environmental programmes;
7. **Market dynamics:** global competition, society/consumers’ expectations, conversion to another practice - organic farming.

The analysis of the literature on Topic 2 – “Farming culture, farm safety and farmer well-being” – has revealed the sources of stressors in the farming environment that arise from farming culture, i.e. a set of beliefs, practises and symbols that are learnt and shared among farmers and farmworkers, shaping their worldview, identities and way of life. More specifically, the stressors identified under this theme are rooted in the agrarian values or ethics, the different cultural identities of farmers and farmworkers, e.g. their health beliefs and risk perceptions, hazard perceptions, discriminatory beliefs and behaviours, etc. The analysis of the selected articles has revealed four such sources of health and safety risks in agriculture, which are not clearly delineated from each other, but interlinked:

1. **Gendered identities and relationships:** The reviewed studies on gender as a cultural stressor in agriculture have consistently found that it has an impact on health, wellbeing, and safety. For example, traditional machismo among Latinx migrant farmworkers increased the impact of stressors such as fear of deportation and discrimination on their mental health. On the other hand, expected gender norms and beliefs among female migrant farmworkers lead them to struggle with the balancing agricultural and domestic duties, while being exposed to increased health risks, e.g. from pesticides. Farmers who adhere to rural masculinity norms and beliefs perceived the consequences of climate variability and agricultural restructuring as a personal failure that harms their health. Although they are more open with their family about their health, they often self-medicate and avoid seeking help, while women who support traditional masculinity often neglect their own health and safety, lack adequate training and insurance, and are exposed to greater financial and health risks, contributing to their poorer mental health and desire to leave the industry.
2. **Structural vulnerability and discrimination:** Structural vulnerability, violence and discrimination, identified as cultural stressors, refer both to mechanisms of power and to the reified

cultural constructions of the disadvantaged social groups themselves (e.g. migrants and seasonal or foreign farmworkers) as “others” and “outsiders”. Such representations are supposed to enable and legitimise racist hierarchies in the workplace, the organisation of work and spatial segregation, and serve to naturalise and justify the inequalities faced by farmworkers. Cultural issues have also been identified in the differing interpretations of illness between migrant farmworkers and host country health care providers, often leaving many of the most immediate factors in farm workers’ suffering unrecognised and untreated. The belief that doctors do not understand a farming way of life is shared by both farmers and farmworkers, which increases their mistrust of local health services and leads to self-medication.

3. **Ruptures in the moral economy** (ethics and emotions): This source of stress is related to changing life circumstances and reactions to them. They occur when farmers are confronted with unexpected difficulties in their work environment over which they have no control or power, or when they are unable to reconcile their own ethics of being a good farmer with the new agricultural realities, such as community-supported agriculture or transition to agroecological farming or when experience an ethical injustice and lack of support from the government.

4. **Risk perceptions, safety and health beliefs in agriculture:** The key point in this context is that perceptions of risk, danger and control over the working and living environment in agriculture are neither general nor universal, but culturally constructed, reflecting the cultural (and structural) differences between particular actors, such as migrant farmworkers, farmers or supervisors, extension workers, health service providers or outreach workers. These beliefs include, for example, the normalisation of risk, fatalism, acceptance of the need to deal with pain and illness while farming, mistrust, postponing or ignoring medical treatment, the attitude of farmers towards their workers that they must take care of their own safety risks, etc., all of which are shaped and justified by the values of autonomy, privacy, economic necessity and hard work characteristic of the farming habitus.

In addition, the analysis in Topic 3 revealed the following stress factors that were identified from the perspective of the social (in)security of farmers and (migrant) farmworkers:

1. **Lack of formal social protection**, i.e. the high prevalence of the absence of a social security scheme and health insurance coverage, denying self-employed farmers and farmworkers, especially migrant workers, access to social and health programmes and services;

2. **Low uptake of social protection measures**, i.e. structural factors (employment status (e.g. unregistered work, legal/migration status of farmworkers), language and cultural barriers, discrimination, linked to economic fears and work pressure), culture of farming (farmers/employers often evade health and safety regulations, believe in spontaneous healing), lack of access (remoteness, limited access to transportation, inactivity of service providers);

3. **Lack of informal social protection** (family, friends, community, etc.), the lack of social protection, e.g. in the sense of not asking for help, is linked to the culture of autonomy, privacy, independence, valuing independence and strength that prevails in farming, the sense that the farm comes first and the work on the farm is never done, that farmers value privacy and keep problems to themselves, e.g. in relation to mental health difficulties. In addition, the lack of social protection is also addressed by the unequal distribution of household labour between the genders and the challenge of balancing farming with caring for children and other vulnerable family members. In addition, family members can only help to a limited extent, especially if they do not live on the farm.

The results of the analysis of the articles in Topic 4 further contribute to the list of stressors that farmers face when applying new technologies in agriculture by adding the following sources of stressors:

1. **data/information overload:** The constant influx of data from new technologies such as sensors and monitoring devices can overwhelm farmers, as the mass of information and data must be analysed and interpreted in order to make optimal and efficient decisions;

2. **techno-intrusion**: being 24/7 on-call to manage technology, e.g. through night alarms etc., to respond to alerts or alarms from automated systems, intrudes on personal time and peace of mind. This intrusion into private life can lead to the feeling of being “always on duty”;

3. **the maintenance of technology and the repair of defective parts**: new technologies often require regular maintenance and occasional repairs, making farmers dependent on e companies and their service technicians which can be a major burden, especially if the farmer does not have the technical expertise or resources to carry out repairs in a timely manner;

4. **the additional workload due to increased production**: new technologies allow farms to expand and become more productive, which can result in increased workload because farmers have to manage more animals and crops to justify the investment in new technologies;

5. **the training of animals to familiarise them with the new technology**: new technologies, such as automatic milking systems, require time and patience in this respect;

6. **the lack of sufficient knowledge and technological expertise**: farmers may not have sufficient training or experience with new technologies, leading to feelings of inadequacy and anxiety;

7. **the burden of debt, which increases with investment in the system**: investments in new technologies often require considerable financial outlay, which can lead to increased debt. The pressure to repay the loans and justify the investment through improved productivity can lead to financial stress.

The analysis of the articles relating to all four topics has shown that farmers and farmworkers are exposed to many sources of stress that can affect their safety, health and well-being. In general, their impact depends on their accumulation and on the ability of farmers and farmworkers to control and manage them. It can be assumed that certain sources of stress can be better controlled by farmers and farmworkers than others. Certainly, climate change and extreme weather events are sources of stress that are beyond the control of farmers, as are developments in the global food market and political events such as international conflicts and wars that impact the supply of basic materials (oil, energy, chemicals, etc.), the transport of food and its prices.

Sources of stress related to family relationships, community life and the work environment (e.g. poor communication between the farm head and family members, working alone, not taking time off and holidays, insufficient knowledge of new technologies, etc.) are likely to be more easily controlled and managed by farmers and farmworkers, e.g. with the help of farm extension services, psychosocial counselling, education, training, awareness raising, the provision of services such as farm relief/replacement services and the like. It is therefore likely to be a room for improvement in this area through effective policy making.

The identified cultural sources of stress, such as gender-specific identities, patriarchal patterns of domination and discrimination, deeply rooted norms, attitudes and ethics, and not least the legal framework of social security, are also likely to be those over which individual farmer and farmworker has little or no control. To overcome these sources of stress, well-designed strategies with sufficient resources and services need to be developed, delivered and implemented at different levels of society, involving different actors such as professional associations, municipalities, national governments, international organisations and the Common Agricultural Policy. These efforts must also involve actors from other sectors such as health, social, economic and other sectors to bring about at least incremental change in this area.

Vulnerable Groups

The analysis of Topic 2 highlighted the following vulnerable groups in particular, some of which were also identified in the analyses of the other topics, showing that they are more exposed to risks, stressors and poor physical and mental health:

1. Farm women and female migrant farmworkers, due to the reproduction of patriarchal relations in farming and new responsibilities and roles.
2. Migrants from indigenous communities because of language barriers and racist prejudices; children and young people because they are invisible.
3. Young, highly skilled and educated farmers who have chosen to stay in farming but face unpredictable ethical issues and challenges in a new consumer environment and struggle with the traditional difficulties of farming life that affect their decisions and wellbeing.
4. Migrant workers in agriculture of both genders due to discrimination, poor working and living conditions and all children due to the social normalisation of their work and agricultural exceptionalism related to safety regulations in agriculture.

Best Practises/Recommendations

The literature review has highlighted just some of the good practises that are already being used to address the problematic working and living conditions of farmers and farmworkers.

In Topic1, the articles analysed highlighted that conversion to organic farming has been shown to increase farmer satisfaction, that greenhouses provide an acceptable psychosocial environment and that improvements in education and health management have a positive impact on the mental health of farmers and farmworkers.

In Topic 2 three best practises have been identified for dealing with structural vulnerability and discrimination that manifests as a cultural stressor:

1. **Identification and assessment of environmental microaggressions (EMs):** Using critical race theory and interdisciplinary methods, researchers have identified how farmworkers experience subtle forms of discrimination. This understanding is critical to addressing the health impacts of these microaggressions on marginalised groups.
2. **Empowerment through participatory education:** Initiatives such as the four-year Preventing Agricultural Chemical Exposure among North Carolina Farmworkers (PACE) project empower farmworkers by directly engaging them in education and training about workplace hazards, particularly exposure to pesticides. By working with community organisations and involving agricultural employers, these programmes improve farmworkers' ability to identify and address their own health and safety issues.
3. **Specialized Local Health Care:** Local clinics and support groups have made significant strides in providing specialised, accessible healthcare for migrant farmworkers. These efforts include better access with open appointments, translation services and community support to meet the immediate health needs of farmworkers and compensate for the lack of comprehensive national systems.

Additionally, to handle the stressor arising out of the ruptures in the moral economy three good practises in research and intervention were identified

1. **Ethical, political and emotional analysis of farmers' distress:** this approach challenges the traditional mental health framework and offers alternative social and political responses to alleviate farmers' distress and prevent suicide by focusing on the cultural, political and emotional dynamics that shape their experiences.
2. **Multidimensional framework to examine working conditions:** A comprehensive theoretical framework examines multiple dimensions of working conditions, such as control, income, job security, health, and political experiences. This systemic analysis identifies specific trends, trade-offs and key

issues in different farming systems (agroecological, organic and conventional) and provides insights to improve sustainability and working conditions in agriculture.

3. Farmer responsibility and knowledge acquisition: Encouraging farmers to take responsibility for health, safety and the environment despite financial constraints promotes a culture of informed change. Programmes such as the Environmental Farm Plan and the Pesticide Safety Course, as well as personal research and peer discussions, help farmers to adapt their practises in a careful and informed way, contributing to an overall improvement in sustainability and safety in agriculture.

Overall, it can be concluded that the working environment and occupational safety and health in agriculture is an area that requires further attention and research, especially as agriculture is a socially indispensable activity and at the same time a dynamic sector that is likely to remain so in the future, given the various drivers of change mentioned above. In this context, the literature reviewed points to a number of substantive and methodological recommendations for further research. These suggestions can be found on the previous pages of this report, but just to recap some of them here.

The articles analysed under Theme 1 have clearly shown that further research should focus on raising awareness of the presence of stressors in the farming environment, especially as work-related stress is directly linked to mental health problems, injuries and general well-being. This could help to improve the quality of life and work for farmers, for example by addressing the misunderstanding of farmers' lifestyles by other professional/social groups, which could help to reduce stigmatisation and encourage farmers to seek help. Furthermore, studies investigating the vulnerability of farmers and farm workers to stress compared to other occupational groups are needed to gain insight into the specifics of their situation. Such studies are rare, especially in Europe.

The articles in Topic 2 dealing with the culture of farming contain several suggestions: to consider a gender-sensitive approach to a more comprehensive understanding of the mental health and well-being of farmworkers of all genders. In addition, they emphasise the need to conduct more research that addresses the international context of migration to better understand ethnic and civic inequalities in health; to use the concept of structural violence to shift the focus of anthropological and health policy analysis from individual behaviours to social structures; to incorporate qualitative health research from a first-person perspective into broader contextual debates and decision-making processes to develop a comprehensive understanding of health and safety in agricultural systems (e.g. community-supported agricultural systems); recognising the significant influence of economic pressures on risk-taking, as this underlines the active and creative ability of farmers to develop different solutions to similar economic challenges, i.e. that health and safety programmes and interventions are both context sensitive and adaptable to the different strategies farmers adopt in response to economic pressures; support interdisciplinary collaboration, e.g. by integrating insights from psychology, behavioural economics, risk science, sociology, anthropology, human geography and others.

It is also suggested from the articles in Topic 3, which deals with the social security of farmers and farmworkers, that further research is needed, as little attention has been paid to this topic, especially in Europe. Therefore, there are several proposals, such as exploring the vulnerability of migrant farmworkers, taking into account their legal status and nationality (which implicitly requires intersectionality), examining their perceptions of risk and their experiences in relation to health, and taking an integrated and global perspective on immigration; medical pluralism and autonomy in health care must be considered in research and recorded in patients' medical records, and health care providers must be aware of these practises so that they can also advise and better incorporate their knowledge; studies addressing the shortcomings in monitoring and auditing working conditions should be conducted in collaboration with all stakeholders such as farmworkers, occupational health and safety professionals, local authorities and the government.

As the introduction of digitalisation in agriculture is still in its early stages, further research should also focus on Topic 4. It is particularly important to map and monitor the process in this area with regard to

the use of various devices and machinery and to review their impact on the working conditions and well-being of farmers and workers in different types of farms. As an analysis of articles on this topic has shown, there is still little empirical evidence on the social aspects of farming with new technologies.

And a final thought: future research that takes into account the above suggestions and existing best practise could be an important driver of change, helping to increase the attractiveness of farming and ensure the sustainability of agriculture in the future.

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APPENDIX 2: DETAILED ANALYSIS AND REVIEW OF STUDIES ON TOPIC 1 IN CHAPTER 1

Table 1: Article no., authors, publication year, country of study, year of study conducted, study type and target group(s)

Article (PDF) No.	Author(s)	Publication year	Country of study	Type of Study	Year of study	Target group(s)
6	L. M. Acosta, A. R. Andrews, M. N. Acosta Canchila and A. K. Ramos	2020	USA (Nebraska)	Quantitative	2016	migrant farmworkers
76	H. Bai, C. Beseler, L. Baccaglini and R. H. Rautiainen	2022	USA (7 central United states)	Quantitative	2018 and 2022	migrant farmworkers
81	P. J. Batterham, K. Brown, A. L. Calear, D. Lindenmayer, K. Hingee and C. Poyser	2022	Australia	Quantitative	2018 and 2019	farmers
90	J. D. Berman, M. R. Ramirez, J. E. Bell, R. Bilotta, F. Gerr and N. B. Fethke	2021	USA	Quantitative	2012-2015	farmers
93	C. Beseler and L. Stallones	2020	USA	Quantitative		farmers
107	C. Bossard, G. Santin and I. Guseva Canu	2016	France	Quantitative	2007-2008	farmers
113	M. Bouttes, A. Bancarel, S. Doumayzel, S. Viguié, M. S. Cristobal and G. Martin	2020	France	Quantitative	2016-2018	dairy farms
128	A. J. Callejón-Ferre, M. E. Montoya-García, J. Pérez-Alonso and J. I. Rojas-Sola	2015	Spain	Quantitative	2010-2012	farmworkers and workers
134	G. Carlo, M. McGinley, S. Maiya and A. K. Ramos	2023	USA (Nebraska and Kansas)	Quantitative	2017-2020	migrant farmworkers
215	K. M. Fennell, C. E. Jarrett, L. J. Kettler, J. Dollman and D. A. Turnbull	2016	Australia	Mixed methods	2008	farmers
225	E. M. Furey, D. O'Hora, J. McNamara, S. Kinsella and C. Noone	2016	Ireland	Quantitative	2015	farmers
245	J. G. Grzywacz, S. A. Quandt, H. Chen, S. Isom, L. Kiang, Q. Vallejos and T. A. Arcury	2010	Norway	Quantitative	2007	migrant farmworkers
262	B. G. Hansen	2022	Norway	Quantitative	2017 and 2018	farmers
277	A. E. Hiott, J. G. Grzywacz, S. W. Davis, S. A. Quandt and T. A. Arcury	2008	USA (North Carolina)	Quantitative	2003	migrant male farmworkers
306	B. Janzen, C. Karunanayake, D.	2020	Canada	Quantitative	2014	rural adult inhabitants

	Rennie, J. Lawson, J. A. Dosman and P. Pahwa					
383	C. G. Magaña and J. D. Hovey	2003	USA (Ohio and Michigan)	Mixed methods	1998	migrant farmworkers
406	D. C. Mora, S. A. Quandt, H. Chen and T. A. Arcury	2016	USA (North Carolina) countries	Quantitative	2010	migrant farmworkers
416	N. J. Negi, J. E. Swanberg, J. M. Clouser and C. Harmon-Darrow	2020	USA (Kentucky)	Quantitative	2013-2014	migrant farmworkers
423	K. O'Connor, M. Stoecklin-Marois and M. B. Schenker	2015	USA (California)	Quantitative	2006-2007	migrant male farmworkers
442	D. Peel, H. L. Berry and J. Schirmer	2016	Australia	Quantitative	2013	farmers
445	K. Pérès, C. Brayne, F. Matharan, L. Grasset, C. Helmer, L. Letenneur, A. Foubert-Samier, I. Baldi, F. Tison, H. Amieva and J. F. Dartigues	2017	France	Quantitative	1988-1989, 2007-2008	farmers
462	H. L. Radunovich, T. Younker, J. M. Rung and M. S. Berry	2022	USA (Florida)	Mixed methods	2019	farmers
465	A. K. Ramos, G. Carlo, K. Grant, N. Trinidad and A. Correa	2016	USA (Nebraska)	Quantitative	2013	migrant farmworkers
466	A. K. Ramos, D. Su, L. Lander and R. Rivera	2015	USA (Nebraska)	Quantitative	2013	migrant farmworkers
469	M. K. Rayens and D. B. Reed	2014	USA (Kentucky)	Quantitative	2000-2002	farm couples
485	J. M. Rudolphi and R. L. Berg	2023	USA (Midwest 5 states)	Quantitative	2021	farm parents and adolescents
486	J. M. Rudolphi, R. L. Berg and A. Parsaik	2020	USA (Midwest: Iowa, Kansas, North Dakota, and Wisconsin)	Quantitative	2018	young adult farmers
528	M. TePoel, D. Rohlman and M. Shaw	2017	USA (Oregon)	Quantitative	2012	farm couples
532	A. Thelin, E. L. Stiernstrom and S. Holmberg	2000	Sweden	Quantitative	1990-1991	farmers
533	A. G. Thelin	1998	Sweden	Quantitative	1994	farmworkers and workers
535	M. O. Torske, J. H. Bjørngaard, B. Hilt, D. Glasscock and S. Krokstad	2016	Norway	Quantitative	1984-1986, 1995-1997, 2006-2008	farmworkers and workers

1. Year of the analysed study

The data collection for the studies analysed in TOPIC 1 took place between 1984 and 2022, which indicates a long-term period of study years, as the first wave of the oldest study dates back to 1984. Most of the studies were conducted in 2018.

2. Geographical location (country) of the analysed study

Most of the thirty-one studies of TOPIC 1 studies took place in the US (N=17), often specifying particular states or regions such as Nebraska, North Carolina, Ohio and Michigan, Kentucky, California, Florida, Oregon, and several Midwestern states. Some studies were conducted in Europe, with France (N=3) and Norway (N=3) being the most frequently cited countries, followed by Spain (N=1) and Ireland (N=1). Three studies were conducted in Australia and one in Canada.

3. Purpose of the analysed study

After reviewing the literature according to the research question and the focus of TOPIC 1, the general aim of the studies examined was to investigate the important stress factors affecting farmers and/or farm workers and, in particular, their impact on mental health and well-being.

The provided text highlights the key areas of research related to stressors and mental health in the agricultural sector, summarized as follows: identification of important stressors and mental health outcomes (depression and anxiety, occupational stress and mental health, substance (mis)use, dementia and cognitive impairment, suicidal behaviour).

4. Methods used

All analysed studies used the quantitative method. Only three studies ([215], [383], [462]) used mixed methods: quantitative and qualitative.

5. Target group(s)

The studies analysed in TOPIC 1 focus on various groups involved in farming, especially migrant workers and farmers, with additional attention to specific subgroups such as farmer couples, young adult farmers and adult rural dwellers.

The most frequently studied target group is "migrant farm workers," who are exposed to numerous stressors that affect their health, safety, wellbeing and quality of life in general. "Farmers" is also a frequently mentioned target group. Variations such as "migrant male farmworkers" and "farmworkers and labourers" are also present, indicating a focus on different subgroups within farmworkers. "Rural adult residents" is listed once, indicating a study focused on adults in rural areas. "Farm couples" and "Farm parents and youth" appear in the list, indicating studies that focus on family dynamics within farming communities. "Young adult farmers" is mentioned, suggesting a focus on younger people involved in farming. One particular study [113] looked at dairy farms, examining a particular type of farm and the satisfaction of workers involved in the day-to-day operations of the farm in the context of conversion to organic farming

6. Concepts, terms and theories

As in other topics (2, 3 and 4), TOPIC 1 also identified various concepts, terms, models and theories in the studies examined, which deal with the perceived health and safety risks of the working and living environment of the group under investigation.

The job demands and control model (Karasek, 1979) and ***The job demands and control and support model (Van der Doef and Maes, 1999?)***, which are widely used in occupational health research to assess workload, were used in the study focusing on the influence of job demands and gender on occupational and psychosocial stress in Hispanic farm workers [528]. The models assume that stress or psychological strain results from the interaction of job demands (e.g. high workload or insufficient direction from the supervisor), decision latitude (the amount of control employees have over their decisions) and social support (support from family, colleagues or supervisors). High job demands and low decision latitude were associated with depression, job dissatisfaction and self-reports of poor physical and mental health.

The job strain model (Karasek, 1979) has been used in two other studies (90), [533]: an occupational cohort study of American farmers and a Swedish study examining the conditions of the work environment in rural areas using psychosocial indices.

The job demands and resources model (Bakker and Demerouti, 2007) provides a useful descriptive framework for conceptualizing the effects of workplace stress on farmers [225]. The core principle of the theory is that work demands can cause psychosocial and physical costs, but work resources trigger motivational processes that can lead to greater work engagement and higher performance, offsetting the costs caused by work demands. As self-employed lone workers, farmers have fewer practical and psychological resources to deal with negative situations in the workplace than the average employee does. In terms of demands, farmers are exposed to higher levels of stress, and the effects of this stress are reflected in negative physical and mental health outcomes.

Lazarus' stress model (Lazarus and Folkman, 1984) was used in the study that looked at psychosocial stressors among Mexican migrant farm workers in the Midwestern United States [383]. According to Lazarus, the stress response is influenced by how people cognitively appraise the stressors and how they can effectively respond to the stressors. People who appraise an event as threatening are likely to experience more stress than those who feel that they are able to respond constructively to the event. Coping occurs as individuals change their cognitions and behaviours to deal with the particular external or internal demands that they perceive to be straining their adaptive resources. This stress model is based on the idea that two people can experience the same stressor or stressors with the same frequency and duration, but do not experience the same level of stress. For example, two migrant farm workers may be exposed to the same stressors but experience different levels of stress.

The Conceptual model of work and health disparities (Lipscomb, Loomis, McDonald, Argue and Wing, 2006), which posits that for marginalised populations, such as Latino farmworkers, the context of hazardous jobs may lead to higher levels of stress and associated health disparities is mentioned in the article [416]. One challenge is how to best operationalize the context of a hazardous workplace in relation to migrant workers' mental health.

The Ecological Stress-based model of immigrant worker safety and health (Ramos, McGinley and Carlo, 2021) has been used to examine the association between work-related injury and stress and family and youth well-being among immigrant US Latino cattle ranchers [134]. It describes historical and contextual stressors (e.g., work-related, major life stressors) as well as intrapersonal factors (e.g., coping, mental health) hypothesized to impact worker health outcomes.

Two stress-based models: Gender role strain theory (Levant, 2011) [6] and The concept of Nervios (Baer, 2003) [423], were used in studies with migrant workers in agriculture. Gender role strain theory, which states that gender role beliefs are most likely to cause significant stress when these beliefs are threatened or conflict with other demands, was used as a theoretical basis in a study [6] describing the conditions under which traditional machismo exacerbates the harmful effects of certain stressors while having no effect on others. The concept of Nervios is a culturally defined mental health condition that is present in all Latino subgroups and for which there is considerable intergroup agreement on the specific characteristics that have important implications for Latino health. It was explored in an epidemiologic study [423]. The lack of understanding of this culture-bound syndrome by healthcare providers and farm employers, contributes to the creation and perpetuation of health disparities among Latinos.

Theory of well-being (Dodge, 2012; Wassell and Dodge, 2015) is a multidimensional concept that encompasses many different subjective dimensions: Health, happiness, optimism, work-life balance, skills, social relationships, environment, and safety, and has been used in two studies [81] and [262]. However, there is no single formula for well-being that applies to everyone. Well-being occurs when individuals have the psychological, social and physical resources they need to cope with a particular psychological, social and/or physical challenge.

The concept of farmers' satisfaction (Kessem, 2021) was examined in a study looking at conversion to organic farming [113]. They focused on five variables representing farmer satisfaction: – Economic status of the farm (e.g., cash flow, debt-to-equity ratio, hereafter referred to as “economic”) – Agronomic,

i.e., soil and crop conditions (e.g., yields, soil health, hereafter referred to as “agronomic”) – Livestock, i.e., social, relationships with relatives, neighbours, and society (e.g., quality of interactions with tourists about the farm, hereafter referred to as “social”). Satisfaction with farm work in general, which has an influence on mental health, was the subject of the study [469].

The family stress model (FSM) (Conger, 2002) was used in examining the mental health of adolescents and adults in agriculture [485] The concept of the FSM suggests that economic difficulties characterized by negative economic events and associated with low family income increase the economic pressure faced by parents, leading to externalizing and internalizing behaviours in adolescents.

7. Results of the analyses

The results of the analysis of the articles were divided into three categories. First, we identify the sources of stress (A) that are most important or threatening for farmers and farm workers. Then we show the effects of the stressors on the well-being (B) of farmers and farm workers and the effects of the stressors on various aspects of mental health (C) of farmers and farmworkers.

A. Sources of stress

The analysis of articles, which focused on the assessment of stressors in farming, showed that [93] **high debt** was the most important predictor of stress. The next group of predictors of stress with the highest rate were **health indicators**: a doctor's visit that was not possible due to cost, limitation or interruption of activities due to illness, a chronic illness, having a usual place to go for of medical care, health insurance, and number of prescribed medications. Another causative factor identified is **exposure to pesticides**. However, married, male farm dwellers with higher education had the lowest stress levels. Among young adult farmers and ranchers, **personal finances** and **time pressure** were also the sources of greatest concern [486].

A thematic analysis of South Australian farmers' sources of stress during drought [215] showed that most (73.1%) of the reported sources of stress were related to farming. A thematic analysis revealed that **drought, financial pressure and uncertainty about the future** were the most prevalent sources of stress. A number of other, more specific stressors related to drought (e.g. poor crop yields, unsatisfactory conditions for livestock rearing, overwhelming workload) and **contextual stressors** (e.g. rising input costs, family involvement in farming, pressure to participate in community work, lack of understanding of farming by ‘outsiders’) were also identified. **Non-drought-related problems** (e.g. machinery breakdowns) and non-agricultural stressors (e.g. illness and death of relatives) were added to the prevalent stressors [215].

The association between drought and the relationship between job strain and stress was mainly caused by an increase in psychological work demands. This result suggests that the relationship between occupational psychosocial strain and drought is determined by effects on psychological job demands rather than decision latitude [90].

A study of stress factors contributing to depression among Latino migrant workers in Nebraska found relatively high levels of stress in the population studied. **The highest rated stressors were related to: 1. economics and logistics, 2. acculturation and social isolation, 3. relationship with partner, 4. health, 5. entertainment, 6. caring for children, 7. substance use by others** [466].

Among the stressors, those related to **business and logistics** were the most important. Acculturation and social isolation were the second most important area. Stress related to 1. acculturation and social isolation, 2. immigration issues, 3. children of workers is positively related to poor self-related health [466].

Associations of **work-related injuries and stress** with family and youth well-being among US Latino/a immigrants working on ranches reported that increased stress and work-related injuries on ranches are associated with mental health problems, which in turn is related to more conflict at home and less prosocial behaviour among youth [134].

The study, which focused on self-employed farmers and ranchers, showed that high perceived stress levels were a risk factor for injury [76]. Stress, sleep deprivation and fatigue showed a similar positive association with injury [76]. The study identified livestock as the most common cause of injury [76]. However, because the study focused on self-employed farmers and ranchers, the results are not generalizable to other employed agricultural workers [76].

The study, which examined the effects of work demands and gender on occupational and psychosocial stress in Hispanic farmworker couples with children during the agricultural season at times of low and high work demands, showed that **women experienced more work-family conflict and less support at work** [528].

There is also a study that reports acceptable working conditions. The study on psychosocial risks of agricultural workers in greenhouses in the southeast of the island found that the greenhouses of Almería provide an acceptable psychosocial environment [128].

Compared to other occupational groups, farmers had a **significantly higher index of psychological stress**, stimulation of work, **but also authority over work** than other occupational groups. Farmers had a significantly higher index than almost all other occupational groups with regard to worries about the future. Of all occupational groups, farmers had the best relationship between psychological demands and stimulation at work [533].

Psychosocial conditions and access to an occupational health service (OHS) among farmers showed that the group with OHS experienced significantly more psychological demands at work, but also had significantly more decision latitude in their work. Farmers with OHS were: less single, better educated, had more social contacts, had larger farms and had fewer psychosocial risk factors [532].

B. Wellbeing

Financial difficulties or financial worries were associated with poorer mental health and well-being, as was younger age [81].

The study on conversion to organic farming showed that dairy farmer satisfaction increased regardless of the strategies used. This is in stark contrast to previous studies that emphasized the multiple risks of conversion to organic farming [113].

Higher levels of work-related stress were associated with lower life satisfaction among workers, which in turn was related to lower levels of prosocial behaviours among adolescents [134].

A study of older rural couples showed that most participants were relatively satisfied with their work in agriculture. Men had higher satisfaction scores than women and this difference was significant [469].

Farmers with a college degree felt more comfortable than those with less education, but the difference in well-being decreased the higher the level of education [442].

C. Mental health

Psychological stress directly predicted farmers' expectation of injury and a direct effect of non-financial stress in agriculture approached significance. Psychological distress mediated these relationships, as evidenced by significant indirect effects of agricultural stress and financial and social support on reducing distress [225].

The relationships between stressors and mental health are not always clear-cut, but can also be indirect. Financial difficulties or financial worries have been associated with poorer mental health and well-being, as has younger age [81]. Financial difficulties and worries can have a direct effect on mental health, but it is also possible that farmers who struggle with their mental health find it more difficult to engage financially and environmentally to support their farms [81].

In the study examining the effects of job demands and gender on occupational and psychosocial stress in Hispanic farmworker couples with children, women reported poorer mental health than men [528].

The prevalence of nervousness, which has been shown to be a clinical indicator of psychiatric vulnerability in Latinos, was 22%, with no difference in prevalence by household status. Nervousness was associated with low family income, substance use, poor housing, self-reported poor health, depressive symptoms, and high perceived stress [423].

Depression and anxiety

The study examining the effects of stress on the mental health of migrant farm workers [277] showed that the mental health of this population is poor. Depression scores in this population were high; almost half of the participants (41.6%) had depression scores, which are often used as a benchmark for possible depression. 18.4% of the population reported anxiety levels above the measurement tool threshold, indicating anxiety that could impair functioning. More than a third (37.6%) of farm workers had a potential case of alcohol dependence. Social isolation has the strongest potential impact on farm workers' anxiety. Stressful working conditions have the strongest potential impact on depressive symptoms [277]. The study with Mexican migrant farmworkers showed that the interaction between fear of deportation and traditional machismo and the interaction between discrimination and traditional machismo were significant in predicting depression. A significant predictor of depression was also harsh working conditions and poverty. Harsh working conditions also significantly predicted anxiety [6].

The study on depressive symptoms among Latino farmworkers across agricultural seasons found a U-shaped pattern, with symptoms highest at the beginning and end of the season. Structural stressors (e.g., marital status) and situational stressors (e.g., work place, cramped living conditions, documentation worries) were key predictors. Unmarried workers reported the highest symptoms of stress, while married workers experienced the lowest level of stress. Having personal storage reduced symptoms, while perceived crowding increased them. Elevated concerns about documentation, discrimination, and exclusion also correlated with higher depressive symptoms [245].

Associations between poor housing and mental health among Latino migrant farmworkers in North Carolina showed significant depressive symptoms, significant anxiety, and potential alcohol abuse among Latino migrant farmworkers [406]. Depression was positively correlated with gender (women), job stress (higher job insecurity, number of days missed due to injury), and work-related ethnicity/ethnicity discrimination [416]. Another study of Mexican migrant farmworkers in the Midwestern United States [383] came to the same conclusions regarding symptoms of depression. The sample also reported relatively high levels of depressive symptoms. The sample reported relatively high levels of anxiety symptoms compared to the census matched standardization sample. The stressors "rigid job demands" and "poor housing conditions" were significantly associated with higher levels of anxiety, and "low family income/living in poverty" and "rigid job demands" were significantly associated with depression [383].

A study of stressors contributing to depression among Latino migrant workers in Nebraska found relatively high levels of stress in the population studied. The highest rated stressors were related to: 1. economics and logistics, 2. acculturation and social isolation, 3. relationship with partner, 4. health, 5. entertainment, 6. caring for children, 7. substance use by co-workers [466]. A study of stress, depression, and occupational injury among migrant workers in Nebraska found that 1 in 3 workers reported relatively high levels of stress and 1 in 2 workers reported relatively high depressive symptoms; compared to the general population [465]. Stress and depression were positively associated with

occupational accidents and occupational accidents were also a significant factor for depression, but not for stress [465].

In the study of stress factors contributing to depression among Latino migrant workers in Nebraska [466], nearly half of the respondents were depressed. Respondents who were exposed to economic and logistical or health stressors were more likely to be depressed. The burden of depression and anxiety is high among young adult farmers and ranchers. Personal finances, time pressure, economic conditions, and relationships with co-workers were associated with anxiety and depression [486].

The results of the study on the mental health of agricultural adolescents and adults showed a strong correlation between the mental health of the parents and that of the adolescents. Parental depressed mood was highly associated with adolescent depression, social anxiety, and generalized anxiety. The economic measure most strongly associated with parental depressed mood was debt [485]. A study of farmers' mental health in Norway: a longitudinal comparison between siblings showed that farmers were the most likely of all occupational groups to had symptoms of depression. Siblings in other occupations were less likely to suffer from depression [535].

Interesting results were found in a study of rural adults in Saskatchewan, Canada [306]. The results suggest that rural Saskatchewan residents who do not live on a farm may be more susceptible to impaired mental health than their agricultural counterparts. Women who did not live on a farm and had two or more chronic illnesses were more likely to report depression than their agricultural counterparts. Men with secondary education who did not farm reported more depression than men who farmed. The other correlates of depression were generally consistent with previous research in rural populations, including younger age, no partnership (men only), higher stress, greater financial burden (women only), and lower social support (women only) [306]. The psychological role that work plays for women is reflected in the study "Predictors of depressive symptoms in older rural couples", which found that women who were more satisfied with their farm work were less depressed [469].

Substance use

The results of the study, "The impact of the opioid crisis on agriculture", provide preliminary evidence that opioid use is significantly impacting personal health, labour availability, and agricultural productivity. Opioid use was significantly higher in the horticulture industry than in food production. Work factors affecting opioid use: on-the-job injuries, opioids often impaired ability to perform daily tasks, absenteeism, being fired from a job [462].

Binge drinking

In a study of adult farmworkers and non-farmworkers in Saskatchewan, Canada, binge drinking was significantly increased among women and men who did not work in agriculture compared to the agricultural population. Among women only, lack of access to a family doctor or nurse was associated with a higher likelihood of binge drinking than among women who had better access [306].

Prevalence of dementia and cognitive impairment

Trends in the prevalence of dementia in French farmers from two epidemiologic cohorts showed that the prevalence of dementia was higher over the study period, but the prevalence of cognitive impairment with disability (CIWD) was significantly lower in the final study period, possibly due to higher levels of education, improved management of vascular risk factors, and health and living conditions [445].

Suicide rate among farmers

Suicide among farmers in France was the focus of a study that found that the rate of suicide deaths among male farmers was elevated compared to the general population. This increased rate was particularly high in the 45–54 age group (31%) and the 55–64 age group (47%) in 2008 (and in the 55–64 age group (64%) in 2009). Two specific types of farming activity were associated with an increased suicide rate in both 2008 and 2009: dairy farming and cattle farming. Hanging was the most common

method of suicide for both genders (61% for males, 54% for females). After hanging, female farmers most frequently chose drowning (15%) or poisoning (9%) [107].

Farm exit intention

The study of Norwegian dairy farmers found that age, work situation, quality of life, and mental health influence the decision to continue or leave farming. Older farmers are more likely to exit, while optimism, lower loneliness, manageable workloads, and a feeling of being valued reduce this likelihood. Satisfaction with the workday is negatively linked to the intention to leave a farm. Modern statistical methods improve the analysis of the causes and consequences of farm exit intention, which has implications for farmers, advisors and policy makers [262].

Another study on the intention to leave the farm showed that a higher intention to leave was associated with poorer well-being and greater psychological stress, and was more pronounced among: (1) less profitable farmers, (2) younger farmers, (3) farmers with larger farms, (4) farmers earning a low to medium proportion of their household income off-farm. Old farmers were more likely to have given up farming for age-related reasons. Young farmers were more likely to give up for reasons related to the viability of the farm [442].

APPENDIX 3: DETAILED ANALYSIS AND REVIEW OF STUDIES ON TOPIC 2 IN CHAPTER 2

Table 2: Article no., author(s), publication year, country of study, year of study conducted, study type and target group(s).

Article (PDF) No.	Author(s)	Publication year	Country of study	Type of study	Year of study	Target group(s)
6	Acosta et al.	2020	US (Midwest)	Quantitative	2016	Migrant farmworkers
25	Alston	2012	Australia	Qualitative	NA	Informants at policy levels, from local communities, farming families and service providers
39	Anneberg and Sandøe	2019	Denmark	Qualitative	NA	Farm employees
47	Arcury et al.	2001	US (North Carolina)	Mixed methods	1997-1999	Farmworkers, farmers, extension agents and health care providers
48	Arcury et al.	2002	US (North Carolina)	Quantitative	1999	Farmworkers
51	Areguin et al.	2020	US (California)	Quantitative	2017	Farmworkers
54	Arnold et al.	2020	US (North Carolina)	Mixed methods	2016 and 2017	Child farmworkers
66	Austin et al.	2001	US (North Carolina)	Mixed methods	1997 and 1998	Farmworkers, farmers, extension agents and health care providers
86	Becot et al.	2021	US (Pennsylvania and Wisconsin)	Quantitative	2018	Farm parents and farmers
89	Benson	2008	US (North Carolina)	Qualitative	2004 and 2005	Farmers and migrant farmworkers
97	Birtalan et al.	2022	Hungary	Qualitative	2015	Farmers
117	Brock et al.	2012	US (Georgia)	Mixed methods	2009	Migrant and seasonal farmworkers
121	Bryant and Garnham	2014	Australia	Qualitative	2005	Farmers
154	Cheney et al.	2022	US (California)	Qualitative	2017 and 2018	Farmworkers
163	Cole et al.	2019	Canada, Mexico and Jamaica	Qualitative	2006-2009, 2010-2013, 2012 and 2011-2014	Doctors, nurses and other healthcare professionals
176	Cur et al.	2021	US (Idaho)	Mixed methods	2018 and 2019	Farmworkers
203	Duke	2011	US (Connecticut)	Qualitative	2002-2004	Farmworkers
204	Dumont and Baret	2017	Belgium	Qualitative	2014-2016	Producers, experts and farm advisors, farm labourer, social secretariat and a member of collective buying group

206	Duval et al.	2021	France	Qualitative	2019	Farmers
213	Farquhar et al.	2008	US (Oregon)	Quantitative	2006	Farmworkers
214	Feldman et al.	2009	US (North Carolina)	Quantitative	2005	Migrant and seasonal farmworkers
218	Fiatkowska et al.	2022	Poland	Qualitative	2019-2021	Migrant farmworkers, employees and farmers-employers
223	Friesen et al.	2010	Canada	Qualitative	2006	Farmers and service providers
250	Gün et al.	2007	Turkey	Quantitative	2018	Agricultural workers
255	Hagel et al.	2016	Canada	Quantitative	2013	Owner-operators
256	Hagel et al.	2013	Canada	Quantitative	2007	Owner-operators
257	Hall	2007	Canada	Qualitative	NA	Farmers
262	Hansen	2022	Norway	Quantitative	2017 and 2018	Farmers
263	Hansen et al.	2020	Norway	Quantitative	2017 and 2018	Farmers
269	Hennebry et al.	2015	Canada	Mixed methods	2008 and 2009	Migrant farmworkers
283	Holmes	2006	US (Washington State, California, Arizona) and Mexico	Qualitative	2003 and 2004	Farm employees, clinicians
284	Holmes	2011	US (Washington State)	Qualitative	2003 and 2004	Farm employees and employers
293	Hull et al.	2022	Australia	Qualitative	NA	Farmers
316	Kallioniemi and Kymäläinen	2012	Finland	Qualitative	2007	Farmers
319	Karttunen and Rautiainen	2011	Finland	Quantitative	NA	Farmers
329	Key and Wheat	2021	US (South)	Qualitative	2018	Farmers
337	Kjestveit et al.	2021	Norway	Quantitative	2012	Farm owners
394	McLaughlin and Mayhorn	2011	US (North Carolina)	Qualitative	NA	Farmers
435	Panelli and Gallagher	2003	New Zealand	Qualitative	2000	Growers
443	Peoples et al.	2010	US (California)	Qualitative	2008	Emancipated migrant youth
447	Perilla et al.	1998	US (Georgia)	Qualitative	1996	Migrant farmworkers and families
466	Ramos et al.	2015	US (Nebraska)	Quantitative	2013	Migrant farmworker
470	Reid-Musson et al.	2022	Canada	Qualitative	2019	Farm operators, family members and farm employees
534	Thu	1998	US (Iowa and Nebraska)	Qualitative	1996	Farmers
557	Wadsworth et al.	2022	US (California)	Qualitative	2018	Agricultural employers

1. Year of the study

In the second half of the 1990s, only one study was conducted on health and safety of farmers and their family members. Other studies on this target group were conducted in the first (five studies) and second (nine studies) decades of the 21st century, with 2019 being the most recent. In five articles, the year of the study was not specified.

Studies on the health and safety of farm workers, including migrants and employees, were conducted in the second half of the 1990s (four studies) and in the first and second decades of this century (nine studies each). Two studies were conducted between 2006 and 2014 and between 2019 and 2021, the latter being the most recent. One article did not specify the year of the study.

2. Geographical location (country) of the study

The studies looking at health and safety of farmers and their family members come from Europe (40%), Australia and New Zealand (20%), Canada (20%) and the US (20%). Another set of studies that focus on the health, working and living conditions of migrant farm workers or employees and the relationships of employers, healthcare providers and others with them are predominantly from the USA (76%), followed by Canada (12%) and Europe and Turkey (12%).

3. Methods used

Qualitative methods predominated in the studies on the health and safety of farmers (thirteen studies) and farm workers (twelve studies). Exclusively quantitative methods were used in seven studies per study group, while mixed methods were only used in (six) studies on the health and safety of farm workers and the relationships of different groups of people with them.

4. Target groups by some characteristics (POPULATION & COMPARATORS)

Research participants: Farmers were the exclusive target group of seventeen studies, while sixteen studies focused on migrants and seasonal farm workers or employees. In three studies, farmers were labelled as farm operators ([255], [256]) or farm owners ([337]) and in one as farm parents ([86]), while five times, they were presented as farm employers and their relationship with their employees was specifically considered ([89], [218], [284], [470], [557]). In four studies, the perceptions of advisors and healthcare providers were also included ([47], [66], [163], [283]). The latter were the only target group in one study ([163]). Three farm-level studies ([25], [204], [223]) involved multiple groups of participants, ranging from policy-level informants, local communities, farming families and service providers, experts and farm advisors, a social secretariat and a member of a buying group, to farmers and farm labourers.

Gender: In the vast majority of studies, only men or predominantly men were included, but there were some exceptions. Two studies with small samples, one of which included equal numbers of male and female farmers ([97]) and another of farm operator and their family members with seven men and nine women, and farm employees with three men and two women ([470]). Female farm workers were the focus of four studies, in three as exclusive participants ([176], [250], [316]) and in one as predominant (74%, [154]). Twelve studies did not include information on gender.

Age: The majority of study participants, which consisted of migrant or farm workers and employers or farmers, had a wide age range and included participants from eighteen to fifty or sixty plus years and in some cases seventy years and older. Five studies included participants of younger ages, firstly farmers aged thirty-eight to forty-five years ([97]), secondly female agricultural workers aged twelve to fifty-four years ([250]) and thirdly migrant farm workers and their family members aged thirteen to twenty-two years ([447]); one study looked at adolescent emancipated migrant youth ([443]) and another at child farm workers aged ten to seventeen years ([54]). In fifteen studies, the age range was not specified.

Ethnicity: Studies on migrant farm workers, mainly from the USA and Canada, focussed on Latinx participants, primarily Mexicans, but also Guatemalans and Salvadorans, for example. Four of these studies also looked at the health and labour issues of indigenous groups such as Guerrero, Oaxaca and Triqui, as well as Latinx farm workers with US citizenship. Caribbean farm workers, including Puerto Ricans, were included in three studies, Jamaicans in two, and African farm workers in one, along with Latinx migrants. Two articles on the European context of farm workers from Poland ([218]) and Denmark ([39]) looked at indigenous and Ukrainian farm workers, while the Danish study also included

participants from Romania, Estonia and Eritrea. A study on agricultural labourers from Turkey included only local seasonal workers ([250]).

Education: Sixteen studies provide information about the participants' education. Eight studies on farm workers mention the level of education attained (from primary school to higher education and vocational training) or other important information that takes into account their structural vulnerability, whether they attended school at all and sometimes, if so, for how long on average. Eight articles on farmers, including one article on farm' parents ([86]), also mention the level of education attained or whether the farmers have any training or qualification related to agriculture.

Type of farming: The nature of farm production was described in twenty-eight studies, of which thirteen referred to hired labour and fourteen to the farm level and one to both groups of studies. Farm employees worked on a variety of farms. The most frequently mentioned types of production were tobacco, fruit and vegetable farming (such as strawberries, sweet potatoes and tomatoes), followed by various types of livestock farming and cotton production. Most of the participating farmers run livestock farms, often dairy farms, and various arable farms; a few farmers were (also) involved in fruit and vegetable growing ([86], [121], [256], [329], [534]). Three studies ([204], [206], [257]) addressed also the agroecological transition of farms with different production methods.

Farm size: Information on farm size was generally not provided, especially in the studies on the migration context. However, there are two exceptions, as one study mentioned that migrant farm workers cultivate about sixty hectares of tobacco fields and another several hundred fruit trees, especially berries. On the other hand, eleven studies on farmers indicated that the farm size ranged from about one hectare to ten or more hectares in five cases and from about fifty to several hundred hectares in six other cases.

Comparators: There were no studies comparing farmers or farm workers with other occupational groups or the general population, with the exception of one study that investigated how horse trainers' and vegetable growers' perceptions of work, home, health and gender relations affect men's and women's respiratory health. The study found that in both primary industries, perceptions of masculinity are likely to influence people's choices and limited use of preventative safety measures, sometimes in the face of significant stress and health problems. Furthermore, women in both industries position themselves differently from men, as women's involvement in training horses can be as autonomous and diverse as men's, while women vegetable growers are positioned as more subordinate "helpers" who endure difficult working conditions while supporting the stressful but more autonomous tasks and working lives of their male partners ([435]). Rather, comparisons are made between different social groups of migrant farm workers by ethnicity ([203], [213], [214], [283], [284]) or between female and male farmers ([25], [257], [263], [316], [435], [470]), between farmers and migrant farm workers or employees ([39], [89], [203], [218], [284], [470]), between younger and older child farm workers ([54]) and between different generations of farmers ([470]), between farmers, farm workers, extension workers and/or health care providers ([47], [283]), between farmers in terms of their agricultural background ([86]) and their use of automatic or conventional milking systems ([262]) and between farmers who do or do not follow agroecological/organic farming principles ([204], [206], [257]).

5. Purpose of the study (ISSUES)

As a result of reviewing the literature in line with the question and focus of TOPIC 2 (the cultural roots of health and safety risks in agriculture), the studies reviewed generally address both workplace safety and wellbeing (including health) of the target groups in order to better understand the phenomenon and propose recommendations for improved solutions (interventions) or research on the topic. However, it is worth noting that most studies focused on cultural sources of health and safety risks in agriculture alongside other main research objectives. Simply put, cultural stressors were not explicitly mentioned in the study objectives, but were later included or discussed in the research analysis.

From the 45 screened articles selected for the final analysis of the systematic literature review, we identified **four groups** of cultural sources of health and safety risks in agriculture.

The first group of articles refers to **gender identities and relationships as cultural sources of health and safety risks in agriculture** ([6], [25], [176], [316], [435]).

The second group of articles considers **structural vulnerability and discrimination as a cultural stressor** to examine the health and safety of farmers and farm workers in their living and working environment, in the community and in the wider regional context ([39], [51], [66], [89], [154], [163], [203], [213], [218], [250], [269], [283], [284], [443], [447], [466]).

The third group of articles aimed at investigating **farmers' or growers' exposure to ethical, political and emotional dimensions of their specific farming systems** (e.g., community-supported agriculture, alternative agroecological farming, contractual farming, organic and conventional farming) **as a cultural source of their discomfort or ill-being** ([97], [121], [204], [206], [257]).

The fourth group of studies addressed **perceived risk, danger, and control over the agricultural work and living environment as a cultural stressor** to determine whether there are differences in the perceptions and beliefs of different target groups – e.g., migrant or seasonal farm workers, farmers or supervisors, extension workers, health care providers or outreach workers, farmers from different agricultural backgrounds, etc. – and how these relate to their health and safety ([47], [48], [54], [86], [117], [214], [223], [255], [256], [262], [263], [293], [319], [329], [337], [394], [470], [534], [557]).

6. Concepts and theories

It is worth noting that the following concepts, terms, models or theories used in the four groups that we identify in relation to cultural sources of health and safety risks in agriculture are not unique and limited to a single group, as cultural stressors were more often addressed implicitly or indirectly in addition to other types of stressors. Therefore, some of them are also used in other groups of studies reviewed.

6. 1. Gender identities as a cultural source of health and safety risks in agriculture

Gender role strain theory and the concept of traditional machismo: Study that directly considers gender as a cultural stressor that may affect the health and safety of the observed study populations used gender role strain theory, which states that stress occurs when demands and life circumstances conflict with gender role beliefs, and concepts such as traditional machismo and traditional machismo beliefs in conjunction with other variables and stressors to determine their effects on depression and anxiety in a male study group ([6]).

The concepts of rurality and masculinity: Another study examined threatened rural masculinity through the concepts of rurality (where men hold the dominant position of influence and power and the majority of rural resources, including land) and masculinity (male hegemony) to explain how rural men describe the way they view themselves and their health, as well as the high suicide rate among rural men in times of crisis ([25]).

A gender approach: The few studies focussing on women did not use a particular gender theory or concept, but simply a gender approach in the form of a gendered study sample ([176], [316], [435]). The same applies to the studies that only consider the gender dimension via the gender representativeness of the sample, but use other theories, models and concepts (e. g. *structural vulnerability* [176]). In addition to the declared male and female gender in most of the studies analysed, other genders of LGBT people were not discussed.

6. 2. Structural vulnerability and discrimination as a cultural source of health and safety risks in agriculture

Studies that directly addressed the phenomena of structural vulnerability, violence and discrimination as cultural sources of health and safety risks in agriculture also used different theoretical approaches and concepts or none at all. Most of these studies formulate concepts for their research purpose, drawing on several academic disciplines. In turn:

The concept of farm worker-specific environmental microaggressions (EMs) (environmental racism or everyday environmental discrimination) was coined by psychologists to create a quantitative measure of EMs for further study. In expanding their initial literature review, the authors included additional relevant literature from other academic disciplines to broaden their theoretical foundations and incorporate a critical race perspective that was previously lacking in psychological research and theorising ([51]).

Structural and symbolic violence has been used as a *theoretical framework* of analysis in studies that seek to explain intertwined political, economic and cultural processes of reproducing the overall social machinery of oppression of vulnerable groups, *as well as a concept* to explain a particular perception based on a specific understanding of alterity that leads to discriminatory behaviour or a vulnerable position or both, in our case of migrant farm workers in relation to farmers, migrant farm workers in relation to each other, farmers in relation to the state or agribusiness, etc. in their working and living environment ([39], [66], [89], [283], [466]).

The same applies to the related *concept or theoretical basis of structural vulnerability*, which has been used to refer to cultural and social determinants of health and the social structures that create systematic barriers to equitable health care for – in our case – mainly migrant and Indigenous farm workers ([154], [163], [213], [269], [443], [447]) and to a lesser extent for farmers. This concept has also been used to explain existing and persistent social and cultural (work and life) hierarchies and inequalities based on gender, ethnicity, socio-economic status and location that may determine a person's level of vulnerability within a community (or society) and their work environment and influence their wellbeing ([176], [250], [284]), and are perpetuated not only by internalised beliefs and myths about the culture of others, but also by a particular form of *governance* – another concept that attempts to explain the way these hierarchies are maintained ([203]).

Structural vulnerability is also indirectly addressed through *the concept of liminality* to show how liminality in the context of managed temporary migration programmes creates the conditions for increased vulnerability that also affects the health of migrant farm workers and their access to health care. Liminality means being between places, categories and time frames and arises from an interplay of structural factors that keep these people in a permanent temporary limbo ([269]).

Finally, *the concept of agricultural exceptionalism*, in the sense of special regulations and exemptions introduced for agriculture in relation to migrant farm workers during the COVID-19 pandemic in Poland that did not exist in other sectors of the economy, was used to examine how this concept came to bear in questionable relationships between farmers and farm workers ([218]).

All of these concepts are useful in explaining the consequences of overt and covert social oppression and discrimination for health and safety in agriculture, which are barely recognised in mainstream study of health and safety in agriculture or health care.

6. 3. Ruptures in the moral economy (ethics and emotions) as a cultural source of health and safety risks in agriculture

Studies that focus their analysis on ruptures in the moral economy of farmers that lead them to experience unexpected difficulties in their work environment that are beyond their control and power, or that they cannot reconcile their own ideas of being a good farmer with the new agricultural realities making their distress and ill-being a possibility, tend to indicate that the moral and emotional dimensions of the political economy of agriculture in relation to farmers' wellbeing are neglected in the mainstream discourse on health and safety in agriculture. These studies refer to the concepts of moral economy, moral sentiment, well-being and ill-being, farmers' distress as emotional suffering and relate them to different variables that fit the purpose of the study.

The concept of farmer distress as emotional suffering, contextualised in the realities of the farming way of life, was used in the study that aimed to investigate how ethical, political and emotional dynamics

cause farmers' distress and make suicide a possibility ([121]). In the same study, farmer distress was framed within a *moral economy* (a concept) that incorporates the ethical, social and economic relationships between farmers, corporations and the State in which their businesses are embedded.

The study that examined growers' experiences of community-supported agriculture (CSA) affecting their *mental health* and work engagement ([97]) used a health psychology approach that built on CSA farmers' individual stories and evaluated their "lived experiences" using interpretative phenomenological analysis.

Two studies examining the advantages and disadvantages of working conditions (including *wellbeing*) of producers in alternative agroecological systems ([204], [206]) drew on the sociological, economic and agronomic literature to define a theoretical framework that defines working conditions as multidimensional. Both studies used *agroecological principles or model as defined by Dumont et al. (2016)*, as a framework. The first study was based on agroecological socio-economic principles (environmental equity, social justice, financial independence, market access and autonomy, sustainability and adaptability, partnership between producers and consumers, etc.), while the second study was based on principles for agroecological livestock systems to optimise ecological processes.

The study ([257]), that analysed whether different restructuring and environmental orientations are related to different approaches to occupational safety and health, did not refer to a theoretical framework.

6. 4. Risk perception, safety and health beliefs in agriculture as a cultural source of health and safety risks in agriculture

Farm workers' perceptions of risk, danger and control over the working and living environment in agriculture were examined using different health models. Farmers' perceptions of their children's safety were examined using the concepts of parenting styles and agricultural background, and the concept of disability based on the International Classification of Functioning was used in the study examining barriers and facilitators to return to work for farmers with a disability. Most of the studies in this group of cultural sources of health and safety risks in agriculture did not use any specific theory or concepts, but investigated perceptions of risk, danger and control over the working and living environment using semi-structured interviews or questionnaires. In turn:

The Health Belief Model with its six key concepts – perceived susceptibility (of the risk as an outcome), perceived severity (of the outcome), perceived benefit (of a health behaviour to change the risk of the outcome), perceived barriers (to taking action), incentives to take action and self-efficacy – was used in the study examining the extent of perceived pesticide risk and control among farm workers and its relationship to knowledge, safety behaviour and action among them ([48]).

Another study was guided by *the Health Behaviour Model* ([214]) to determine the extent to which health care utilisation reflects the skin problems of farm workers and to compare the overall level of health care utilisation among farm workers with that of the US adult male population.

The Ecological Model for Farmworkers' Musculoskeletal Health was used in the study ([117]) as an *adaptation of the Theoretical Model of Determinants of Hispanic Migrant Farmworker Health*, which includes health beliefs, acculturation, location of injury control, type of compensation, potential and actual access to health care, and physical work environment.

A study ([319]) investigated the prevalence and risk factors for a decline in work ability among Finnish full-time dairy farmers based on a *Balance Model*, in which the individual's resources are balanced with the demands of work in a safe and healthy way.

Another study investigated the relative importance of individual, farm and work environment-related risks for occupational injuries and discussed the latent conditions for injuries among Norwegian farmers using *sociotechnical system theory*, which emphasises the interdependence of technical and social systems in the organisation to achieve the most efficient outcomes, implying that external/contextual factors also play a role in preventing occupational injuries and not just the worker/farmer ([337]).

Nine studies did not explicitly refer to the concepts or models, but rather explored farm workers' perceptions of the presence of elements of field hygiene and safety behaviours in pesticide use ([47]), as well as their perceptions of heat hazards, heat-related symptoms in the work environment and protective strategies ([54]), the prevalence of hazards, safety investments, safety practises and work habits and their relationship to farm injuries ([255]), the focal relationships between economics and safety while simultaneously adjusting for confounders at the farm level ([256]), the broader individual, social and systemic factors that influence help-seeking behaviour in relation to physical and mental health, from the perspective of Australian farmers ([293]), experienced farmers' perceptions of hidden and non-intuitive hazards, their typical tasks and the tasks and machines they consider particularly dangerous ([394]); the relationship between experiences and identities at the farm level and the process by which the boundaries and jurisdiction of labour law are shaped in relation to workplace safety, with the core premise of legal geographies that social relations and experiences are simultaneously legal and spatial ([470]); the pattern of social and economic conditions associated with industrial agriculture identified by farmers, which together create stressful conditions that lead to an increased risk of injury and health problems among farmers ([534]); and the perspectives of farm employers on safety and health risks related to climate change ([557]).

The attitudes and practises of farming parents regarding the safety of their children were analysed using *the concepts of parenting styles and farming background*, with first-generation farmers defined as those who did not grow up with or inherit a farm and multi-generation farmers where more than one generation of a family was an owner-operator ([86]).

The study examining the barriers and facilitators to return to work for farmers with a disability ([223]) used *the concept of disability* as limited participation in meaningful activities of work or daily living within the theoretical underpinning of *the International Classification of Functioning – a health and disability classification framework* that recognises personal and contextual barriers and facilitators to participation in life roles and activities.

Two studies were based on *Dodge's concept of wellbeing*, i. e. the psychological, social and physical resources people need to cope with a particular psychological, social and/or physical challenge. They investigated the intention to quit farming in relation to farmers' satisfaction with different aspects of their lives ([262]) and how different dimensions of wellbeing (income, level of job satisfaction, mental health and work-life balance) are influenced by the characteristics of the farm, the farmer and the management of automatic milking systems ([263]).

The study on occupational safety and health among limited resource African-American farmers used a *concept of agrarian ethics* for which there was no explanation ([329]).

APPENDIX 4: DETAILED ANALYSIS AND REVIEW OF STUDIES ON TOPIC 3 IN CHAPTER 3

Table 3: Article no., authors, publication year, country of study, year of study conducted, study type and target group(s)

Article (PDF) No.	Author(s)	Publication year	Country of study	Type of study	Year of study	Target group(s)
11	A. Agudelo-Suárez, D. Gil-González, E. Ronda-Pérez, V. Porthé, G. Paramio-Pérez, A. M. García and A. Garí	2009	Spain	qualitative	2006-2007	migrant farmworkers
45	T. A. Arcury, K. F. Furgurson, H. M. O'Hara, K. Miles, H. Chen and P. J. Laurienti	2019	USA, North Carolina	quantitative	2007	migrant farmworkers
100	W. L. Boal, J. Li and S. R. Silver	2022	USA, 31 states	quantitative	2017-2018	Workers in different sectors (also agriculture)
140	S. Caxaj, A. Cohen and S. Marsden	2020	Canada	qualitative	NA	migrant farmworkers
164	C. Colindres, A. Cohen and C. Susana Caxaj	2021	Canada	quantitative	2019	migrant farmworkers
176	C. L. Curl, L. Meierotto and R. L. Som Castellano	2021	USA, Idaho	mixed	2018-2019	migrant farmworkers
223	M. N. Friesen, O. Krassikouva-Enns, L. Ringaert and H. Isfeld	2010	Canada	qualitative	NA	Farmers, their spouses and service providers
225	E. M. Furey, D. O'Hara, J. McNamara, S. Kinsella and C. Noone	2016	Ireland	quantitative	NA	Farming men
250	S. Gün, B. Gülçubuk, E. Olhan and N. Yildirak	2007	Turkey	quantitative	2001	Female farmworkers
258	E. R. Hamilton, J. M. Hale and R. Savinar	2019	USA	quantitative	2000-2015	Migrant farmworkers
264	E. Hartman, H. H. E. Oude Vrielink, R. B. M. Huirne and J. H. M. Metz	2003	Netherlands	quantitative	1994-2001	Farmers with injuries
267	M. S. Haugen, A. Blekesaune	2005	Norway	mixed	NA	Farmers and farm spouses
269	J. Hennebry & J. McLaughlin & K. Preibisch	2015	Canada	quantitative	2008-2009	Migrant workers
278	Hoerster KD, Beddawi S, Michael Peddecord K, Ayala GX.	2010	USA, California	quantitative	2001, 2002	Farmworkers, mostly migrants
279	Hoerster KD, Mayer JA, Gabbard S, Kronick RG, Roesch SC, Malcarne VL, Zuniga ML.	2011	USA	quantitative	2006,2007	farmworkers

283	Holmes, Seth, M.	2006	USA, Washington, California, Mexico - Oaxaca and then Arizona and back to Washington state	qualitative	Around 2004	Migrant farmworkers and service providers
293	M. J. Hull, K. M. Gunn, A. E. Smith, M. Jones and J. Dollman	2022	Australia	qualitative	NA	farmers
297	M. Ingram, K. A. Schachter, J. Guernsey de Zapien, P. M. Herman and S. C. Carvajal	2014	USA, Arizona	qualitative	NA	Migrant farmworkers and service providers
320	J. P. Karttunen and R. H. Rautiaine	2013	Finland	quantitative	2010	Farm couples
373	M. L. Loureiro	2022	USA North Carolina	qualitative	2021	Community health workers
398	R. H. Meyer and R. J. Fetsch	2006	USA	quantitative	2003	Farmers & AgrAbility clients)
426	R. A. Okyay, F. Tanir and P. M. Ağaoğlu	2008	Turkey	quantitative	2023	Farmworkers (migrant and non-migrant)
432	D. Öztaş, B. Kurt, A. Koç and M. Akbaba	2018	Turkey	quantitative	2017	Migrant farmworkers
444	M. Perceval, J. Fuller and A. M. Holley	2011	Australia	mixed	2007-2009	farmers
447	J. L. Perilla, A. H. Wilson, J. L. Wold and L. Spencer	198	USA, Georgia	qualitative	NA	Migrant farmworkers
455	A. Posturzyńska, A. Wojtyła, L. Hans, I. Morawik, J. Strzemecka and M. Jabłoński	2012	Poland, Germany	qualitative	NA	Na (comparison of two systems)
457	K. Preibisch and G. Otero	2014	Canada	mixed	2007-2009	Stakeholders
474	H. Rinne, M. Laaksonen and J. Blomgren	2017	Finland	quantitative	2012	Different occupational groups
479	A. Ropponen, A. Samuelsson, K. Alexanderson and P. Svedberg	2013	Sweden	quantitative	1993-2008	Twins in Sweden, - comparison with workers in agriculture, forestry, fishery
482	M. Rubio González, M. D. M. Jiménez-Lasserrotte, M. I. Ugarte-Gurrutxaga, K. El Marbouhe El Faqyr, J. Granero-Molina, C. Fernández-Sola and F. J. Plaza del Pino	2023	Spain	qualitative	2022	Service providers
555	L. F. Vosko, T. Basok, C. Spring, G. Candiz and G. George	2022	Canada	mixed	2021	Migrant farmworkers

1. Year of the study

The oldest study analysed dates back to 1993. Earlier studies examined longitudinal data, e.g. on the use of sick leave among farmers. Only two studies conducted before 2000 were included in the analysis.

2. Geographical location (country) of the study

In terms of geographical focus, eleven studies were conducted in the USA, six in Canada, three in Turkey, two in Australia, Spain and Finland and one in the Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Ireland, Germany and Sweden. Only one study used data from two countries (Poland and Germany).

3. Methods used

More than a half of the analysed studies used quantitative approaches; about a third qualitative methods and five used mixed method design.

The studies that have been conducted more recently have used qualitative approaches, in particular interviews (with farmers, farmworkers and professionals who meet them) and focus groups, and in rare cases long-term ethnographic fieldwork. Of the studies analysed, sixteen used quantitative methods, ten used qualitative methods and five used a mixed methods approach. Sometimes, only a part of the study based on larger data sets is presented in the article and we refer to the methods as they are presented in the articles. Only four studies were longitudinal studies, and among these, there were no qualitative studies. As a rule, existing statistical data (surveys, register data) were analysed based on longer time series.

4. Target groups

The analysed studies analysed migrants and the 'local population' in equal proportions, some of the articles compared farmers/farmworkers to other occupational groups and only a few compared migrant and non-migrant farmworkers. Some articles focussed on the experiences of service providers and other stakeholders encountering farmers and farmworkers.

Out of all the analysed articles, thirteen focussed on the experiences of migrant farmworkers as the main group included in the analysis and six articles examined the experiences of different service providers/ stakeholders. Three articles compared farmers to other occupational groups, two articles focussed on women and men as spouses in farm families, two examined farmers with disabilities and two articles compared health service uptake and utilization between 'local' and migrant farmworkers using health statistics. One article focussed on the experiences of AgrAbility clients, one on the experiences of female farmworkers, one article focussed only on male farmers and one article on farmers with injuries. One article was a comparative presentation of two national social protection systems and the other articles focussed on farmers in general.

With regard to gender, one article analysed only women and one article only men. Especially when data coming from professionals working with farmers and farmworkers were presented, the information on gender was usually missing and this was the case in some, although rare articles on farmers and farmworkers. When both genders were included in the study, the majority of research participants were usually men, which might reflect the gendered structure of migrant farm work or the higher prevalence of men in studies conducted on livestock farms. Only one study included information about non-binary participants and none of the studies focussed on the LGBT+ populations.

Regarding age, none of studies focussed on children and specifically on older farmers (65+), and in most studies the participants were of the 'working age population' (18-65), although particularly the studies on migrant farmworkers usually included younger age cohorts (approximately 30 to 40 years of age).

When studies analysed farmers that were non-migrants as a rule no information was given on their ethnicity, and regarding migrant farmworkers, articles employ different ethnic categories. In the majority

of cases, the terms 'Latina' and 'Mexican' farmworkers are used, but sometimes more specific ethnic affiliations and regionally specific groups are mentioned (e.g. Triqui, Oaxaca region, etc.). Especially in the USA and Canada, the great majority of research participants are from Mexico and other countries in Central America, while within studies in Europe, there are greater ethnic/countries of origin variations (e.g. workers from Central, South America, workers from African countries, workers from Romania, etc.). In certain cases, information about citizenship status, rather than information about ethnicity is given.

None of the studies focussed specifically on farmers and farmworkers with higher education levels and in most of the studies, only sporadic and not very systematic information about education is provided (e.g. the percentage of participants that have completed high school or certain years of schooling).

More particularly, one study focussed on farmers with experiences of injury, and some studies, especially those analysing women, included information about the number of children, length of stay in the country, employment status severity of injury, etc.

In most cases, the information about the type of farming was not given. In studies including migrant farmworkers, most of them worked in picking (e.g. berries) while for farmers, there were studies conducted on dairy farms, cropping and picking. Even rarer was the information about farm size, although in some cases, we could suppose from the interview material that research was taking place on big industrial farms, one study was conducted on a midsize farm and one on a small family farm.

5. Purpose of the study

A strand of the analysed studies focussed on working conditions and characteristics of employment in connection to the general well-being and quality of life. Studies also focussed on barriers to accessing social security, in particular concerning health insurance utilization, and the role of social support (both formal and informal) in providing such security. Rarer studies compared migrant and non-migrant farmworkers and/or farmers/farmworkers to other occupational groups. Some studies sought to capture the experiences of stakeholders and professionals encountering farmers and farmworkers.

Some studies examined the working conditions and characteristics of employment as well as experiences of discrimination at work and the relationship to health, particularly of migrant farmworkers ([11]), status, living and working conditions of female seasonal farmworkers in cotton production ([250]), and the challenges to well-being and related social, cultural, and workplace risk factors among Latina farmworkers ([176]). They also assessed the characteristics and distribution of compensated agricultural work injuries, and identified work-related and personal risk factors for compensated claims ([320]). More generally, differences in life satisfaction among female farmworkers in different labour categories were studied ([267]).

Another branch of research looked more closely at barriers to accessing social security e.g. gaps in benefits for migrant farmworkers. It attempted to assess various indicators of effectiveness and sustainability ([164]), access to health services for seasonal farmworkers ([432]), examined barriers and facilitators to return to work after injury or disability ([223]), factors associated with health care use among California farmworkers ([278]), and individual, environmental, and policy-level factors that affect U.S. farmworkers' health care utilisation ([279]). It examined the ways in which migrant workers' social context affects their health and health care ([283]), assessed migrant workers' health and service needs ([447]), the barriers and facilitators that affect farmworkers' help-seeking behaviour related to health and mental health problems ([293]), and described the use of a community-based participatory approach to assess and address gaps in migrant farmworkers' perceptions of mental health care in the US-Mexico border region ([295]).

A subset of studies also focused on the role of social support, such as examining the role of social support actors in shaping workers' needs, identifying gaps, challenges, and opportunities that influence the development of appropriate support for migrant farmworkers ([140]), identifying community support (formal and informal) needed and available to farmworkers with disabilities ([223]), and how social

support increases available resources and decreases expectations related to psychological distress and injury ([225]). Some studies have taken a comparative approach, e.g. comparing seasonal and resident farmworkers in terms of socio-demographic characteristics and occupational health and safety ([426]).

Specific studies ([45]) focused on documenting the use of conventional health care providers, traditional and complementary therapies, and perceived purposes and differences in use by age and education to include less traditional means of obtaining social security. The effects of time constraints on the health of migrant workers and the difficulties they encounter in accessing care and compensation from health systems designed for citizens were investigated ([269]).

Studies also examined professionals' perceptions to understand how health professionals in the field are proceeding to identify important and credible health information for migrant and seasonal farmworkers ([373]) and assessed the impact of the national AgrAbility project on farmers and ranchers with disabilities ([398]) and whether Farm-Link has succeeded in improving access and responsiveness to mental health services for farmers and farmworker families ([444]).

With regard to the use of certain social protection services, the studies focused on baseline data on diagnosis, incidence and duration of sickness absence among self-employed Dutch farmers ([264]), examined how occupational groups and psychosocial working conditions were associated with future disability pensions due to musculoskeletal diagnoses, taking into account family factors in the associations ([479]), and compared the principles of social insurance and health insurance for farmers in Poland and Germany ([455]). Utilization of outpatient and inpatient health services and differences between occupational groups were investigated, as well as whether these differences were explained by sociodemographic factors and health status ([474]).

Health insurance utilisation has also been the focus of studies, such as in the context of COVID-19, where one study sought to assess access to health insurance coverage prior to the pandemic (baseline) and other measures of access to health care among selected workers in critical infrastructure, particularly workers with limited ability to move, including farmworkers [100]. With respect to COVID-19, studies have focused on discovering and describing the experiences of migrant farmworkers during COVID-19 ([482]) and the relationship between the structure and functioning of Canada's Temporary Agricultural Worker Programme, migrant farmworkers' risk of contracting COVID-19, and their experiences working and living in Ontario and Quebec during the pandemic ([555]).

6. Concepts, terms and theories

Some studies, particularly those on migrant workers in agriculture, analysed different levels of society such as the study of *discrimination* and *racism* at the individual, group and structural levels and considered discrimination as a complex phenomenon that can be experienced by both immigrants and the native population of the host country ([11]). The concepts of structural *vulnerability/racism/inequality* [176], *structural violence* [283], the concept of *health inequalities* ([258]) and the *social determinants of health approach* [269] were used in selected studies. These concepts shed light on the structural organisation of agriculture and farm labour. As cited in the article on migrant farmworkers in Canada ([176]), 'structural vulnerability asserts that existing social hierarchies determine an individual's level of vulnerability within a community (or society) and points to the political and social contexts in which people work. Structural violence is enacted in contemporary agriculture through the domination of the market and then channelled through international and national racism, classism, sexism, and anti-"illegal" immigrant sentiments ([283]). All these concepts can serve as useful in analysing health inequalities in vulnerable populations, such as migrant workers. The framework of *medical pluralism*, which links the use of traditional healers and complementary therapies to the use of conventional medical care ([45]), was used to focus on alternative forms of access to social security in one study, and one study focused on the concept of *patient-centred care* ([297]).

Articles also described different dimensions of *social support (formal and informal)* ([140], [223], [225]), and some used *gender inequalities* as the main conceptual framework ([176], [250], [267]), emphasising

that the additional marginalisation associated with gender can lead to further disadvantage [176]). With regard to stress at work in agriculture, one study described the *model of work demands and resources* - work demands may impose psychosocial and physical costs, but work resources trigger motivational processes that may lead to greater work engagement and performance, offsetting the costs imposed by work demands ([225]). Another study described the concept of *quality of life* in more detail ([267]). The *health information seeking behaviour framework* has been used to describe how community health workers help farmworkers overcome language, educational, and transportation barriers to access health services and information ([373]). The framework of *cultural care theory* is used in one study ([447]) to emphasise the importance of care, knowledge, and practises that are transculturally different. Thus, culture-based care can contribute to the well-being of individuals, families, groups, and communities within their settings; and such culturally congruent care can only occur when the individual, group, family, or community's cultural care values, expressions, or patterns are known and used appropriately and meaningfully when working with people ([447]).

APPENDIX 5: DETAILED ANALYSIS AND REVIEW OF STUDIES ON TOPIC 4 IN CHAPTER 4

Table 4: Article no., authors, publication year, country of study, year of study conducted, study type and target group(s).

Article (PDF) No.	Author(s)	Publication year	Country of study	Type of study	Year of study	Target group(s)
[263]	Gunnar Hansen et al.	2020	Norway	Quantitative (online questionnaire)	2017-8	Farmers
[265]	Hartung et al.	2018	Spain, Italy, UK, Netherlands, France, Hungary, Germany, Sweden, Denmark, Belgium	Qualitative (interviews)	2014-6	Farmers
[321]	Karttunen et al.	2016	Finland	Quantitative (online survey)	2014	Farmers
[334]	King et al.	2021	Canada	Quantitative (online survey with validated psychometric scales)	2019	Farmers
[501]	Sazili Shahibi et al.	2023	Malaysia	Qualitative (interviews)	/	Farmers
[236_1]	Gunnar Hansena & Stræte	2020	Norway	Quantitative (online questionnaire)	2017	Farmers
[334_1]	Tse et al.	2018	Canada	Mixed-method (online surveys & interviews)	2014-5	Farmers
[236_2]	Gunnar Hansen B.	2015	Norway	Qualitative (unstructured interview)	2011-2	Farmers
[236_3]	Alpass et al.	2004	New Zealand	Quantitative (online questionnaire)	/	84% farm owners; 11% sharemilkers
[236_4]	Mathijs E.	2004	Belgium, Denmark, Germany, Netherlands	Qualitative (interviews)	2001-2	Farm managers
[321_1]	Molfino et al.	2014	Australia	Qualitative (case study: survey & interview)	2014	Farmers

1. Year of the study

Table 4.1 provides an overview of the eleven studies included in the systematic literature review. Most of the data in these studies were collected between 2012 and 2022. In one study ([236_4]), however, the baseline assessment process was already initiated in 2001. In nine studies ([263], [321], [334], [236_1], [334_1], [236_2], [321_1], [236_4], [236_3]) the farmers had dairy farms, in one study ([265]) data were collected from nine pig farms, five broiler farms and seven dairy farms, and in one study from a paddy farm ([501]).

2. Geographical location (country) of the study

Eleven studies were included. The included studies were conducted in Norway ([263], [236_1], [236_2]), Finland ([321]), Canada ([334], [334_1]), Malaysia ([501]), New Zealand ([236_3]) and Australia ([321_1]). However, in two studies, the researchers collected data in several countries simultaneously, in the first ([236_4]) in Belgium, Denmark, Germany and the Netherlands and in the second ([265]) in Spain, Italy, the United Kingdom, the Netherlands, France, Germany, Sweden, Denmark, Belgium and Hungary. Most of the data were from Europe, but studies from Australia, New Zealand and Malaysia were also selected as the data are comparable to the European data in many respects and the findings are useful and applicable to the European agricultural context.

3. Purpose of the study (ISSUES)

What all studies have in common is that they deal with the impact of technological progress in agriculture on various aspects of farmers' lives. A considerable number of the studies (e.g. studies [263], [265], [334], [236_3]) specifically examine the relationship between the introduction of technology and farmers' mental health, well-being and stress levels. Many studies (e.g. [265], [236_1], [321_1]) focus on how the introduction of new technologies changes farmers work processes, working conditions and job satisfaction. They examine specific agricultural technologies, such as precision livestock farming (PLF) systems, drone technology and automatic milking systems (AMS). Each study aims to understand the impact of these technologies on the working environment, health, safety and overall quality of life of farmers. Some studies (e.g. studies [334_1], [321_1]) address the transition period and the adaptation process of farmers when adopting new technologies, focussing on the challenges and benefits that arise. The specific objectives of the selected studies are presented below:

- 1) The aim of the study [265] was to gain an insight into the benefits and problems of PLF (livestock production systems) in practice. The aim was to find out from farmers in their living and working environment their views and opinions on the effects of introducing PLF technology on their farms.
- 2) The study [501] aimed to gain an insight into the use of drone technology and its impact on the working environment and health of Malaysian rice farmers.
- 3) The aim of study [263] was to investigate the well-being of dairy farmers with AMS and the factors associated with well-being.
- 4) The aim of the study [265] was to analyse the changes in working conditions when switching from a conventional milking system (CMS) to an AMS. The focus was on health, quality of life and the working environment.
- 5) The aim of the study [334] was to investigate the relationship between the mental health of farmers and the well-being of cows on dairy farms using robotic milking systems.
- 6) The aim of the study [236_1] was to investigate how farmers experience the effects of new technologies (AMS) in their daily work. The focus was on the working environment and process as well as job satisfaction.
- 7) The aim of study [334_1] was to investigate the experiences of dairy farmers during the transition to and use of AMS.
- 8) The aim of study [236_2] was to investigate what motivates farmers to invest in AMS and what impact this has on farmers' lifestyles and farm management.
- 9) The aim of study [236_3] was to investigate dairy farmers' perceptions of stress, particularly in relation to the introduction of new technologies and the relationship with age and gender.
- 10) The aim of study [236_4] was to investigate, in a first part, the motivations and characteristics of farmers investing in the AMS and, in a second part, the effects on farmers' work input and quality of life.

- 11) The aim of the study [321_1] was to investigate the effects of the introduction of AMS on the work process and the effects on the lifestyle and quality of life of dairy farmers.

4. Concepts, terms and theories used

A number of psychosocial concepts have been used in studies to assess the impact of new technologies on farmers. Researchers used the concept of *stress* to assess the psychological and physical effects of increased workload and technological challenges, while the concept of *well-being* was applied to examine the improvement in life satisfaction and happiness due to reduced physical labor. *Job satisfaction* was analysed in relation to the changes in work routines and tasks, and the concept of *mental and physical health* was used to assess the impact on overall health. *Motivation* was examined to understand the driving forces behind technology adoption, such as economic benefits and personal interest. *Quality of life* was considered in terms of work-life balance and personal fulfilment, while *animal welfare* was linked to farmers' mental health and job satisfaction. Finally, the concepts of *social and human capital* were used to examine the impact on farmers' skills, knowledge sharing and community support. More specifically:

The *stress* concept used in the studies ([236_3], [236_1], [334]) is defined as the psychological and physical response to demands that exceed one's ability to cope. The researchers sought to assess the impact of new technologies on farmers' mental and physical health, focussing on workload, technical challenges and overall stress.

Based on the concept of *well-being* ([263]), the study examined the impact of new technologies on farmers' life satisfaction and happiness, including the reduction of physical labour, etc.

When the researchers investigated the extent of fulfilment and satisfaction with one's work, they used the concept of *job satisfaction* ([236_1], [263]). They investigated how the use of new technologies influences farmers' satisfaction with their work processes and tasks.

Using the concept of (*mental*) *health* ([263], [501], [265], [334]), the researchers attempted to analyse the effects of the usage of new technologies on farmers' mental and physical health.

In analysing what motivates farmers to adopt new technologies, focusing on the economic benefits, efficiency and personal interest in the innovation, the researchers used the concept of *motivation* ([236_4]).

Using the concept of *quality of life* ([236_4], [236_1], [334], [265], [321_1]), the researchers investigated how new technologies affect farmers' work-life balance, leisure time and personal fulfilment.

The study ([334]) investigated how the technological AMS system affects animal welfare and established a link with farmers' mental health and job satisfaction. The concept of *animal welfare* was used for the analysis.

When the researchers ([236_2]) sought to understand the impact of new technologies on farmers' social and human resources, including skills, knowledge sharing, community support and collaborative networks, they used the concepts of *social* and *human capital*.

5. Methods used

Quantitative, qualitative and mixed methods were considered, looking at different aspects of the measurement of psychosocial and safety problems among farmers and farmworkers.

Five of the included studies were quantitative studies ([236_3], [263], [321], [334], [236_1]), mixed methods studies ([334_1]) and studies that used qualitative research methods ([265], [501], [236_2], [321_1], [236_4]). In the studies that used qualitative methods (n = 5), the data was collected using a structured or unstructured interview. In the studies that used quantitative methods (n = 5), the data was

collected using online surveys. In one study ([334]), the data was collected using established psychological instruments that had been validated.

6. Target group(s) (POPULATION & COMPARATORS)

The research subjects in all the studies in our selected articles were very uniform, namely male farmers using new technologies in farming. Only the study from New Zealand ([236_3]) considered gender and different age groups of farmers. However, the impact on the safety, (mental) health or quality of life of farmers and farm workers can be divided into three main categories depending on which technology they use: 1) automatic milking systems (AMS), 2) precision livestock farming (PLF), 3) drones and 4) other technologies.

Farmers participating in eight studies used AMS technology ([263], [321], [334], [236_1], [334_1], [236_2], [321_1], [236_4]), in one study ([501]) farmers reported on the use of drones, in one ([265]) livestock management systems are reported on and in the last ([236_3]) on many different technologies are presented:

- 95.4% artificial insemination;
- 92.2% soil testing;
- 91.2% somatic cell counting;
- 83.8% mineral supplements;
- 73.4% last available pasture species;
- 68.6% treatment of dairy cows against intestinal parasites;
- 62.7% CIDRs (controlled intravaginal drug release to increase conception rate);
- 44.3% use of computers to record data;
- 42.2% use of computers to record events (e.g., mating, calving);
- 37.2 % use of maize silage;
- 29.4 % feed analysis;
- 18.4 % use of computers for feed budgeting;
- 1.1 % certified organic farming (e.g. BioGro).

7. Results of the analyses – Psychosocial and technological stress factors resulting from the introduction of new technology

The stressors most frequently mentioned in the studies were those related to the mental workload caused by technology overload and, consequently, the technostress caused by the introduction of new technologies and the inability to deal with new technologies optimally and effectively.

The stressors that fall into this category are:

- *data/information overload* ([263], [334_1], [236_2], [321_1]). The constant influx of data from new technologies such as sensors and monitoring devices can overwhelm farmers. The mass of information and data must be analysed and interpreted in order to make optimal and efficient decisions. Quite a few farmers expressed the problem of data processing and the associated stress.

- *techno-intrusion*: 24/7 on-call alerts to manage technology, e.g. through night alarms etc. ([263], [321], [236_2]). The need to be available 24/7 to manage technology, for example to respond to alerts or alarms from automation systems, intrudes on personal time and peace of mind. This intrusion into private life can lead to the feeling of being "always on duty".

- *the maintenance of technology and the repair of defective parts* ([265], [236_3]). New technologies often require regular maintenance and occasional repairs, which makes farmers dependent on the companies and their service technicians. The responsibility of keeping the technology operational can be a major burden, especially if the farmer does not have the technical expertise or resources to carry out repairs in a timely manner.

- *the additional workload due to increased production* ([236_1], [321_1], [236_2]). New technologies allow farms to expand and become more productive. As a result, farmers have reported that their

workload has not decreased. The workload has also increased because farmers have had to manage more animals, crops (to justify the investment in new technologies) or data points, which can overtax their physical and mental abilities.

- *the training of animals to familiarise them with the new technology* ([334_1]). Familiarising animals with new technologies, such as automatic milking systems, requires time and patience. The support from the company and the experts has proven to be very welcome.

- *the lack of sufficient knowledge and technological expertise* ([236_3], [334_1], [321], [265], [263]). Farmers may not have sufficient training or experience with new technologies, leading to feelings of inadequacy and anxiety. Some farmers mentioned the social network as a very important source of information and knowledge.

- *the debt burden that increases with investment in the system* ([236_3], [265], [263]). Investments in new technologies often require considerable financial outlay, which can lead to increased debt. The pressure to repay loans and justify the investment with improved productivity can lead to financial stress.

8. Results – Technology – impact on the future health and safety of farmers/workers

In the next section, the results of an analysis of selected articles that addressed the research question of **how the use of modern technologies in agriculture impacts the safety, health and well-being of farmers and farmworkers** and follow the selected variables are presented. The results of the selected articles are presented separately for each technology category.

Category: Automatic Milking Systems (AMS)

The selected studies (n = 8) in this category investigated the impact of the use of automatic milking systems (AMS) on farmers' work, safety, health or quality of life. The findings are summarised in two ways. The first presents the researchers' findings in relation to work-related health and quality of life, the second presents the researchers' findings in relation to finances and costs.

1. All farmers ([236_4], [321], [334], [334_1], [321_1], [263], [236_2], [236_1]) *reported that the use of AMS improved their work-related health and quality of life, although it was also argued that the new technology could even increase the volume of work due to higher production:*

1) In the study (2004) [236_4] conducted in four EU countries (Belgium, Denmark, Germany and the Netherlands), the physical health of AMS users improved in 55%, mental health in 41% and sleep quality in 30%. Two thirds of all farmers stated that their quality of life had improved: 86% of all farmers spent more time with their family and 62% spent more time on their hobbies. The researchers found that the improvements in quality of life were relatively independent of the chosen growth strategy. The researchers concluded that the quality of life had largely improved, even among farmers who opted for a growth strategy and thus less leisure time.

2) The authors of the study [321] analysed the changes brought about by the switch from CMS to AMS technology in Finland. The majority of participants ($\geq 74.1\%$) found that AMS made the organisation of farm work more flexible and increased leisure time, quality of life, productivity of dairy farming work and the attractiveness of dairy farming among the younger generation. In addition, the majority ($\geq 71.9\%$) stated that the switch to AMS increased the dairy farmer's own opportunities as well as the opportunities for hired labour and farm helpers to work healthy and injury-free. However, the opportunities to get enough sleep after switching to AMS were rated differently by the participants.

Almost all participants (98.2%) stated that AMS generally reduces physical strain. However, it was also found that daily cleaning of the AMS was physically demanding for 42.5% of participants and that daily handling of rejected milk was somewhat or very physically demanding for 66.2% of dairy farmers. Coping with the daily cow traffic associated with AMS was another issue that was physically demanding for many farmers (28.5%). The majority of respondents mentioned AMS-related work tasks that posed a

risk of injury, such as training heifers and dairy cows to use the AMS, assisting the milking robot and administering medication or grouping cattle.

The vast majority of respondents (94.3%) were of the opinion that AMS generally reduces the risk of injury. The majority (89.5%) also stated that the risk of injury (e.g. from kicking, head-butting and trampling) was reduced by working in close proximity to the dairy cows' hooves. A minority of farmers (34.2 to 46.9 %) reported a lower risk of injury, while around half of the farmers (45.6 to 54.4 %) saw no difference between AMS and CMS.

The majority (87.7%) believed that AMS reduces the overall burden of occupational and other work-related diseases. Similarly, the majority felt that AMS, compared to CMS, reduced the specific risks of respiratory diseases (such as allergic rhinitis, allergic asthma and hypersensitivity pneumonitis caused by organic dust from animals, grain and hay), skin diseases (such as irritant and allergic contact dermatitis caused by cow dander, moisture, dirt, rubber (e.g. in gloves and hay) and allergic dermatitis (in connection with disinfectants and cleaning agents) as well as musculoskeletal disorders (70.2, 91.7 and 96.1 % respectively).

About half (47.8%) found that AMS reduced their mental distress in general. No significant difference in psychological distress was reported by 19.7%, and 31.6% stated that their psychological distress had increased. However, the majority found that switching to AMS had reduced the monotonous, repetitive, fast and hectic nature of milking. These characteristics of the work typically cause both mental stress and physical strain, which are commonly reported in CMS.

The majority (93.4%) mentioned one or more AMS-related problems that cause (some or a lot of) mental stress. Three problems in particular emerged from the responses: night-time alarms triggered by AMS, reliance on farm helpers and/or hired labour to manage milking with AMS, and monitoring 24/7 on-call availability for AMS. Night-time AMS alarms caused psychological stress in 71.5% of participants. The majority (87.3%) had no or only a few night alarms per month, while others had night alarms at least weekly (11.8%) or almost daily (0.9%). For 67.6 of farmers, having to rely on support staff and/or hired labour to deal with the AMS was psychologically stressful. Several farmers (51.7%) felt psychologically stressed by the 24/7 on-call duty required to manage the AMS. In addition to these problems, power outages and high repair and maintenance costs were also cited as causes of mental stress.

3) In the study [334] conducted in Ontario, Canada, the authors concluded that stress experienced by farmers was positively related to the prevalence of severe lameness in cows and was lower in farmers using automation feeding systems. Overall, the better mental health of dairy farmers using robotic milking systems was associated with a lower prevalence of severe lameness in cows and a higher milk protein percentage. In addition, mental health scores differed by feeding method (better mental health in those using automation feeding systems compared to manual feeding) and social environment (better mental health in those working with others compared to those working predominantly alone).

4) The sample of Canadian farmers in study [334_1] reported that overall, producers rated all four themes about improvements and expectations of AMS (improved profitability; improved quality of life; improved quality of life of cows; fulfilled expectations) positively (median scores of 4 or 5 on the 1 to 5 scale), indicating high satisfaction with improved profitability (3.8 ± 0.1 , $P < 0.05$), the improved quality of life of producers (4.5 ± 0.1 , $P < 0.05$) and the improved quality of life of cows (4.5 ± 0.1 , $P < 0.05$). The most frequently cited improvements in quality of life since switching to AMS were greater time flexibility (97% of producers), less stressful and less physically demanding work (37%), easier staff management (14%) and indirectly through better herd health and management (11%).

There was a weak but significant negative correlation between farmers' ratings of the statement "AMS has met expectations" and time since changeover ($r_s = -0.16$, $p = 0.02$). There was also a weak, negative correlation between herd size and the ratings "AMS has improved my quality of life" ($r_s = -0.17$,

$p = 0.01$) and “AMS has met expectations” ($r_s = -0.15$, $p = 0.03$). No differences were found between the ratings of improvements and expectations and the age groups of the farmers ($P \geq 0.17$).

The negative correlation between the statement “The AMS has met expectations” and the time since switching to the AMS means that satisfaction with the AMS has decreased over time. The researchers interpreted the data to mean that older AMS devices may require more maintenance or that newer AMS models have improved and have fewer problems than older versions. However, instead of interpreting the older AMS farms as less satisfied, one could assume that the general understanding of this milking technology has improved, leading to more reasonable expectations among new AMS users.

Two further correlations showed that the quality of life of producers improved to a lesser extent on AMS farms with larger herd sizes and that the expectations of AMS were also met to a lesser extent on AMS farms with larger herd sizes. The researchers pointed out that it was hypothesised that producers with larger herds would not rate the statement “AMS has improved my quality of life” as positively as producers with smaller farms because larger farms would not be able to reduce the number of employees (i.e. employee management) to the same extent as smaller farms. However, no correlation was found between the change in herd size and the change in the number of employees on the farms that switched to AMS. Further research is therefore required to fully understand the extent of these correlations and the possible causes of their negative associations.

5) In a case study [321_1] conducted in Australia, the results showed an interesting finding: farmers with health problems who use AMS are able to continue farming that they would otherwise have given up. In terms of working hours and work patterns, (all 5 AMS farmers) stated that AMS had had a positive impact on their quality of life and that their expectations regarding the impact of the technology have been successfully met - less time spent working/ more flexible working patterns / less physical labour. Farmers no longer have to bring the entire herd to the dairy and no longer have to stand for hours on a concrete floor to manually attach the teat cups - these are the two main physical tasks that can be eliminated with AMS. However, three of the four farmers with previous dairy farming experience agreed that they now do less physical work per day due to the increased production and other work involved. Most farmers agreed that they have more time to focus on management aspects (e.g. pasture management, nutrition, animal health, reproductive performance, milk quality).

6) In a study [263] conducted in Norway, the results showed that differences in the well-being of farmers with AMS, measured as income, job satisfaction, mental health and work-life balance, are related to the characteristics of the farm and the farmer as well as the use of AMS. Farmers with AMS have lower well-being in terms of income and mental health, but higher well-being in terms of work-life balance and increase in leisure time. The use of AMS in long-term planning is associated with a better work-life balance. However, if the farmer experiences data overload, this leads to a decrease in well-being in terms of mental health and causes technostress, also due to the 24/7 on-call time required to manage the AMS. Adequate AMS training and the availability of counselling services are therefore associated with higher mental health well-being.

In addition to the characteristics of the farm and the farmers, the study also investigated whether age is related to well-being. The results show that age has no significant influence on income, job satisfaction, mental health or work-life balance. The hypothesis is that although older farmers have difficulties with the technical features of the milking system, they have expertise that can improve income, job satisfaction, mental health and work-life balance. It is also hypothesised that the positive effects of expertise offset the potential negative effects of advanced technology.

Farmers' well-being in terms of income, job satisfaction, mental health and work-life balance improves significantly when farmers have colleagues. The reason for this is that farmers who use AMS have more social contacts with different experts or interest groups.

7) In the qualitative study [236_2] conducted in Norway, several farmers emphasised that adaptation to AMS takes time. According to the farmers, the clear biggest advantage of AMS is flexibility and more rest and sleep. However, only some of the farmers mentioned a reduced workload as an advantage of AMS. Many of the farmers work just as much as before, but due to the higher production and greater number of animals.

Some farmers emphasised the importance of the social network for their decision to invest in AMS and for their daily work. They can share their experiences with other farmers and ask if something is not working.

The interviews also revealed that the robot's management programme provides farmers with huge amounts of data and a lot of information about the animals, which sparked five farmers' interest in farming, but also brought with it the risk of increased technostress. The results revealed a certain paradox: the increased flexibility of work went hand in hand with the fact that the work never really ends. Farmers are therefore constantly on call, around the clock. But farmers have also adapted their work to the new technologies, e.g. night alarms, and have made certain adjustments to reduce the frequency of night alarms, e.g. by switching off all non-emergency alarms.

8) The study [236_1] investigated how AMS affects the job satisfaction of Norwegian farmers. They found that farmers with AMS are more satisfied with their working day, work safety and working environment than CMS farmers. Farmers with AMS are more often in contact with advisors and other farmers, while CMS farmers can manage their dairy farm alone to a certain extent.

A linear-by-linear test of the three items (I am satisfied with my working day (item 1), I am satisfied with work safety on the farm (item 2) and I am satisfied with the working environment on the farm (item 3)) across the two groups shows that AMS farmers achieve significantly higher values for items 1, 2 and 3 with $Z = -5.999$ ($P < 0.001$), $Z = -2.178$ ($P < 0.005$) and $Z = -5.967$ ($P < 0.001$) respectively. This shows that the AMS farmers have higher job satisfaction than the CMS farmers.

A linear-by-linear association test shows that AMS farmers work significantly more hours compared to CMS farmers, $Z = -4.930$ ($P < 0.001$), and co-operate more frequently with others during their working day, $Z = -5.357$ ($P < 0.001$). However, despite the higher number of working hours, AMS farmers believe they have a more flexible working day, $Z = -6.461$ ($P < 0.001$), more time for their family, $Z = -2.420$ ($P < 0.05$), and more time for friends and leisure activities, $Z = -5.967$ ($P < 0.001$), compared to CMS farmers.

The data also showed that AMS farmers were able to increase their production by an average of 70 per cent as a result of installing the AMS. However, a higher stress level, i.e. a larger milk quota, means more stress for AMS farmers compared to CMS farmers. Increasing feed production means a significant additional workload compared to the pre-AMS situation. In some regions, there is also strong competition for arable land. Overall, this can lead to a higher level of stress, i.e. a higher milk quota means more stress for AMS farmers than for CMS farmers.

II The majority of farmers in this category, i.e. in the articles ([236_4], [334_1], [321_1], [263], [236_1], [236_2]), stated that the use of AMS has long-term financial benefits in combination with other benefits:

1) In the study [236_4], farmers reported an average labour saving of 19.8 %, which increases to 21.3 % if only farms that keep their herd size more or less constant are taken into account. The highest labour savings were found in Belgium (28 %) and the lowest in Denmark (11.5 %).

2) In study [334_1], the researchers concluded that producers rated the first main statement about improvements and expectations of AMS, (1) improved profitability, positively overall (median scores of 4 or 5 on the scale of 1 to 5), indicating a high level of satisfaction with improved profitability (3.8 ± 0.1 , $P < 0.05$).

3) The results of the study [321_1] showed that with the help of the new technology, farmers manage to reduce the total cost of labour used compared to their previous CMS operation by reducing the number of labourers used and/or the number of hours worked. On average, the farms tested achieved a labour efficiency (cows/full-time equivalent) 54% above the regional average.

4) The results of the study [263] show that work-life balance and income are positively correlated with the number of years in which the AMS is used on the farm. Even after attending introductory courses, farmers spend a lot of time “learning-by-doing” on the farm to familiarise themselves with the milking robot. The introduction of the AMS requires a transition period. The data analysis also showed that experience with the AMS increases well-being in relation to income.

5) In study [236_2], farmers reported their dissatisfaction with the high investment and operating costs, although they emphasised that the majority of farmers had significantly increased their production and thus their income.

6) In study [236_1], the data analysis showed that farmers who had installed the AMS were able to increase their production by an average of 70 per cent.

Category: Precision Livestock Farming (PLF)

Only one of the selected studies investigated the effects of the use of Precision Livestock Farming (PLF) on the work, safety, health or quality of life of farmers.

The study ([265]) investigated the use of PLF technology on medium and large farms, namely nine pig farms, five broiler and seven dairy farms. The study concluded that PLF has significant potential to improve animal health, animal welfare and transparency in processing, which is very important for consumer trust. PLF gives them the assurance that the animals are healthy and that production is going well.

Overall, dairy farmers were satisfied with the technology, but cited the high costs as an obstacle. It is important to note that the decision to introduce PLF was not always in the hands of the farmers, but was often due to project-related incentives and free installation of the equipment. This raises the question of the extent to which farmers' perceptions are influenced by external funding. Conversely, pig farmers wanted to use PLF as a means to increase production, while broiler farmers primarily wanted to keep up with technological trends. These different motivations illustrate that the adoption of PLF may be shaped by the broader agricultural context and industry trends rather than the specific needs of the farmers themselves.

Although some farmers recognized the non-invasive nature of PLF as a positive aspect, broiler farmers were still concerned about the high cost of the technology. While dairy farmers appreciated the earlier detection of lameness in cows, some complained about malfunctioning sensors, indicating possible technical reliability issues that could undermine the effectiveness of the system.

The study's conclusion underlines that PLF needs to demonstrate its tangible benefits in areas such as animal welfare and farm profitability for it to be widely adopted. However, the high cost, maintenance burden and unclear understanding of how PLF systems work remain significant barriers. Farmers also expressed dissatisfaction with the fact that the data generated by PLF is controlled by producers, raising concerns about data ownership and transparency.

Category: Drones

Only one of the selected studies analysed the impact of the use of drone technology on farmers' work, safety, health or quality of life. The study conducted in Selangor, Malaysia [501] examined the effectiveness of drones in agricultural production and highlighted their affordability, simplicity and significant benefits in terms of cost savings and operational efficiency. Drones were found to be particularly beneficial in reducing the use of water, pesticides and insecticides. They played a central

role in irrigation and ensured efficient water distribution in rural areas while minimizing wastage. In addition, drones have been used effectively for a variety of agricultural tasks, including mapping, crop monitoring, spraying and seed application.

One of the key benefits was the ability of drones to frequently collect field data, allowing farmers to identify problems immediately and take timely remedial action. The study also pointed out that drones require less time in the field thanks to their intelligent flight modes, which reduces labour and equipment costs.

In disease management, particularly bacterial leaf blight (BLB) in rice farming, drones were praised for their ability to be deployed without farmers having to enter affected areas to prevent the spread of the disease. This represents a significant safety advantage over conventional methods, which often require physical labour in contaminated fields. In addition, the autonomous flight modes of the drones enable targeted spraying so that healthier parts of the field are spared from the chemicals.

However, when critically examining these results, it is important to consider the wider implications of the introduction of drone technology. While drones reduce labour costs, the initial investment and maintenance costs could still be a financial barrier for smallholder farmers. In addition, the reliability of the technology and the need for ongoing training in its use could pose a challenge, particularly in rural areas where there may be a lack of technical expertise. However, the relative success of drone technology in Malaysia could depend on the specific agricultural conditions and type of crops. In regions with different environmental or economic conditions, the cost-benefit ratio and operational feasibility of drones could vary. Therefore, although drones offer promising solutions for Malaysian rice farmers, further research is needed to evaluate their adaptability and sustainability in different agricultural environments and for different types of crops.

Category: *Other Technologies*

Only one of the selected studies examined the impact of the use of different technologies, even if only on dairy farms, on farmers' work, safety, health or quality of life.

The study conducted in New Zealand [236_3] examined the stress levels of dairy farmers in relation to new technologies and products and the use of various agricultural innovations. The results showed that dairy farmers generally experienced no significant stress associated with the introduction of new technologies and only a few technologies caused stress. Of the 13 technologies adopted by farmers, artificial insemination, soil testing, somatic cell counting and mineral supplementation were the most commonly adopted, with adoption rates ranging from 95.4% to 68.6%. In contrast, newer technologies such as feed analysis, computer-based tools for recording data, and maize silage were adopted by a lower percentage of farmers, although many considered them important to their farming needs.

A critical analysis of these results suggests that while the relevance of newer technologies was perceived to be high, actual adoption rates were low, particularly for feed analysis (29.4%) and computer-based tools for feed budgeting tools (18.4%). This discrepancy suggests a potential gap between perceived value and practical application, which could be influenced by factors such as cost, complexity or lack of familiarity with the technology. The study does not elaborate on barriers to adoption, such as financial constraints, lack of technical knowledge or access to training, which are frequently mentioned in other studies on technology adoption in agriculture.

The results in relation to stress show that new technologies rarely cause stress, with "deciding whether new technologies are worth the risk of adoption" and "understanding new technologies" rated as the least stressful. This finding contrasts with studies in other regions where farmers often report significant stress when faced with the uncertainty of adopting new technologies. This raises the question of whether the reported low levels of stress are representative of the general challenges faced by dairy farmers, particularly in less favourable conditions.

The study also compared stress levels between male and female farmers and found that while there were no significant differences in overall stress related to the introduction of new technologies, female farmers experienced more stress in “understanding new technologies” ($t(948) = 2.19, p < .05$; males: $B = 1.73, SD = 0.83$; female farmers: $M = 1.91, SD = 0.86$). This result is consistent with some studies that point to gender differences in technology adoption, particularly in terms of confidence in using and understanding technology.

In addition, the study analysed the correlation between age and stress levels and found small effects, with older farmers reporting higher levels of stress related to understanding and adopting new technologies. However, these correlations were low, and when education level was taken into account, the correlation between age and stress decreased. This suggests that age-related stress could be mitigated by education or experience, which could provide a buffer against the challenges associated with new technologies.

Comparing these findings with other studies on the adoption of agricultural technologies, this study supports the notion that while new technologies can offer significant benefits, the actual adoption process is complex and influenced by a variety of factors beyond mere availability or perceived importance. Barriers such as cost, lack of technical knowledge and external conditions are likely to play a more important role in farmers' decisions than the relatively low stress scores in this study suggest. Therefore, further research is needed to explore the deeper reasons for the discrepancy between perceived importance and actual use and how farmers, especially women and older farmers, can be supported to overcome the challenges of adopting new technologies.

9. Recommendations, good practices and future research

The researchers emphasized the importance of educating and training farmers and farm workers in the use of new technologies and the data they generate to ensure a smooth transition and maximize farm efficiency and productivity. Promoting and demonstrating the effectiveness of these technologies is crucial as it will significantly influence farmers' decision to adopt them. The availability of advisory services is highlighted as essential for providing ongoing technical support to help farmers adapt technologies such as automatic milking systems (AMS) to their specific needs and ensure optimal performance. Finally, the researchers also call for further research into the social aspects of the use of new technologies in agriculture, an area that has been under-researched to date. We have divided what we have just said into four categories that further summarize what we have just said:

1) *Training and educating farmers and farm workers in the use of new technologies and the use of the data they generate to facilitate the transition* ([334_1], [263], [236_2], [321]) is crucial. New technologies are often associated with new safety protocols. Training and education empower farmers by providing them with the skills and knowledge they need to manage their farms independently and proactively. The right training ensures that farmers and farm workers can use new technologies effectively to maximise the efficiency and productivity of their farms. When farmers learn how to interpret and utilise data, they are able to make informed decisions. When they know how to make the best use of these technologies, they achieve the best possible results in terms of yields and resource management. Training facilitates a smooth transition, reduces stress and helps farmers adapt more quickly to new practises and technologies.

2) *Promote new technologies and demonstrate their effectiveness* ([334_1], [265], [334], [321]). Companies developing new technologies need to work with farmers. Some farmers pointed out that demonstrating the effectiveness of a new technology is an extremely important aspect of promotion that determines whether farmers decide to purchase the technology or not

3) *Availability of extension services* ([263], [236_1]). Advisory services aim to support farmers in the effective adoption and utilisation of AMS technology. Their main role is to provide ongoing technical support for operational problems, software updates and hardware maintenance to ensure that the AMS is functions smoothly. They also help farmers adapt the AMS to their specific farm conditions and

management styles, including adjusting for herd size, barn layout, data management and other unique factors that can improve the optimisation and efficiency of the new technology. By fulfilling these functions, extension services play a critical role in helping farmers effectively integrate AMS into their operations to increase productivity, improve animal welfare and promote overall farmer well-being and quality of life.

4) *Further research in this area* ([236_1], [265], [334], [236_2], [236_3], [321_1]). Researchers have identified a significant gap in the current understanding of the social impacts of the introduction of new technologies in agriculture. While the focus has been on the technical and economic benefits of these technologies, there is a need for more comprehensive research on the psychosocial impacts. This includes how the introduction of new technologies affects the relationships between farmers and farm workers, their sense of belonging and the general well-being of those working in agriculture. In addition, reliance on technology can change traditional roles in farming households and communities, affecting the division of labour and decision-making processes. Understanding these social dimensions is critical to developing strategies that ensure that the benefits of technology are shared equitably and that the process of technology adoption strengthens rather than weakens social ties within farming communities.

APPENDIX 6: REPORT FROM THE WORKSHOP ON PSYCHOSOCIAL STRESSORS/RISKS IN FARMING

Held on 20 June 2024, Zoom meeting from 15:00 (CET) to 16:45.

Participants (in order of presentation):

Majda Černič Istenič, Nataša Dernovšček Hafner; Alin Croitoru, David Rose, Salvatore Barilla, Emmanuelle Hedio, David Meredith

SafeHabitus WP4 Workshop Summary

Objectives

1. Assess and identify gaps in current farming stressors
2. Identify vulnerable populations exposed to specific stressors
3. Identify resources/approaches needed to prevent/manage psychosocial stressors

Discussion: Key Themes

1. Culture of Farming

- Migration background and family separation stress
- Masculinity and self-esteem issues
- Illusion of temporality for migrant workers
- Invisibility and uncertainty in subcontracting models
- Challenges for non-farming families entering agriculture
- Intergenerational interactions and work dynamics

2. Social Protection

- Lack of social security for part-time and migrant workers
- Language and cultural barriers affecting access to benefits
- Difficulties in accessing social security for displaced workers within the EU
- Work-life balance issues, lack of holidays and statutory leave

3. Stress Factors in Farming

- Social expectations and criticism on social media
- Rural crime
- Intersectionality of different stress factors
- Uncertainty and time pressure
- Food security concerns

4. New Technologies in Agriculture

- Differing impacts on farm owners vs. farmworkers
- Adaptation to new regulatory systems
- Potential benefits: reduced workload, more family time, reduced injury risks

5. Drivers of Change

- Impact on part-time farmers
- Challenges for subsistence farmers
- Uncertainty and time pressure as significant stressors
- Food security as an emerging stressor

Additional Considerations

- Importance of including farm families as vulnerable groups
- Need for social rights and guarantees for farmers and workers in the EU
- Variations in stressors based on demographics, production type, and location
- Access to basic resources (healthcare, childcare, emergency services) in some regions
- Impact of policy shifts and market trends
- Past trauma among farmers
- Labor shortages and access to reliable workers
- Engagement with global vs. local agricultural economies
- Critique of overemphasis on cultural explanations for mental health issues
- Understudied aspects of social protection in agriculture
- Methodological concerns in stress and mental health research in agriculture

Recommendations

1. Conduct more empirical research to understand effective interventions
2. Consider structural changes alongside efforts to change culture or individual behavior
3. Involve a multidisciplinary approach, including anthropologists, geographers, political scientists, and historians
4. Ensure recommendations are nuanced and account for knowledge gaps

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